
*Conceptualising the impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Institutions
(HEIs)*

A critical assessment of the impact and practices in Scottish HEIs

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A Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement of the University of
the West of Scotland for the Award of Doctor of Business Administration
(DBA).

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

My sincere gratitude goes to my supervision team – Dr Anne Clare Gillon (Director of Studies), Professor Dominic Elliot (Second Supervisor), Professor Heather Tarbert (Assessor) and also to Professor Edward Borodzicz – who was my second supervisor at the start of this study. Professor Dominic Elliot did the unthinkable – I am honoured that despite the very short notice, Professor Dominic agreed to join the supervisory team as my second supervisor and created time from his very busy schedule to review my work in good time and many thanks for your insightful comments, advice and constructive criticisms. Dr Anne Clare has been pivotal to the completion of this thesis. Her encouragement gave me the strength to carry on when all seemed lost and her insightful comments and guidance was second to none. Words may fail to show my appreciation, but in the absence of a better word, I wish to say THANK YOU!

I would like to say a big thank you to my friends and colleagues too numerous to mention. Through their constant support and encouragement, I have been able to overcome this herculean task that at some point seemed insurmountable.

Also, no amount of thanks would be enough to show my gratitude to my wonderful siblings – Commodore U.J. Egbele retd., Mrs Ehi-Douglas O.M. (who is like my second mum), Mr. Mathew Egbele, Mr Francis Egbele, Mrs Judith Igbinhi, Barr. Tom. O. Egbele – who never rested on their oars to offer every needed support both financially and otherwise in ensuring this dream is actualised. To my wonderful Mum – Mrs M.O. Egbele – her prayers and support kept me going even through thick and thin.

Finally, to my wonderful family: my dearly beloved wife – Rosemary who has been my pillar, my rock and confidant. Thank you for all your support, encouragement and prayers – I LOVE YOU loads. To my lovely kids: Adley, Alvin and Aziel – thank you all for all your understanding. Throughout the duration of this study, I know my attention has been divided towards you all and some of the time I wasn't always there when you needed me most. I am deeply sorry; but I am grateful for your understanding and support, we have seen this to a successful completion.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to God Almighty for giving me the grace to complete this study successfully. Despite all the challenges that came along, the Lord was with me and gave me the grace and strength to conquer.

Also, to my late Dad – Mr. M.E. Egbele, this would have brought you joy seeing your son achieve this feat; but I know you are happy and proud where you are. Thank you for giving me the foundation to build upon.

Finally, I dedicate it to my family – Rosemary (my better half), Adley, Alvin and Aziel – without whom, this dream wouldn't have been actualised. God bless you all.

ABSTRACT

Universities before now have always regarded themselves as unique entities different from corporate businesses and other non-for-profit organisations thus due to their collegiate enclave, they were generally thought to be free from risk. However, changes to the university structure due to globalisation, technological changes, New Public Management (NPM) and other factors have brought about competition, internationalisation as well as reports of natural disasters and scandalous events from some universities across the globe have made these establishments to rethink their stance on risk and risk management and also brought about increased scrutiny from the public and regulatory directives for greater accountability from these Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs). Therefore, it is on this premise that this thesis intends to **‘Conceptualise the impact of Risk Management in Scottish Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs)**, with the aim to critically assess the impact and effects of risk management on the structures and practices of Higher Institutions in the UK with a direct focus on Scottish HEIs only.

The study was founded on the pragmatist philosophy and mix-methods research design was adopted; using the explanatory sequential mixed-method approach, quantitative data was initially gathered from every university across Scotland in order to evaluate the structures and practices of risk management in the HEI context and also to determine which institutions that have established and institutionalised risk management framework as required by regulatory authorities. Establishing this context was essential towards the selection of case institutions and participants for the qualitative phase of the study. Thus, in-depth interviews were conducted with risk experts as well as documents sourced from six case institutions and these qualitative data were analysed thematically.

Findings from the study were integrated at various stages of the study: ‘the design stage’, ‘methods stage’ and at ‘interpretation and reporting phase’, majorly through ‘common unique identifiers or overarching themes. Through these key themes (‘Policies and Procedures of Risk Management’, Attitudes and Approach Towards Institutional Risk Management’ and Strategies to Manage Institutional Risk’) the researcher was able to simplify and successfully integrate the findings (both quantitative and qualitative) of the research to achievement of each

specific research objective (enumerated in chapter 6.1) for greater understanding and clarity and validity of the study.

Thus, some key findings revealed that although HEIs have been mandated by regulatory authorities to adopt a risk management framework for more accountability, however enhancement of decision-making seems to be the overarching objective while HEIs have actually taken the step to adopt a risk management framework – however, most institutions are yet to fully entrench risk management into their University-wide and governance process. The study also revealed that although there is an increased level of confidence from stakeholders brought about by their risk management practices, however, uncertainties regarding Brexit is affecting HEIs strategic planning, administration and implementation programs.

Risk management in the academic world is quite a new phenomenon and thus there has been no academic research to this effect in the UK prior to this study. Therefore, this research has comprehensively and critically evaluated and discussed all aspects of risk and risk management as it affects HEIs thus it would be useful to both HEIs and regulators as it would be a reference document for them to gauge their risk management process and practices and understand how they might continuously improve on their risk management models. The researcher also believes that this study would motivate academics to research further on risk management in the academic cycle. Furthermore, further research would be to examine how administrative bureaucracies due to compliance and risk management may impact and affect the teaching-research quality in HEIs.

Finally, the future focus of this study is to investigate on how best to institutionalise risk management practices and processes into the basic fabrics and culture of the institution while also developing a risk management model or framework that is unique to the university environment as against the current generic frameworks that have been designed specifically for firms within the financial and non-financial organisations without considering the uniqueness of academic establishments.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 RATIONALE BEHIND THE STUDY

The present-day world is one that is preoccupied with the notion of risk. Sophistication and technological changes have brought in uncertainties, more complexities and risk to the global society and environment. Examples in the UK and rest of the world such as the ‘Brent Spar affair’ (Löfstedt and Renn, 1997; Jordan, 1998), ‘Chernobyl disaster’ (Havenaar et.al., 2003), the last global financial melt-down (Llewellyn, 2007; Keasey and Veronessi, 2008; Goodhart, 2009), terrorist attacks in major cities across the globe (Borodzicz, 2005; Sandler and Enders, 2008; Krueger, 2018) just to name a few have called for major concerns and reawakening for risk reduction to its barest minimum. Borodzicz (2005) opines that these concerns are not alien to humans since risk and the management of risk qualifies as one of the oldest human activity.

Consequently, Risk management (RM) has become a major organisational activity in various sectors in the world-over such as: finance (Hood et.al, 2001), education (Rothstein et.al, 2006; Huber, 2010), charities (Groso et.al, 2012), housing (Klinke and Renn, 2012) etc. Besides, international organisations such as the European Commission and OECD regards RM as a standard practice and as such, management of risk has become a major tradition or ritual enshrined in the corporate governance codes of private sector organisations and has also recently crept into the public sector (Huber and Rothstein, 2013) though Universities have always been regarded as a not-for-profit organisation thus, many thought that the introduction of risk management to the educational circle would disrupt the culture, nature and environment of institutions.

Although Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) have operated successfully in the past without major significant events though they had strategies for minimising hazards and compliance management, however, these cannot be substituted for a holistic risk management because such activities were usually reactive to events and only focuses on down-side risk events and it is evident that there is increase in the multiplicity, type and magnitude of risks affecting HEIs as a result of globalisation and other external factors with the impact of unmitigated risks and the consequences of opportunities missed becoming more significant (NACUBO, 2007). However, global dynamism, uncertainties and events such that happened in the United States

just over a decade ago i.e., ‘Virginia Tech tragedy’, ‘Hurricane Katharina’, the New Orleans Saga etc., (Fraser et.al., 2014) were indication of the need for HEIs to adopt a holistic risk management framework.

Thus, in 2001, the Higher Education Funding Council in England (HEFCE) instructed all HEIs in England to adopt a holistic Risk management framework and not long the Scottish Funding Council (SFC) issued same directive for all HEIs in Scotland to implement a model for a holistic risk management within their institutions. As such, HEIs gradually began implementation of RM framework based on their structure, institutional culture, geographical location and other external factors. Though the adoption and implementation of RM frameworks and models within the academic environment is gaining momentum however, empirical research in this area is limited compared to other organisational sectors.

It is useful to note that while this study was being finalised, it coincided with the global pandemic situation of COVID 19 coupled with uncertainties of Brexit. These situations and the aftermath of them have posed great risk and uncertainties in every sector as well as the educational sector which is the focus of this research. These undoubtedly, will be areas for many future studies on risk strategy and management.

1.2 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Having carried out consultations through library materials and online academic resources, it was discovered that there are separate regulatory bodies within the UK academic system. Therefore, the scope and parameters of this study had to be restricted only to HEIs in Scotland (since the researcher is a student in a Scottish University, i.e. The University of the West of Scotland) because of the separate legislation that exists between Scottish HEIs and HEIs in other parts of the UK – in order to ensure a valid, measurable and generalisable findings and results. As such, the scope and spectrum of the study (Marrelli, 2007; Baxter and Jack, 2008) entailed a careful selection (informed judgement from quantitative strand of the study) of some institutions that have a fully embedded risk management framework as case reference (discussed in chapter 3).

1.3 RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS

Prior to the commencement of this study, the researcher had already been conversant with private sector risk management coupled with having an MSc in Financial Services, Risk and Operations and a professional member of the Chartered Institute for loans and risk management of Nigeria (CILRM). Although, the researcher has a good knowledge of private sector risk management, his inquisitiveness regarding Risk Management (RM) in HEIs was aroused after reading an article which argued that introducing RM in HEIs would be counter-productive because it would distort and disorganise the system, structure and the culture of Universities (Huber, 2010). Upon further research, the researcher discovered that very limited empirical studies have been carried out regarding RM in Universities globally and with none so far published in the UK as at the time of commencing this study compared to numerous studies on RM in other organisational sectors. This gap in literature further provoked the researcher's interest to investigate the RM practices and composition within UK HEIs.

Furthermore, because of the distinctive and unique features of HEIs such as 'shared governance' structures, decentralised decision-making and implementation, institutional culture etc., (Charette, 2012; McNally, 2015) as compared to other organisations, the researcher was keen to investigate the composition of RM and its impact on the structures, practices and processes in Scottish HEIs and to understand its adoption, development, integration and changes if any in relation to implementation. This led to the research aim and subsequently the research objectives as well as research questions as highlighted below.

1.3.1 Research Aim

The aim of this research is to critically assess the impact and effects of risk management on the structures and practices of Higher Institutions in Scottish HEIs.

1.3.2 Research Objectives

1. To evaluate the structures and practices of risk management within the HEI context.
2. To analyse the patterns of adjustment subsequent to adoption, implementation and/or restructuring of the risk management framework
3. To investigate the implications of risk management practices in HEIs

1.3.3 Research Questions

1. How do HEIs structure and execute their risk management functions?
2. How do the different institutional and technical factors influence the adoption and implementation of HEIs risk management frameworks?
3. What are the impact and effects of risk management in HEIs?
4. How can HEIs advance and align their risk management architecture to better suit the needs of their business contexts?

1.3.4 Research Methods

The sequential mixed methods design was used to address the objectives and research questions of this study. As with every sequential mixed methods study, this research was conducted in phases whereby the quantitative strand of the study was conducted first to inform and build on the later phase (qualitative). Likert scale questionnaires were used in the initial phase of the study primarily ‘to evaluate the structures and practices of risk management across Scottish HEIs’ and also to provide relevant information and guidance on other research objectives and research questions as well as providing the needed information for selecting case institutions and participant selection (see chapter 3.5).

Consequently, the second strand of the study involved interviews with risk experts from case institutions. These risk experts were mainly senior risk managers or senior executive personnel involved in risk management decision making process of the case institutions. Because RM is a specialised activity and function in every organisation, it was essential that only persons with the relevant knowledge and expertise should be interviewed for a reliable, credible and valid findings. Thus, these persons were identified through ‘purposive expert sampling technique’ (see chapter 3.6.2). Furthermore, to enhance the validity and credibility of the study, documents were sourced from case institutions to corroborate findings from the interview and were analysed thematically alongside the transcribed interview data.

The documents were all publicly available on the websites of the various institutions thus because they are not linked to any individual, it would therefore not be of detriment or cause harm to any individual or organisation. Although ‘document analysis’ was not part of the original plan for this research, however, it was useful in complementing and corroborating

(triangulation) results and findings of the study which indeed enhanced the validity and credibility of this research.

1.4 SUMMARY OF CHAPTERS

Chapter 1. Introduction

This chapter detailed the background of the study and also outlined the overarching aim, research objectives and questions, alongside a summary of the research methods employed for the study. Subsequent chapters in this study are therefore summarised below.

Chapters 2 Literature Review

Chapters 2 of this study is a comprehensive review of literature which discussed about the evolution of risk and risk management. It provides details about some of the major models and general processes for modern day risk management. Furthermore, it looks at the UK higher educational context and how the educational system in the UK has evolved over time while highlighting the various categories of HEIs in the UK. Additionally, it provides details about risk and risk management in the UK educational sector.

Chapter 3 Methodology

This chapter being the glue that binds the entire study together, presents the study's research aim, objectives and research questions and the methods employed in investigating the research problem as well as discussing the rationale behind and the justification for the methods/approach/choice adopted for the research explaining the why's and the how's these methods have been used. It also discusses how results and findings from the quantitative and qualitative phases were integrated as well as discussing ethical considerations and delimitation of the study.

Chapter 4 Presentation of Results and Analysis from the Quantitative Study.

This presents the results and analysis from the quantitative phase of the study. This quantitative phase of the study was vital in evaluating the structure and practices of risk management within the HEI context, selection of case universities, participants for the qualitative phase as well as informing and building on the findings of the qualitative research.

Chapter 5 Results from the Qualitative Interview and Document Analysis

This chapter presents findings from the qualitative phase of the research. As discussed in chapter 3 of this research, qualitative interviews alongside documents sourced from case institutions were analysed thematically while themes from the analysis formed the basis of the discussion and findings from the study.

Chapter 6 Conclusion

In this concluding chapter of this study research questions were readdressed in conjunction with the key empirical findings to demonstrate how through the research questions the aim and objectives of the study have been addressed and how the study has contributed to knowledge and the wider implication of the study to all stakeholders. The study also presented recommendations based on key findings from both the qualitative and quantitative strands of the research. Limitations to the study and areas for further research were also discussed. And finally, personal reflection and final remarks were presented concluded this chapter and research.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

INTRODUCTION

The chapter looks at the evolution of risk and the historical underpinnings of Risk Management, while also discussing some of the key risk management models and their practicability. At the time of writing up this chapter in mid-2017, the risk management frameworks (COSO and ISO 31000) discussed here had not been updated by the relevant bodies (i.e., COSO and ISO), thus the prevailing versions were captured in this study. However, updated versions of these frameworks were released later in 2017 and 2018 respectively by COSO and ISO and these updated versions have also been captured in this chapter. The chapter also discusses considerations in selecting a risk management model while the chapter also presents discussions regarding the generic risk management process.

Furthermore, this chapter takes a critical look at the UK Higher Education context and its evolution to date. It discusses key factors responsible for some of the major changes that have occurred in the educational sector and the impact of regulation and risk management in addressing the challenges of the sector while also discussing some major risks that threaten Higher Educational Institutions' (HEIs) in achieving their strategic goals and objectives. Finally, this chapter details some of the key challenges HEI regulators may encounter in their duties as well as the risk culture in HEIs.

2.1 BRIEF OVERVIEW OF RISK

Risks have always been associated with human activity and existence (Borodzicz, 2005; Hollnagel, 2008) and its field of research commenced as much early as humans began to imagine the possibility of their own demise whereas seeking ways to circumvent hazardous circumstances (Renn, 1998). However, it was not until the early years of the 19th century that it became associated with equipment and system failures (Hollnagel, 2008) although (Aven, 2011) reports that the statistical tools for risk assessment had been developed over a century before actual risk analyses were even tested on 'technical systems'.

There are claims by some authors that the systematic study of risk started in 1968 with the seminal article of 'Chauncy Starr on risk and voluntariness' (Starr, 1974; Kates and Kasperson, 1983; Covello and Mumpower, 1985). While (Kolluru, 1995) counteracts that it began in the

early 1950s during the design of programmes for space exploration with the development and implementation of probabilistic tools for safety analysis and yet again, there is another school of thought which is of the opinion that the earliest risk assessment carried out relates to the studies of nuclear or chemical power plants (Society, 1983). However, despite the several dates or timelines quoted by various authors, the general consensus is that the scientific, systematic study of risk or modern risk management (as some literature puts it) began after the second world war (Renn, 1998; Borodzicz, 2005; Hollnagel, 2008; Dionne, 2013).

2.1.1 Risk Defined

There is actually no consensus to the definition of risk. A study of literature reveals various ways risk concept have evolved and have been defined over the years ranging from definitions centred around probability (Kaplan and Garrick, 1981; Kaplan, 1991; Graham et al., 1995; Willis, 2007), expected values or chance (Willis, 2007), uncertainties (Rosa, 1998; 2003; Aven and Renn, 2009) to danger or undesirable events (Lowrance, 1976).

Holton (2004) argues that two factors are important for risk to exist which are: uncertainty regarding the probable effects from an event and secondly that the outcomes should be important to providing utility or something of a significant value. There is an age-long debate as regards risk and uncertainty. (Knight, 1921) in his formative work, distinguished between risk and uncertainty, arguing that the words ‘risk’ and ‘uncertainty’ are often mis-used in daily interactions and/or economic discussions. According to him:

“Uncertainty must be taken in a sense radically distinct from the familiar notion of Risk, from which it has never been properly separated. The term "risk," as loosely used in everyday speech and in economic discussion, really covers two things which, functionally at least, in their causal relations to the phenomena of economic organization, are categorically different. ... The essential fact is that "risk" means in some cases a quantity susceptible of measurement, while at other times it is something distinctly not of this character; and there are far-reaching and crucial differences in the bearings of the phenomenon depending on which of the two is really present and operating. ... It will appear that a measurable uncertainty, or "risk" proper, as we shall use the term, is so far different from an unmeasurable one that it is not in effect an uncertainty at all”. Knight (1921, pp. 19-20).

In summary therefore, from the above, Knight initially used the word ‘uncertainty’ as an umbrella term but however distinguished between risk and uncertainty in terms of value measurement. Whereas risk can be quantified while uncertainty cannot. (Hubbard, 2009)

remains critical of this assertion because according to him, the ‘Knightian’ theory falls short in acknowledging risk as a form of loss. According to Hubbard (2009; p.80), risk is “*A state of uncertainty where some of the possibilities involve a loss, injury, catastrophe, or other undesirable outcome (i.e., something bad could happen)*”.

Conversely, (Damodaran, 2007) is of the opinion that risk should not be construed to only reflect negative outcomes or consequences. He hypothetically presented his argument with a Chinese symbol for risk (as shown below) which he termed a combination of danger (crisis) and opportunity and which according to him, perfectly captures the dyad of risk (i.e., upside and downside).

Chinese Risk Symbol:

危險

Source: Damodaran (2007).

Hubbard (2009) is highly critical that risk should also be defined to include opportunities because according to him, it lacks substance. He retorts that there is already a word that fits that purpose (uncertainty) and further argued that adhering to that notion would be a deviation from the original connotation of risk and undermine its literary meaning as contained in all English dictionaries since not one of them made mention of it as a form of or even ‘the possibility of a positive outcome’. It may be bias to make assertions based on the English word alone since research has shown that risk is a concept that has evolved overtime and originally not an English word (Cline, 2004; Aven, 2012).

Nonetheless, the debate regarding the definition of risk seem not to be ending anytime soon. Some literature (Douglas and Wildavsky, 1983; Aven, 2011; Šotić and Rajić, 2015) suggests that the various definition accorded risk over the years have resulted due to evolution of time and events associated with risk and available knowledge depending on the area of specialisation or the relevant field of discourse such as ‘economics’, ‘psychology’, ‘engineering’, ‘finance’, medicine etc.; as specific and distinct areas requires different and diverse views to risk and its management framework. And as Hubbard (2009, p.21) succinctly puts it; “*Institutions evolve, standards are codified, and professions mature in such a way that it causes all of us to think in more limited ways than we need to*”.

However, it is startling how little agreement there is therefore to the definition of risk; despite the ubiquity of risk to every human engagement, which is why Hubbard (2009) raised concerns and regards the use of the word “risk” as arbitrary and vague while referring to it as one of the weak points to the management of risk. But (Curtis and Carey, 2012) believes that so far in the 21st century, there has been quite a consensus to the definition of risk which has been built around a function of ‘likelihood and impact’. Holton (2004) and (Hillson, 2016) claim that any risk definition should essentially encompass ‘uncertainty’, ‘effect or consequence’ and ‘measured against defined objectives’. This gives credence to the definition of risk that has become generally popular by practitioners which as defined by ISO 31000 (2009; p.8) is the “*effect of uncertainties on objectives*”. Where effect is regarded as a “*deviation from the expected*” that could either be positive and/or negative.

From the foregoing therefore, the definition of risk by Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) as presented below has been adopted for the purpose of this discourse not only for the fact that it is similar to the widely accepted definition by ISO 31000 as stated above, but also because; it captures both the likelihood of creating opportunities and threats in its definition. Moreover, being *de facto* regulator of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) in most parts of the UK, hence using HEFCE’s view of risk will present an opportunity to critically and holistically assess the implications of risk management in the educational sector.

HEFCE (2001; p.4) defines risk as ‘*the threat or possibility that an action or event will adversely or beneficially affect an organisation’s ability to achieve its objectives*’. This definition allows HEFCE to offer a direct relationship between objectives and risk which according to them, “*objectives include taking opportunities such as launching a new course or winning a new research contract*”. Hence “*the risk of taking or not taking these opportunities may significantly affect the achievement of the institution’s objectives*” (HEFCE, 2001; p.4). The process of identifying and taking these opportunities as well as proactively identifying and mitigating any actions or events that may adversely affect or prevent an organisation from achieving its goals is known as risk management.

Some key discussions on the overview of risk as presented thus far in the above paragraphs is to help understand the dynamism of risk in order to fully comprehend the overarching purpose of this research. Critical examination to the definition of risk were discussed to enable the

researcher to adopt a working definition for this study. Therefore, going by this definition which relates to risk management – identifying and taking opportunities as well as proactively identifying and mitigating events that may affect the achievement of organisational targets, the next section will seek to understand and discuss what risk management entails as it relates to the objectives of this research.

2.2 RISK MANAGEMENT

2.2.1 Overview and Historical underpinnings

We now live in a society that is preoccupied with the notion of risk. As technology keeps changing and becoming more and more sophisticated, so has risk. Examples in the UK and world over such as the ‘Brent Spar affair’ (Löfstedt and Renn, 1997; Jordan, 1998), ‘Chernobyl disaster’ (Havenaar et.al., 2003), the last global financial met-down (Llewellyn, 2007; Keasey and Veronessi, 2007; Goodhart, 2009), terrorist attacks in major cities across the globe (Borodzicz, 2005; Sandler and Enders, 2008; Krueger, 2018) just to name a few have called for major concerns and reawakening for risk reduction to its barest minimum. Borodzicz (2005) opines that these concerns are not alien to humans since risk and its management qualifies as one of the oldest human activity. In his words:

“From the time of primitive ‘oracles’ to a contemporary world of science, risk has and continues to perplex humankind. All societies, both traditional and modern, face choices and decisions about how to confront risk. ... Despite some of the most dramatic technological advances over the last 150 years, we now appear to live in a more dangerous world than ever before...it would be wrong to presume that risk and security is a modern concern. The management of risk is probably among the oldest recorded human activities.” (Borodzicz, 2005; pp.1-2).

Although Risk management (RM) has evolved down the years (please see Appendix 2.1 for some key events and milestones regarding the evolution of risk management over the years) to checkmate these ever-growing and dynamic uncertainties, unfortunately, Cassidy (2005) believes that very little success has been achieved in terms of proactive RM. The perceptions, ideas and tools of RM over the past decade have changed the way organisations both in the private and public establishments regularly manage their growing range of likely adverse effects associated with their businesses. There seems to be no constraint to the range of negative outcomes that are obviously perceived as risk needed to be managed: such as risks emanating from operational, legal, security, ethical, reputational etc. Ewald (1991; p. 199) summarises that; “*Nothing is a risk in itself; there is no risk in reality. But on the other hand, anything can*

be a risk; it all depends on how one analyses the danger, considers the event". Thus, organisations have expanded their RM scope beyond just financial loss or health and safety.

Suffice to say that management of adverse situations has been an age long tradition (Borodzicz, 2005; Cassidy, 2005). However, what seems to be interesting is the manner in which the management of risk has evolved as a new and unique discipline with peculiar set of normative theories or frameworks for analysing, outlining and responding to information and events with potential negative effects (Renn, 1998), which is why Hubbard (2009; p.21) sees RM as "*...a very old idea that has recently taken on somewhat of a new character*".

However, some literature (COSO, 2004; NACUBO and AGB 2007; Pargarch and Warr, 2010; Arena et.al., 2010) are of the view that RM frameworks are often regarded as rational, efficient and generally applicable ways of checkmating organisational activities without impacting negatively on entrepreneurialism. Within the western world, risk management has become a major organisational activity in various sectors namely: finance (Hood et.al, 2001), education (Rothstein et.al, 2006; Huber, 2010), charities (Groso et.al, 2012), housing (Klinke and Renn, 2012) etc. Besides, international organisations such as the European Commission and OECD regard RM as a standard practice and as such, management of risk under the guise of 'Enterprise Risk Management' – (ERM) has become a major tradition or ritual enshrined in the corporate governance codes of private sector organisations and has also recently crept into the public sector (Huber and Rothstein, 2013).

In spite of the widespread popularity and investment on RM in various organisational sectors in recent years, there are concerns however, as several analysts contends the extent to which risk management theories are able to meet the challenges of organisational practices or whether they are actually 'fit for purpose remains to be seen (Hutter and Power, 2005; Miller, 2005; Leveson et.al, 2009; Gephart et.al., 2009). Conversely, Huber and Rothstein, (2013) opines that despite these wide range of practices regarding RM, it is nonetheless based upon the assumption that it does not seek to eliminate all potential risks as it is not only costly and may create unintended results but will also result in a wild goose chase should attempts be made to do so.

It is imperative to note however that research in organisational studies shows that organisations often resist attempts to changes in age-long enshrined practices (Piderit, 2001; Burke, 2017), to which risk management may not be an exception due to the fact that its practices may conflict with long held traditions in the establishments. Nevertheless, some significant researches on ERM within the private and financial sector suggests that it has the tendency to become disconnected or decoupled from already existing organisational practices (Power, 2009; Arena et.al., 2010; Mikes, 2011) to which Power (2009) famously termed the ‘risk management of nothing’ which amounts to nothing more than a knee-jerk reaction from an increasing growth in audit culture, with little or even counterproductive effects on business operations.

Furthermore, Arena et.al., (2010) opines that, RM models such as ERM, Integrated Risk management (IRM) and their likes, emerged as a result of changing institutional and organisational environment with the dire need for transparency and accountability as against what critics believes to be their technical promise while Huber and Rothstein (2013) joined their voices to buttress this argument further that RM does not actually challenge pre-existing organisational practices, but rather it “*acts in subtler ways to reflect and reinforce existing organisational understandings and practices*” (Huber and Rothstein, 2013: p.3).

2.3 RISK MANAGEMENT IN MODERN TIMES

Managing risk is a fundamental concern in today’s global dynamic environment. In recent years, there has been a paradigm shift from the historical traditional perspective to a new dimension of RM which has seen three evolutionary phases namely: Traditional Risk Management (TRM), Advanced Risk Management (ARM) and the Strategic Risk Management approach (Gallagher, 2009). Some literature, however, recognise just two stages of RM i.e., Traditional Risk Management (TRM) and Integrated risk management approach (D’Arcy and Brogan, 2001), while some others see the advanced, integrated or strategic methods as one and same and often refer to it as Enterprise Risk Management (Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2003; Beasley et.al., 2007; Berg, 2010; Simona-Lulia, 2014). This study will however present the three different approaches hereunder for a proper understanding of the evolution of RM to-date but will subsequently adopt the general term ERM which has become a fashionable term among Risk practitioners.

2.3.1 Traditional Risk Management

Traditional risk management (TRM) is a system of RM often used to describe a process whereby each business units or departments in an organisation is solely responsible for the management of its own risk which is conventionally regarded as RM in silos. This model of RM was entirely focused on loss prevention i.e., pure risk and therefore Insurance and Hedging were seen as best measures often used by organisations to limit loss outcomes (Gallagher, 2009).

Historically TRM was credited to have reduced firms' earnings volatility through reduction in the probability of devastating losses (Hoyt and Liebenberg, 2011; 2015). However, it has been widely criticised by a host of analysts as it is said to have been characterised by several inadequacies emanating from lack of harmonisation among the various proliferated risk management departments in the organisation and therefore have failed to pass-on an accurate information of aggregated risk to management and board (Lam, 2000; 2003; D'Arcy and Brogan, 2001; Dabari and Saidin, 2014; Hoyt and Liebenberg, 2015). Although the TRM is still being used today solely by some organisations, Kemp and Patel (2011) have it that firms only use the TRM approach because of the following reasons:

- *“As a result of the organisations historical structure which may be difficult or may take quite long to alter,*
- *The benefits of modern technique are yet to be fully grasped and understood by the Board members; or*
- *Individuals with the relevant expertise to implement the new risk framework may not be readily available or it could also be as a result of some limitations that has emanated from the internal organisational framework or structure”.*

(Kemp and Patel, 2011, pp.32-33)

2.3.2 Advanced Risk Management

Dionne (2013) reckons that in the mid -1950s, there were apparent deficiencies observed in the TRM approach coupled with rising cost of insurance premiums, therefore alternative forms of RM began to emerge and led to several contingency planning actions which saw the advancement of risk management taking a different approach whereby risk was being quantified, standardised and evaluated while several statistical tools for measuring and managing risk were also developed. An example is the early 1970s, financial risk (culminating from: fluctuations in interest rates and prices, foreign exchange rate volatility, etc.) which

emerged as a major source of concern and uncertainty for institutions and in reaction, instruments were developed to handle these uncertainties.

However, by the early 1980s, financial risk had become a major turmoil to institutions and D'Arcy (1999) reckons that although RM tools to manage financial risk had been developed a decade earlier, but organisations did not apply these techniques and tools because they had ignorantly and wrongly classified all risks as pure risk and hence risk managers were simply comfortable with the traditional risk management approach and were not willing to expand their knowledge learning new techniques. D'Aarcy and Brogan (2001) concludes that such failure and ignorance became very costly to firms and the RM field altogether.

Gallagher (2009) refers to the transformation phase of RM as the Advanced Risk Management (ARM) stage which unlike the TRM that had a negative perception of risk and was focused on risk transfer, the ARM however, views risk as an expense and its focus is on how to reduce the cost associated with risk. Also, unlike the TRM, the ARM approach to RM enabled organisations to become proactive and also brought about some collaboration among various departments in managing their risk thereby gradually jettisoning silo form of RM (Kageyama, 2014).

2.3.3 Strategic Risk Management

The strategic risk management approach views risk as uncertainty and thus it is aimed at aligning risk opportunities to the organisation's corporate objectives thereby taking advantage of the positive prospects while at the same time mitigating the downside risk in achieving the firm's goals by the use of various analytical tools in identifying and evaluating a wide range of risk (Kageyama, 2014). This approach involves a holistic RM approach as against the silo-based perspective and often involves a top-down approach, but ensures that everyone is not just risk aware, but also involved in the management process thereby ensuring risk is often mitigated at its originating unit (Gordon et.al., 2009).

The strategic risk management is seen by many as significantly similar to other modern risk management frameworks namely: integrated risk management, enterprise risk management, enterprise-wide risk management, business risk management, holistic risk management etc. (Lienbenberg and Hoyt, 2003; Drew et.al, 2006; D'Arcy, 2001; Kageyama, 2014) while

Kageyama (2014) even regard them as one and same, which has recently adopted a common and fashionable term ERM. Therefore, as mentioned earlier, for the purpose of this study, the term ERM (discussed in more detail in section 2.4) has been adopted hereafter.

It should be noted that these stages of RM as discussed above, vary from firm to firm. It does not necessarily mean that one stage is totally wiped out to give way for the next framework. As RM process has evolved overtime, the previous process is incorporated or becomes the foundation for the next framework or process. For instance, organisations in today's world still purchase insurance even though they have fully adopted modern frameworks for RM (Simoniulia, 2014; Kageyama, 2014). Please refer to Appendix 2.2 for a representation of the above discourse on the evolution of risk management.

2.4 ENTERPRISE RISK MANAGEMENT (ERM)

There have always been diverse views among several authors and regulatory bodies over what ERM entails. Before ERM became fashionably popular in the risk management world, several literatures have at some time in the past initiated or aired their views on some RM concepts such as: “total risk management” (Haimes, 1991), “enterprise-wide risk management” (Manab et.al, 2010), “strategic risk management” (Frigo and Anderson, 2011), “integrated risk management” (Miller, 1992) etc. As highlighted previously in section 2.3, these frameworks share a magnitude of semblance and similarities with ERM as they all accentuate an umbrella concept or a comprehensive risk management approach to all the risk that a business is faced with. This is therefore seen as a move away from the traditional risk management approach.

2.4.1 Definition

The term ERM became a terminology in the business world about two decades ago and ever since has not only become a fashion but has since become paramount in corporate governance practices (Blaskovich and Taylor, 2011). In its generalisation, it refers to the comprehensive or company-wide management (with thorough identification, assessment, prioritising, prevention and response) of an enterprise key risk which may affect it from achieving its long-term objectives and/or strategies. This is as against the traditional form of RM, where risks are managed in silos or in an unplanned or ad-hoc basis (Lermack, 2008). Additionally, the ERM framework also recognises both risk as an opportunity and a threat and stipulates RM to be part

of the business process and value-creating, rather than a separate function (CAS, 2003; Abrams, et.al, 2007; Acharyya, 2008).

The Casualty Actuarial Society (CAS) asserts that the rationale behind this drift from TRM, and the evolution and trend behind the concept of ERM stems from both internal (competitive advantage) and external pressures (corporate governance) (CAS, 2003). However, before delving into such rationales behind ERM's evolution, it is paramount to understand the basic definition of ERM. Although there is no unique definition of ERM, but various bodies and organisations have come up with some useful definitions to which organisations have modelled their definition and framework in line with the framework they wish to adopt. Therefore, some of the major definitions by renowned RM organisations are presented hereunder.

CAS (2003, p.8) in their definition states that “*ERM is the discipline by which an organization in any industry assesses, controls, exploits, finances and monitors risks from all sources for the purpose of increasing the organization's short- and long-term value to its stakeholders*”.

The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission's (COSO) framework is one that is very popular among risk practitioners and utilised by several companies that have adopted ERM. The COSO framework is said to have gained considerable influence because of its affiliation to the Sarbanes-Oxley requirements for listed companies in the US (AIRMIC, et.al., 2010). COSO defines ERM thus:

“Enterprise risk management is a process, effected by an entity's board of directors, management and other personnel, applied in strategy setting and across the enterprise, designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity, and manage risk to be within its risk appetite, to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity's objectives”
(COSO, 2004; p.2).

Furthermore, the International Organization for Standardization's (ISO) ERM framework is also very popular among organisations. Although ISO through its 'risk management standard', (often referred to as ISO 31000:2009) released in November 2009; did not explicitly define ERM, albeit offered definitions for RM which is also construed as ERM since RM is an umbrella-term.

Therefore, according to ISO 31000:2009, risk management is referred to as the “*coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to risk*” (ISO 31000, 2009; p.2). For clarity as regards this definition, ISO regards risk management as the ‘architecture’ while the activities needed for it to be effective include risk management principles, risk management framework and risk management process as shown in figure 2.1 below.

However, despite numerous definitions regarding ERM, Abrams et.al., (2007) discusses that research on several ERM definitions presents three important key characteristics:

- **Integrated** – i.e., ERM must encompass all the business units
- **Comprehensive** – i.e., all risk types must be included in the ERM process and,
- **Strategic** – i.e., must be in alliance with the organisation’s objectives and business strategy.

More so, Bromiley et.al., (2015) adds that notwithstanding the obscurities and variances on what ERM actually entails, there seems to be a general agreement about what ERM is all about: First, based on the assumption that there is more efficiency in managing the portfolio risk of an organisation than managing the risk individually or separately in subsidiaries. Secondly, ERM encompasses all risk types a company faces which ranges from product liability and accidents to product obsolescence and actions from competitors making sure that every key decision within the establishment involves RM analysis; and finally, ERM encourages firms to see risk not just as a threat but also as an opportunity.

2.4.2 RM Models

A model or framework according to RIMS (2011, p.3) is “1) a structure for supporting the organization’s strategic and operational objectives, and 2) a system or group of interacting, interrelated, or independent elements, such as ideas, principles, methods or procedures, that form a complex whole.” More so, Dafikpaku (2011, p.6) defines a RM framework as “an organizational specific set of functional activities and the associated definitions that define the risk management system in an organization and also the relationship to the risk management organizational system.” Models and standards, it has been argued are reported to be effective in improving the sustainability and resilience of an organisation (Fox, 2011).

Prior to the 1990s as documented by Brown (1993) RM model consisted just two elementary phases namely: risk assessment and risk control, which according to him, risk assessment also meant identification and risk control deals with making decisions on identified risk. However, RM models have evolved over the years beyond just risk assessment and risk control (as discussed in subsequent sections) to more rigorous frameworks in order to meet the challenges and protect organisations from risk-fraught activities. Although there are various RM models which organisations may decide to adopt. However, research have shown that of the several RM frameworks, COSO and ISO models are the most prominent among organisations and across industries (Rubino, 2018). Hence only these two frameworks would be discussed majorly in this literature.

2.4.2.1 ISO 31000:2009 Model

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is a non-governmental and independent standard-setting organisation responsible for enacting and promoting commercial, proprietary and industrial standards (Rubino, 2018). ISO headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland and has its roots in over 163-member nations is seen as a link between private and public-sector organisations as many of its unit members are either part of, mandated by government of member states or they are deeply rooted from the private sector (RIMS, 2011).

As stated earlier in section 2.4.1, the ISO in November 2009 released a standard for RM which it titled “*Risk Management: Principles and Guidelines*” (often referred to as ‘ISO 31000:2009’) and was released in the form of an architecture with guidelines for implementation. It comprises of principles (11 features of RM), framework and process as shown in figure 2.1 below. According to Gjerdrum and Salen (2010), the basis for this architecture is that RM is key to the success of every organisation and is designed to address issues as regards corporate governance, financial reporting and stakeholders’ trust. Shortreed (2010) and RIMS (2011) both connotes that the ISO 31000 is not intended to provide assurance against controls but rather it focuses on the quality of management in the organisation and the decisions taken on identified risk thereby seeking out ways to effectively improve organisational efficiency through its stated objectives.

Figure 2.1: ISO 31000:2009 ‘Risk Management Architecture’ (Interdependencies between risk management principles, framework and process).

Source: ISO 31000 (2009; p.vii)

Risk management framework

This is referred to by ISO 31000 (2009; p.2) as a “set of components that provide the foundations and organizational arrangements for designing, implementing, monitoring, reviewing and continually improving risk management throughout the organisation”.

Risk management process

The “systematic application of management policies, procedures and practices to the activities of communicating, consulting, establishing the context, and identifying, analysing, evaluating, treating, monitoring and reviewing risk” (ISO 31000, 2009; p.3).

Risk management principles

This is another major activity contained in the ISO standard in which eleven (11) principles were enumerated as vital (please see figure 2.1 above for a list of these principles) and must be complied with by all levels of an organisation for an effective risk management.

The ISO 31000:2009 risk management architecture propose that every organisation must clearly understand the risk management principles and thereby mandate and ensure that every member of the organisation understands and are fully committed to these principles. More so, because every organisation is unique, organisations are expected ‘establish the contest of their business’ (i.e., to define both the external and internal factors and/or parameters, culture, environment etc.) to enable them design a suitable risk management framework (that conforms to the nature of business, environment, culture etc.) that will oversee the risk management process (Gjerdrun and Salen, 2010; Shortreed, 2010; McClean, 2010). However, despite the ISO’s RM model distinguishing between RM process and RM framework, Fraser (2014) is of the opinion that these two in practice are often combined.

A major trademark of the ISO 31000:2009 risk management architecture according to some analysts is its simplicity, i.e., easy to understand and implement (Rubino, 2018). Another point is the fact that it is universal and dynamic because organisations are free to design and implement their own framework according to their specific environment, culture, business operations etc. (Rubino, 2018). RIMS (2011) states that the ISO 31000, with its universality and ease of use, may be most beneficial to *rapidly changing organizations, those with constrained implementation resources, and those looking for greater flexibility in their strategic and operational risk management practices. Also, any organization with a global footprint may find that this international standard is more widely embraced* (p.7).

2.4.2.2 ISO 31000:2018 Model

In March 2015, ISO set up a technical working committee (ISO/TC 262/WG 2) to make revision to its ISO 31000:2009 as a response to risk practitioners’ call for an update to the 2009 principles and guidelines for RM (Tranchard, 2015). This update was also imperative and exigent because of the dynamism of risk in today’s global space. And as Tranchard (2018, np.) rightly observed, “*yesterday’s risk management practices are no longer adequate with today’s threat and they need to evolve*”. Therefore, in February 2018, ISO published an updated version ISO 31000:2018 thereby replacing and withdrawing the former ISO 31000:2009 version. Highlights of the new release according to ISO (2018) are technical changes relating to:

- “review of the principles of risk management, which are the key criteria for its success,

- Highlighting of the leadership by top management and the integration of risk management, starting with the governance of the organization,
- Greater emphasis on the iterative nature of risk management, noting that new experiences, knowledge and analysis can lead to a revision of process elements, actions and controls at each stage of the process,
- Streamlining of the content with greater focus on sustaining an open system to fit multiple needs and contexts” (ISO, 2018, np.).

Further to the above changes, ISO also states that the new guidelines has been designed to be clearer and more concise thereby eliminating unambiguous terms and languages for better understanding to stakeholders. These changes also brought in place a new structure (with revisions to the ‘Principles, Framework and Process’) as depicted in figure 2.2 below.

Figure 2.2: ISO 31000:2018 ‘Risk Management Architecture’

Source: ISO (2018, p.v)

ISO (2018) reiterates that successful RM is characterised by an effective approach based on clear principles, framework and process as shown in diagram above and detailed in ISO 31000:2018. Therefore, ISO advised that although these components might have existed

partially or wholly in organisations, it however needs to be revised or improved upon for a reliable, effective and efficient RM practice.

Risk Management Principles - ISO 31000:2018

In line with ISO's proposal for an unambiguous, clearer and fit-for-purpose model, it modified and streamlined the principles contained in the earlier version ISO 31000:2009 from 11 RM principles to 8 in its 2018 version. ISO maintains that the basis for RM is to create value and enhance protection and innovation and performance improvement (ISO, 2009; 2018; RIMS, 2018) and as such, the principles (highlighted below) as contained in ISO 31000:2018 outlines useful information, guidance and features for an efficient, consistent and reliable RM.

- **Customise** – ISO insists that its RM architecture is intended for organisations to use as a guide. Therefore, organisations have the liberty to model it to suit their needs and environment. However, in customising the organisational model, care should be taken to ensure the framework and processes are proportionate to the risk confronting the organisation (IRM, 2018).
- **Inclusive** – ISO stresses and reiterates the importance of appropriately involving stakeholders in a timely manner enabling them to contribute their knowledge in order to ensure their feedback is considered. According to ISO 30100:2018, A stakeholder refers to: *“person or organization that can affect, be affected, or perceive themselves to be affected by a decision or activity”* (ISO, 2018: p.1).
- **Structured and comprehensive** – ISO highlights the need for an organised, integrated and a far-reaching approach to RM as this would allow for reliable and comparable outcomes.
- **Integrated** – The importance of RM to any organisation can no longer be undermined; hence it is imperative that RM be entrenched into every organisational activity.
- **Dynamic** – As risk continues to evolve particularly through internal, external, political and environmental influences, the structure for managing risk in the organisation must be dynamic in order to effectively and efficiently respond to such risks.
- **Best available information** – Historical data, current information and trend as well as forecast on future outcomes and expectations are the ingredients needed for a credible RM program. Therefore, RM should explicitly take into consideration any reservations and limitations that may emanate from such information or report and such relevant data should be clear, and readily available to all stakeholders.

- **Human and cultural factors** – At every stage (i.e., design, review and implementation) in organisational RM cycle, proper consideration should always be given to human behaviours and cultural factors within and around the institution as these significantly affect the organisation in various ways.
- **Continual improvement** – There can never be a one-size-fit-all approach to RM. It is a cyclical process of learning and endless improvements. Hence organisations should always learn from past, current and expected future outcomes and build on it for a sound RM model.

From the foregoing, RIMS (2018) deduced that the first five principles as highlighted above, gives useful insight and provide initiative on the design and planning of RM whereas the last three principle details the ways and manner these principles can be applied for effective results.

Risk Management Framework - ISO 31000:2018

RIMS (2018) observe that the ISO 31000:2018 framework and principles are interrelated or linked. This observation is factual given the similarities of their components. For instance, common element between the two is ‘Integrated’ and ‘Integration’ respectively. As a result, RIMS (2018) conclude that the ISO principles is an outline of what needs to be achieved while the framework substantiates, evaluates and provides details on ways to accomplish such. ISO (2018) reiterating the importance of the framework stresses that it functions as the tool by which RM can be integrated into the core activities of the organisation. ISO goes on to suggest that effective RM is dependent on how supportive stakeholders (especially top management) are, and how successful organisations are able to entrench the framework into their decision making, governance etc.

As shown in figure 2.2 above, the features of the framework comprise of ‘Integration, Design, Implementation, Evaluation and Improvement’.

- **Integration** – Understanding the structures and context of the organisation is key for an effective RM integration. Though structures can vary depending on the organisational intricacy, purpose and objectives; management of risk should however be the responsibility of everyone in the organisation. But this should be carried out with a direction or guidance from top management. Embedding RM into an organisation

should be a continuous and dynamic process and must conform to the organisation's needs and culture.

- **Design** – This component is characterised by various features which according to ISO (2018) must be considered during design of the organisational framework. The features are discussed briefly below.
 - i. Understanding the organisation and its context: Organisations should carry out an assessment and have a total knowledge of its internal and external environment when designing its RM framework. ISO (2018) presents a description of factors to be considered when such assessment is to be carried out.
 - ii. Articulating risk management commitment: There should be an endless commitment to RM from stakeholder (top management, boards and everyone responsible for oversight functions) through their actions and policies that obviously and visibly reflects the organisation's commitment to RM. Such commitment according to ISO (2018, p. 6) should involve but not limited to:
 - a. The organisation's essence for managing risk as it relates to its policies and objectives,
 - b. Expressing the necessity to entrench RM totally into the organisational culture,
 - c. Acting as lead in the integration of RM into the fundamental business activities of the organisation and the decision-making process,
 - d. Ensuring good governance through responsibility and accountability,
 - e. Ensuring availability of essential resources,
 - f. Ensuring ways of handling contradictory objectives,
 - g. Ensuring ways of reporting and measuring the organisation's key performance indicators (KPIs),
 - h. Mapping out the frequency for reviews and how improvements should be carried out.

- iii. Assigning organisational roles, authorities, responsibilities and accountabilities:
There should be proper and clear-cut task delegation as regards managing risk and risk owners (persons with the responsibility of managing risk) should be identified.
 - iv. Resource allocation: Stakeholders should ensure where and when possible, appropriate and efficient allocation of resources for RM. This can be in the form of manpower, technology, training facilities etc.
 - v. Establishing feedback loop (i.e., consultation and communication): The organisation in order to ensure an effective RM process, should design a feedback mechanism for efficient communication and consultation with specific audiences. This will ensure that relevant data is collected, collated, produced and disseminated in a timely manner.
- **Implementation** – The organisation should ensure implementation of the RM framework by designing a relevant plan which includes time and resources, relevant departments and authorities responsible for decision making, making changes if necessary, to the decision-making process and ensuring that RM structures in the organisation are unambiguous and is clearly understood and practicable by everyone involved.
 - **Evaluation** – The performance of the RM framework should be evaluated at regular intervals by taking into cognisance its expected outcomes, purpose, plans, implementation, indicators etc., so as to ascertain its relevance towards the achievement of the organisation’s goals and objectives.
 - **Improvement** – The organisation should ensure frequent monitoring for gaps in the framework and continuous improvement to the RM framework when and where necessary in order to ensure it adapts to relevant external and internal changes. If any gap is identified during the course of monitoring, plans should be put in place for enhancement to ensure it is fit-for-purpose.
 - **Leadership and commitment** – From the foregoing, it is the responsibility of top management to oversee the applicability of the framework and implementation of the above listed components and also ensuring all stakeholders are committed to the success of the framework.

Risk Management Process - ISO 31000:2018

The risk management process as presented in the ISO 31000:2018 architecture is very similar to the previous version of 2009 except for few terminologies and the inclusion of 'Recording and Reporting' into the new 2018 version. As earlier stated above in section 2.4.2, it is the *"systematic application of management policies, procedures and practices to the activities of communicating, consulting, establishing the context, and identifying, analysing, evaluating, treating, monitoring and reviewing risk"* (ISO 2009, p.3; 2018, p.9). For ISO, this is a key part in the RM design and should form the nucleus of any RM activity. As stated in section 2.4.4 below and reiterated by ISO (2018), there are various ways to the application of RM process, but what is ideal is for organisations to customise it to achieve their aims and objectives while considering their internal and external context and also factoring in human behavioural and cultural dynamism.

The activities ('Risk Assessment, Risk identification, Risk Analysis, Risk Analysis, Risk Evaluation and Risk Treatment') in this new version ISO 31000:2018 as it relates to RM process is presented in a set of coordinated manner and iterative unlike the old version ISO 31000:2009 whereby the activities were interconnected with arrows suggesting a compulsory linear flow of activities. However, ISO (2018, p.9) acknowledges that *"although the risk management process is often presented as sequential, in practice it is iterative"*. Please see section 2.4.4 more insight on these activities of RM process.

The ISO 31000:2018 RM architecture is still in its early stage having just been released a few months ago. Hence not much literature has been written or analysis carried out on it. However, as Risk practitioners and organisations are still investigating and assessing its global acceptance and relevance to the RM field, a vital concern has been raised regarding the ISO new model for managing risk. According to RIMS (2018, p.8) *"ISO 31000 suggests that effective risk management is characterised by principles, framework and process. The separation of principles, framework and process is not in line with the suggested format for management system standards..."* This according to RIMS (2018) may become a herculean task for the risk professional and pose a challenge when trying to generate a checklist or an implementation plan for their RM activity using the ISO 31000 architecture.

2.4.2.3 COSO ERM – Integrated Framework

Subsequent to the gross financial misconduct experienced in the 1980s, The Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway commission (COSO) was formed in 1985 through a collaboration of five independent bodies (AAA - American Accounting Association, AICPA – American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, FEI – Financial Executives International, IMA – The Association of Accountants and Financial Professionals in Business and IIA – The Association of Internal Auditors) with the initial responsibility to research into the root causes of misconduct in financial reporting (Arena et.al., 2010). However, its mission currently is to “provide thought leadership through the development of comprehensive frameworks and guidance on enterprise risk management, internal control and fraud deterrence designed to improve organizational performance and governance and to reduce the extent of fraud in organization” (COSO, n.d).

True to its mission of developing comprehensive frameworks and guidance on ERM, COSO in 2004 released the *Enterprise Risk Management – Integrated Framework*. Although this framework is non-mandatory, it nonetheless provided a common language against which internal control and risk management systems can be examined and enhanced (URMIA, 2007). Despite criticisms and ambivalence drawn from some quarters (Williamson, 2007; Power, 2009; Kurniawanti, 2010; Desender, 2011; Rubino; 2018) the framework has however become a *de facto* accounting standard (Abrams et. al., 2007) and has become a model generally accepted in arguably every industry and establishment across the globe (URMIA, 2007; Abrams et al., 2007; Arena et al., 2010).

As shown in figure 2.3 below, the COSO framework is depicted in the shape of a cube which illustrates links between objectives (Strategic, Operations, Reporting and Compliance) highlighted on top of the cube and the eight components (Internal environment, Objective setting, Event identification, Risk assessment, Risk response, Control activities, Information and communication and Monitoring) shown in the front depicts what is needed to achieve the objectives. And to the side is a third dimension representing organisational units (Subsidiary, Business unit, Division and Entity level) highlighting the framework’s capability to focus not only on parts of the establishment but also the organisation as a whole (Moeller, 2007).

Figure 2.3: COSO ERM – Integrated Framework (2004)

Source: www.coso.org

Despite the wide popularity and acceptance of the COSO integrated framework, it is however not devoid of some criticisms. (Williamson, 2007; Demidenko and MacNutt, 2010) points out that despite the COSO’s 2004 framework making huge contributions to RM process, but it is fraught with serious limitations because it has not provided a feasible standard to ascertain the effectiveness of ERM. More so, its ‘risk’ definition has been accused to have allegedly diverted attention from both opportunities and uncertainties which falls outside the remits of its closed rational procedures. Furthermore, it has been accused of focusing too much emphasis on ‘controls and command’ and thus ignoring combined management of uncertainties, third parties and social effects of ERM. This as a result according to Williamson (2007) could lead to major threats being created.

Besides, there are other concerns of complexity surrounding the COSO 2004 framework (Williamson, 2007; Power, 2009; Kurniawanti, 2010). Cogitating the approach of the ‘COSO 2004 – Integrated framework’ the following ‘major technical weaknesses’ as shown below were revealed by the North American Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA, 2012, p.3):

- “It is internally focused, and the context is not established in terms of both external and internal factors and influences.
- Stakeholders and their objective are ignored in terms of setting risk criteria.
- Risks are seen as events, not associated with the effect of uncertainty on objectives.

- Risk is incorrectly estimated in terms of the likelihood of an event and its consequences. This produces 'phantom risks' and does not lead to effective and appropriate risk treatment.
- Risks are only seen in a negative light and risk treatment (response) is only about mitigation.
- "Risk responses", "control activities" and "monitoring" are confused. Control is used as both a verb and a noun.
- Risks are said to "occur", and likelihood is when risks occur!
- Inherent risk is used. This is recognised as a highly confusing and flawed concept that is unnecessary.
- "Risk appetite" and "risk tolerance" are mixed up and confused. They are dealt with in a naive and simplistic way.
- The description of the risk management process is mixed up with the framework required for the effective implementation of risk management through integration”

(IIA, 2012, p.3).

2.4.2.4 COSO 2017 ERM Framework

Following the perceived scepticisms and ambivalence surrounding the COSO 2004 – Integrated framework, COSO in September 2017, released an updated version of its ERM framework which it retitled; *‘Enterprise Risk Management – Integrating with Strategy and Performance’*. According to COSO (2017) part of the reasons for the update to the 2004 integrated framework is as a result of changes to risk complexities in modern day business environment – with the emergence and multiplicity of new risk progressing geometrically than previously witnessed, global economic terrain becoming increasingly unpredictable while shifting customer altitudes continues to wield huge influence. Furthermore, COSO emphasises that technological changes and evolution and the need for improved transparency and risk reporting calls for a new RM model.

Besides retitling the framework from ‘COSO ERM – Integrated framework’ to COSO ERM – Integrating with Strategy and Performance, some key changes according to Chesley (2017) include:

- **A new design:** Unlike the very famous cube-like 2004 – Integrated framework (see figure 2 above), this new framework has been streamlined to just five components with twenty guiding principles which are easily manageable is expected to oversee the ‘day-to-day’ activities of the establishment as well as size, sector or type in order to enhance communication between management executives and the board.
- **Enhances the various benefits of ERM:** The framework offers a sound judgement for aligning ERM activities with ‘strategy-setting’ and ‘performance management’ activities to assist in realising the expected goals.
- **Provides a direction for incorporating RM:** The framework enhances better decision-making through the provision of guidance on better ways to integrate ERM (i.e., aligning risk with policy objectives and ‘day-to-day’ activities while enshrining it into the organisation’s practices and culture).
- **Designed from business perspective:** By ensuring major risk themes are well defined, the framework eliminates complexity and ensures universality thereby enabling hassle-free involvement from all levels of management.

Figure 2.4: COSO ERM – Integrating with Strategy and Performance (2017).

Source: www.coso.org

The above diagram shows five components consisting of twenty underlying principles (between three to five each) which must be understood clearly in order to achieve enhanced performance from the ERM objective. Because there is always a possibility that an

organisation's business strategy may not be in alliance with its vision, mission and core values, therefore, the aim of for this update is to ensure that ERM is entrenched into the core values and activities of the organisation which allows for better RM and resilience (IRM, 2017).

Furthermore, the updated COSO framework differentiates clearly between internal control and ERM and provides more explanation on risk appetite and tolerance. More so, the framework emphasises the role of culture to the successful achievement of RM and finally, COSO is of the opinion that ERM will on the long run improve the organisation resilience (i.e., able to anticipate and react to change) thereby ensuring organisations are not only able to identify risk factors, but also change factors and how such changes would result in improved performance and lead to a positive shift in strategy (COSO, n.d.).

2.4.3 Selecting a RM framework

There are several RM frameworks or models available for HEIs to choose from. This literature however focuses on the ISO 31000 and COSO ERM frameworks which have been adjudged most popular (Padro, 2015). Although, these frameworks have their limitations, criticisms as well as benefits, both frameworks due to their holistic approach, maturity and reliability, organisations could potentially profit from some potential benefits associated with the application of a universal RM model (DeLoach, 2012). A major strategic decision for firms is the choice of a RM framework thus, it is essential for HEIs to consider their unique culture and other relevant interrelated factors such as governance and management structures before selecting a framework (Mikes, 2005) because, it is vital that the implemented RM model is a representation of the organisational realism (Martin and Power, 2007; Blaskovich and Taylor, 2011).

There are fundamental differences between the ISO 31000 and the COSO ERM framework, however, in general, they possess more similarities than differences as observed above. While the COSO framework is often seen or accused of being regulatory based rather than risk management based, it has also been criticised as a complex framework difficult to implement whereas, the ISO 31000 framework is often seen to be easier to understand and implement (Power, 2009; Gjerdrum and Peter, 2011; Bugalla, et.al., 2012; Padro, 2015). However, Charette (2012) opines the strength of ISO 31000 may also amount to its weaknesses because its universality would mean that HEIs may incur significant amount of time and resources to align it to the organisation's culture and strategic objectives. However, HEIs can use these

frameworks as guides for initiating and implementing their RM process. There have been suggestions from practitioners of the prospect to combine both the ISO 31000 and the COSO frameworks for firms' specific needs however, the trend so far is that organisations have been using them independently (Padro, 2015).

It should be noted nonetheless that there is no best risk management framework, and organisations often choose a framework that best suits their business context (Mehta, 2010). However, McNally (2015) discussed some essential characteristics of a good RM framework which is highlighted below:

- Should be a mechanism to assist firms in achieving its strategic goals and objectives,
- Should be principles-based and enhances performance,
- It must be tailored to the organisation's environment and culture,
- Must be implemented locally, integrated and built into the system and should be evolving and dynamic.
- It must be integrated into the governance structure and should be seen as having value for money.

Integrating a RM model or framework into the firms' governance structure is very important particularly for HEIs because it defines the success of the process (Padro, 2015). The above highlights according to McNally (2015) are by no means exhaustive but should provide suitable guidance for firms to choose or evaluate their framework.

2.4.4 Risk Management Process

As highlighted in section 2.4.2, RM has evolved beyond just risk assessment, control and analysis which was majorly the case prior to 1990s even up to the early 2000s (Brown 1993; Aven, 2016), such is the case presented above highlighting various ERM frameworks and their continuous updates. However, researchers, stakeholders and practitioners of risk highlights several activities required for a sound and effective RM process such as: a well-defined RM policies and objectives and a clear communication of such within and around the organisation (COSO, 2004; ISO, 2009; Cendrowski and Mair, 2009; Deloitte, 2011). More so, there should be a common risk language shared within the organisation (CAS, 2003; Aabo et al., 2005; Shenkir and Walker, 2008; COSO, 2018).

Although, historically there is no global and simple formula for risk management (Klinke and Renn, 2002), however, irrespective of framework or definition, almost all RM processes share a relatively common activity and approach (as highlighted in figure 2.5 below) such as: ‘Defining objectives’, ‘risk identification’, ‘risk analysis’, ‘risk evaluation’, ‘risk response/mitigation’ etc. (Muelbroek, 2002; COSO, 2004; ISO, 2009; Mehta, 2010; Emblemstvag, 2010; Ruzic, et al., 2014; Fraser, et.al., 2015). The stages in this process are cyclical and may vary in name depending on literature, but ideally, when addressing risk, the trend is usually carried out in five stages: ‘Set Objectives’, ‘Identify Risks’, ‘Analyse’ ‘Evaluate’ and ‘Respond’ (Lundquist, 2016) and according to IRM (2018) it should conform to the universally agreed RM principles (i.e., Proportionate, Aligned, Comprehensive, Embedded and Dynamic) often connoted with the acronym ‘PACED’. Please see table 1 below for brief analysis.

Figure 2.5: Risk Management Process

Source: Beirman (2016)

Table 2.1: Risk Management Principles

Principle	Description
Proportionate	RM activities ought to be equivalent or proportionate to the amount of risk faced by the establishment.
Aligned	RM activities must be fully aligned with all other organisational activities.
Comprehensive	The approach to RM must be fully comprehensive to ensure reliability and effectiveness.
Embedded	Every effort must be taken to ensure that RM activities are fully embedded into the organisation.
Dynamic	There must be dynamism in scope and scale of the organisational RM activities; in that it is able to respond effectively to changes in risk.

Source: IRM (2018)

2.4.4.1 Objective Setting

Organisations in a bid to accomplish their goals and provide value for their stakeholders often encounter uncertainties and risk that may hinder the achievement of their goals. Therefore, risk practitioners opine that an essential first step towards a successful RM process should begin with setting strategic objectives and aligning such with mission, vision and culture of the entire organisation (COSO, 2004; ISO, 2009). Thus, RM must not exist as a separate function but should be embedded into the planning and governance process of the organisation (Acharyya, 2008; Achampong, 2010; Beasley, et.al., 2012). Fraser and Simkins (2007) warns that it would amount to a grave mistake for organisations to see RM as an end to itself and separated from the strategic objectives of the organisation. Achampong (2010) specifically admonished Higher educational institutions to ensure that RM is integrated into their strategic planning activities in order to ensure resilience and continuity.

2.4.4.2 Risk Identification

Risk identification is an elementary phase of the RM process. Most literature (other than COSO 2004 and ISO 2009, that regard this process as the second stage of RM after objective setting,) regard this phase as the very first stage of the RM process (Tchankova, 2020; Achampong, 2010; Beasley, et.al., 2012). This stage demands that all risk (external or internal, negative or positive) should be identified and documented using a **risk register**. Initiation of this process rest on the authority of either the Chief Risk Officer (CRO), Risk committee, or senior administrators with the aid of techniques such as: reviewing existing documents, workshops, surveys and/or interviews (NACUBO, 2007; Aabo, et al., 2005; Raanan, 2009; Marchetti, 2011; Abraham, 2013, Fraser, 2013).

Most HEIs draw-up a list of institutional risks on their risk registers during this process but Abraham (2013) has criticised such approach as being inefficient because after a period of time, such list even though properly documented could become so ambiguous and cumbersome to manage. Therefore, Gallagher (2009) recommends asking directors in every unit to identify their risk and evaluating such risk for common themes and categories. This risk identification process should not be seen as a one-off thing but should be an ongoing process and also one that must be embedded into the institution's management and governance process and to ensure that a comprehensive risk identification process is achieved, executive and senior management teams as well as the board must be involved (Abraham, 2013).

Ensuring an effective Risk identification

PKF (2011), highlights that to ensure an effective risk identification process, organisations would start by analysis of their corporate and strategic objectives and then apply some frequently used tools to identify risks within the internal and external environment. Some of these management tools according to (PKF, 2011) include: 'SWOT analysis', PESTLE analysis, Facilitation, Brainstorming etc. However, as a result of the constant changes within the internal and external environments, institutions should always ensure they have full knowledge and awareness of their internal and external risks. Therefore, as part of their risk identification process, institutions should continuously perform a review of their internal and external environment in order to identify any activity or inactivity that may produce risk that have not previously been identified. This process is known as horizon scanning. This is also an excellent process for detecting any of the risk discussed above.

2.4.4.3 Risk Analysis

Risk analysis refers to the process by which organisations assess and estimate the probability of occurrence and their impact of identified risks to ascertain their likelihood of occurrence. Factors usually considered ranges from potential financial loss, damage to reputation of the organisation, loss of time, impact and severity etc. By carrying out the analysis of every identified risk would allow organisations to categorise their risk and ascertain which ones are more severe and require urgent attention (Fekete, 2009). Risk analysis also help to uncover common problems associated with projects and further help to improve the risk management process and practice towards subsequent projects (Vasvári, 2015).

2.4.4.4 Risk Assessment/Evaluation

This stage relates to the evaluation of risk in relation to the level of acceptable risk and the level of control that has been achieved already (i.e., the risk management controls and techniques available). The level of acceptable risk is arrived at by the risk attitude or risk appetite as contained in their risk management policy (Gallagher, 2009; Fraser, 2013). It is imperative that the key risk identified would raise concerns and be assessed (Dafikapaku, 2001; Gallagher, 2009, Fraser, 2013) and carefully evaluated for impact and the organisations exposure to such risk (Marchetti, 2011). This process may involve the use of qualitative and quantitative techniques to assess effects (e.g., Risk rating matrix – used to determining the frequency and severity) it may have on the organisation’s objectives (Mehta, 2010; Marchetti, 2011).

Usually, organisations take into cognisance their **risk tolerance** and **risk appetite** when evaluating and ranking their risk as contained in their risk management policy (Gallagher, 2009; Fraser, 2013). Gallagher (2009, p.30) recommends HEIs to consider the following questions when determining their risk appetite:

- ‘What risks will the institution not accept? These might include academic quality compromises, regulatory compliance fines, and electronic data breaches.
- What risks will the college or university take with any new initiatives? Examples are lower than desired student registrations for a new academic program, and anticipated controversy over a new research project.
- What risks will the institution accept for competing objectives? An example of competing objectives might be a high volume of research grants versus fewer grants that present greater potential for technology transfer revenue’ (Gallagher, 2009, p. 30).

Essentially, the aim of implementing risk management is to reduce the impact of risk (gross risk) to a level that is acceptable (net risk) as against completely eliminating risk (Fekete, 2009). There are occasions however when organisations may realise that their net risk deviates from their stated risk appetite. In such situations, PKF, (2011) advises that institutions should map out new control measures and thus the risk appetite would be achieved through these new measures once they have been successfully implemented. A vital requirement regarding the risk management techniques employed is that the risk impact and the reduction cost should not be more than the associated cost of control (Hornai, 2001) as illustrated in figure 2.6 below.

Figure 2.6: Risk Impact and Cost of Risk Management

Source: Vasvári (2015).

Generally, a common risk management practice by organisations is the multiplication of probability by impact to enable them to quantify and measure key risks. To achieve this, most organisations rely on risk rating/scoring matrix and it is a very common tool among institutions which allow organisations to graphically map out risks, by plotting probability and impact against each axis (Klinke and Renn, 2002). Risk matrices would allow organisations to present and make decisions on evaluated risk and could also be used to indicate the actual level of risk across the organisation as it would help to identify areas where risk have either increased, decreased or remained same.

There are quite a few categories of risk scoring matrix as there is often a considerable variance on the number of defined scores on either axis across institutions (i.e., 3x3, 4x4, 5x5, etc.). Thus, organisations may choose to adopt any particular type that suits them best (Ruzic-Dimitrijevic and Dakic; 2014). However, PKF (2011) sounds a note of warning to organisations by ensuring that the type of risk matrix adopted is understood perfectly by their staff in order to ensure that key risks are not underscored or underrated as not given required attention to key risks could result in grave consequences. They therefore advised that organisations should always provide guidelines and definitions for their rating procedure within the risk matrix. A sample of a risk matrix is presented in Appendix 2.3 of this study.

2.4.4.5 Risk response

This is the action taken on risks that were identified, evaluated and prioritised for decision making (Raanan, 2009; Bubka and Coderre, 2010; Curtis and Carey, 2012). This stage may involve the use of key risk and performance indicators (Beasley, et al., 2012; Marchetti, 2011b). According to Gallagher (2009) and Marchetti (2011) organisations' approach in responding to such risk may depend on their capability, environment, policy, risk tolerance and/or risk appetite. However, any approach they decide to adopt falls within any of the categories described below:

- Reduction/Mitigation: reduce the probability of occurrence and/or the impact to a level that is deemed acceptable
- Control: control and reduce the damage after a loss event
- Transfer: assign the risk to a third party (e.g., Insurance)
- Acceptance: agree to take responsibility (this is often the case when the cost of control is perceived to be greater than the loss impact)
- Avoidance: This often depends on the organisation's risk appetite. Undertakings perceived to result in greater threat or uncertainties may be avoided.

The above categories of risk response as highlighted above is presented in Appendix 2.4 for a proper illustration. One major dilemma often encountered by decision-makers is how to achieve optimum control of risk (see figure 2.6 above). As already mentioned above, it is fundamental that control cost is lower than the magnitude of risk to be controlled (Hornai, 2001). Thus, there are situations decision-makers would deliberately or as a best and most effective strategy, avoid taking some risk and Broder and Tucker (2012) sees this as the most effective way of controlling risk and according to them, you need not worry about the risk if it does not exist. However, (Vasvári, 2015) argues that this is a risky venture and may in turn become hazardous and subsequently the resultant liability of opportunities mixed would be transferred to stakeholders.

Farkas and Szabó (2005) discuss that risk mitigation strategy is at best seen as 'retained risk' because decision-makers rely on their own resource capabilities to manage the risks. They further classified the risk mitigation process as 'pre-loss' (aim is to reduce the probability of occurrence with the risk effect being assumed) and 'pro-loss' (aim is to mitigate the impact of the risk with the assumption that the probability of risk occurrence is certain). However, Taleb

(2012) posits that in order to ensure that the right decisions are made, focus should be on the potential consequences of risks – which can be certain, as against their probability of occurrence – which cannot be determined. This can be seen as a precautionary approach or strategy which is geared towards the ‘resilience’ and ‘vulnerability management’ which guarantees better resistance against unexpected events (Klinke and Renn, 2002).

Organisations may decide to share their risk when they are not willing or capable of undertaking the risk alone. Common ways of doing this would either be to engage third party contractors (e.g., consultants to help with the risk management process) or seek insurance cover (Farkas and Szabó (2005). However, it has been argued that seeking insurance policy may sometimes lead to moral hazard because some people within the organisation may decide to take unnecessary risk with the belief that there is an insurance cover; though some believe that in an ideal world, taking such risk could lead to opportunities and by extension economic growth (Bernstein, 1998).

Organisations would choose to accept some certain risks when the control cost is higher than the impact of the risk or when the risk in question is within the risk appetite of the institution (Vasvári, 2015). Practically, though some decision-makers are either seen as ‘risk-averse’, ‘risk-neutral’ or ‘risk-seeking’; it is often best to consider every risk event critically and respond with the most appropriate risk response technique based on the institution’s risk appetite and their prevailing circumstances rather than the decision-makers’ personal views or inclination (Fehér, 2008).

2.4.4.6 Monitoring and Review

This process is very important because it ensures that the RM program conforms to the organisation’s culture, up-to-date and effective throughout the establishment (CAS, 2003). A continuous and regular review of the RM program would also ensure that the risk assessment shows a true picture of the organisation’s “*current operations, threats, probability, impact, and countermeasures*” (Loghry and Veach, 2009, p. 34). There should also be regular reports on progress and evaluations with past assessments to ensure that variances and deviations are easily identified and communicated to the authority in charge for required action to be taken (Marchetti, 2011).

2.4.5 Benefits and Criticisms of ERM

There is a growing debate on the linkage between ERM and firm performance or value creation. It has been argued that most organisations that have adopted ERM are either finding it difficult or are unable to ascertain the extent to which substantial benefits (perceived to accrue from ERM) such as value enhancement, corporate organisational performance, reputation etc., have enhanced their firms (Rogers, et al., 2010). There is no gain re-echoing the fact that an extensive amount of literature has attributed several benefits and value creation to firms adopting ERM.

Prominent among such claims by several risk practitioners and researchers is that ERM will bolster the chances for organisations to achieve their corporate objectives by making available a framework for better strategic planning (CAS, 2003; COSO, 2004; Williamson, 2007; Acharyya, 2008; ISO, 2009; IIA, 2010; Beasley, et.al., 2012; Fraser, 2013; Esaides, 2013); value creation and competitive advantage (Barton, et.al., 2002; Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2003; Nocco and Stulz, 2006); gaps and silos reduction through improved governance and decision-making (CAS, 2003; Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2003; Kleffner, et.al., 2003; Wilson, et.al., 2010), enhance the organisations ability to identify, assess and respond efficiently and effectively to risk within and around the establishment (Dickerson and Fallon, 2004; Beasley, et.al., 2009; Gallagher, 2009; IIA, 2009), assist the organisation to establish their levels of risk tolerance and risk appetite (COSO, 2004; Fraser and Simkins, 2007), foster and encourages innovation thereby providing a context for identifying and seizing opportunities (COSO, 2004; ISO, 2009), improved ratings from rating agencies (Fraser and Simkins, 2007; Standard and Poors, 2008; Moody, 2011), and improves the organisation's financial standing while reducing losses and chances of misappropriation (COSO, 2004; Beasley, et.al., 2008; Demidenko and McNutt, 2010 Hoyt and Lienbenberg, 2011; Grace, et.al; 2014).

Despite the comprehensive literature enumerating the benefits of ERM due to its perceived strategic model, in contrast, critics continue to question the viability of ERM. Blaskovich and Taylor (2011) rhetorically connotes "*if ERM is the solution to unmitigated risk, it is shocking to note that some of the most financially-literate executives at venerable Wall Street institutions made some of the most egregious risk miscalculations in history*" (p.6). Leech (2012) claimed that there is an evolving evidence to indicate that at its best, ERM has performed below standard and highly vulnerable at worst. This position according to (Lin et al., 2012) received backing with the failure of American International Group (AIG) which is said to be among the

first insurance firms in the United States to adopt ERM. While Samanta (2009) asserts that the benefit and true value of ERM are yet to be seen arguing that what has been seen is continuous experiments with trial-and-errors.

More so, Lin et al. (2012) observes that with all its accrued benefits “*when blindly following the wave of ERM adoption, managers are likely to underestimate the difficulty and cost of initiating and maintaining ERM programs or overestimate their own abilities to coordinate and aggregate various IRMs and risks*”. (p.12). They have argued that such could result in a further bureaucratic process and become counter-productive if applied wrongly. Buttressing this point, Henry (2007) stresses that such bureaucracies usually result from red tapes that the framework presents, resulting in unnecessary cataloguing of events which leads to oversight of some major activities and other pitfalls that could impact negatively on the organisation.

From the foregoing, Esaides (2013) opines that many establishments are reluctant to adopt ERM because it has failed to convince them of its benefits apart from presenting a catalogue of exposures that are already known. Arena, et.al. (2010) opines while adopting ERM, existing management framework are often ignored, which brings to the possibility that firms often adopt ERM as a mere compliance tool or as a form of internal control event, without embedding it into the organisation’s business objectives. And according to a survey carried out by Arena et.al. (2010) revealed that most CEO’s usually regard ERM as an external regulatory function that does not actually impact on managerial operations, activities and decisions. Such regulatory directive as regards ERM, has made Huber (2009) to criticise the obligatory requirement by regulators in the UK for HEIs to adopt a RM model arguing that adopting a RM framework could disorganise and destabilise HEIs long-aged traditional model and culture.

More so, there are some who regard ERM as being purely subjective and has criticised such approach arguing that analysis of risk when carried out by different groups would generally result in various assumptions (Emblemsvag, 2010). Williamson (2007) argues that appraising the viability and efficiency of ERM and its features can be very challenging and thus requires a sound judgement. Therefore, subjective opinions of potential events (i.e., its impact and management) could result in bias judgement due to power and interest. Additionally, Koenig (2008) believes that placing much trust on quantitative measures could result in a wrong judgment of security. According to him, “*risk and uncertainty make us uneasy...Quantifications are one manner by which we try to turn subjective risk assessments*

into objective measures. We attempt to convert uncertainty, which is not measurable, into risk, which is believed to be measurable” (Koenig, 2008, p.15).

Finally, one other major criticism of ERM comes from Michael Power who alongside David Martin, are regarded as very strong sceptics of ERM (Blaskovich and Taylor, 2011). Power (2009) have opined that ERM stems its root from the accounting field and having an internal control framework thus as such, it has a concept that is limited to ‘rule-based compliance’ thereby has failed in its objective of being entrenched into the governance and decision-making process of institutions adopting it. Martin and Power (2007) in furtherance to this argument connotes that ERM due to its design and origin, is better suited for serving the interest of regulators and accounting practitioners than managing risk.

Owing to these various critical views of ERM, Power (2007, p.11) has called for caution which according to him, ERM being an “umbrella concept”, administrators need not “...*assume that ERM refers unequivocally to a coherent set of practices*” especially with pressures from regulatory bodies mounting on firms to incorporate risk management practices into their governance structure, new categories are being created and this according to Power (2004) has led to the “risk management of everything” with the resultant effect according to Power (2009) amounting to the “risk management of nothing”.

Critical assessments and discussions on Risk, Risk Management, as well as some major frameworks or models for managing risk presented thus far in this literature is to help evaluate and understand the structures and practices of RM within the HEI context. However, due to the limited empirical studies on RM in the academic sector, it was essential to review the generic literature on risk management and draw inference from it to HEIs. Discussions above have shown how key components of the risk management system have been coupled in order to have a solid background knowledge on the operationality of these risk management architectures, structures and practices because this would help to examine the risk management systems of case HEIs.

Furthermore, the above sections also discussed considerations in selecting risk management models by organisations as well as the benefits and criticisms of risk management as presented by several academic literature. Subsequent sections in this chapter will therefore discuss the context of UK Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) as regards their structure, regulation,

Risks associated with HEIs and their RM processes and practices. This will allow for a perfect understanding of HEIs RM structures and approaches which would be useful for the researcher in formulating questions on policies, procedures and practices of risk management within the HEI setting.

2.5 UK HIGHER EDUCATION CONTEXT

Although the scope and boundary of this study is restricted to only Scottish Universities because of this separate legislation governing higher institutions across the UK, however, these separate legislations have not been in place from the onset. Therefore, it is essential to look at the general background of UK Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) in order to create an understanding of how HEIs in the UK have evolved over time.

HEIs in the UK differ in various ways ranging from size, shape, ethos, history, mission, vision and even location (Cranfield and Taylor 2008). It has a rich history and tradition which dates back to 1096 as documented and it is believed that teaching began in the city of Oxford, making the University of Oxford the first established institute of Higher learning in the English-speaking world. The University of Cambridge followed suit and it marked its 800th anniversary in 2009 as it was established in 1209. Subsequently, four more Universities (St. Andrews, Glasgow, Aberdeen and Edinburgh) were established in Scotland (which are often regarded as Ancient Universities in Scotland) in the 15th Century with authority from the see of Rome – papal bull (Burnes et.al, 2014).

However, the 19th century witnessed a major expansion to the number of Higher Education (HE) in the UK with the establishment of a good number of schools through royal charter. Also, during this period between 1950 and 1960, the government embarked upon an expansion program to the HE sector which came as a response to the needs of an increasing population and the demands of a growing technological economy, hence new colleges of advanced technology were founded and these were later given university status in 1966; Universities that were established in this period and further up before the 1992 Act, are usually referred to as Civic Universities. (Anderson, 2010).

In 1992, there was another significant expansion through the Further and Higher Education Act, the British government converted about 35 polytechnics and other institutions mainly colleges of higher education to university status (Burnes et.al., 2014). Between 2001 and 2013,

there was again an increase to the number of HEIs with the establishment of a further 31 universities and these universities that were established after 1992 are often referred to as ‘post-92’ or ‘modern’ universities (Wyness, 2010).

2.5.1 Structure and Growth of the UK HE Sector

HEIs in the UK although not publicly owned but there is a considerable level of influence exerted by the government which differs depending on the region in the UK. However, these HEIs are sovereign legal entities with governing bodies or councils saddled with the responsibility for making strategic decisions, monitoring its financial affairs and ensuring proper governance (Anderson, 2010; 2016). Although HEIs are not directly under the control of government, there are independent funding councils however, saddled with the responsibilities of appropriating funds to these public funded HEIs. The responsibilities of these bodies differ based on their region within the UK. For instance, HEIs in Northern Ireland are funded directly by government through its Department for the Economy – DfE (David and Amey, 2020).

In England however, HEI receive funding from various public and private sources. But with the reintroduction of the revised tuition fee in 2012, majority of funding for HEIs came from tuition fees (Anderson, 2016). The Office for Students (OfS) was set up through the Higher Education and Research Act of 2017 and became fully operational in 2018 replacing both the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and the Office for Fair Access (OFFA). Part of the remit of the OfS is to distribute funds to HEIs through annual grants and allocations based on a policy framework determined by the government (Eurydice, 2019a). While teaching is funded by OfS, research however, is jointly funded by the Research England and the Research Councils in conjunction with Innovate UK and these are part of the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The OfS and the UKRI have an understanding to collaborate in achieving shared objectives on teaching and research (Eurydice, 2019a).

HEIs in Scotland are majorly funded by the Scottish Government. HEIs receive these funds primarily through grants from the Scottish Funding Council (SFC). According to (Eurydice, 2019b), the SFC invests over £1.6 billion funds annually on HEIs on teaching, learning, research and other relevant activities in accordance with the Scottish Government’s educational goals and objectives. However, there are other sources of funds for these HEIs other than the

government funding such as a significant amount of income from international students and other considerable grants from private entities (Eurydice, 2019b).

2.6 CHANGING CONTEXT OF UK UNIVERSITIES

The conventional idea of Higher Education (HE) presents a picture of an elitist group of people privileged to attend public or grammar schools (Anderson, 2010; Bathmaker, 2003). As put forward by Barnett, (2000), the traditional universities got its roots from a guild of intellectuals that collaborated and organised themselves into a self-governing committee and later developed into a formal institution with the authority to award degrees. Judging from this, the University became a citadel of universal knowledge and a place for learning and searching for truth where both teachers and students shared a common value of enquiry (Barnett, 2000), with the solitary aim of exposing these students to the best global knowledge and thinking (Smith and Webster, 1997).

The Robins report of 1963 became the catalyst that gave rise to some major reforms in the HE sector (Deem et.al, 2007; Burnes et.al, 2014). However, some analysts (Hardy, 1991; Reisz, 2008; Anderson, 2010; Burnes et.al, 2014) contends that such reforms became the basis, underpinning the changing context of the traditional universities (Collegiality) to a business-like approach (New Public Management – NPM, often referred to as New Managerialism – NM in the academic terrain). For a proper understanding of this context, this report will look at the trail of events with regards to External/Internal factors.

2.6.1 External Factors

Basically, most of the external factors that has contributed to the changes in the educational terrain has often stemmed from governmental policies and regulations (some of which has already been discussed in section 2.5). This is drawing from Abrahamson (1991) summation on ‘forced selection perspective’ acting as a driver for change, where external forces such as governmental organisations exert the authority to impose certain changes.

Parry (2001) in a detailed account of the trail of events from the 1980s onwards as regards changes to the UK higher educational system, records that prior to mid-80s which he termed as the early periods of the educational reform overseen by the newly elected government which introduced austerity measures partly as a result of governments inability to fund the increasing number of students.

The resultant effect was a devastating one to HE which saw an end to the expansion that had been witnessed between the 1960s and 70s as the government made plans to cut public spending on HE over three years from 1981 to 25% (Burnes et.al, 2014), coupled also with an embargo placed on the introduction of new courses (Deem et.al, 2007; Cranfield and Taylor, 2008) and eventually brought an end to university autonomy (Shattock, 1994; De Boer et.al, 2008). Deem et.al (2007) connotes that there was eagerness to make universities more accountable and efficient to the government and the general public.

Burnes et. al (2014) reports that the Committee of Vice-Chancellors and Principals (CVCP) under pressure from the government, commissioned the Jarrat Report of 1985 to investigate how universities should be governed; hence following the report, the CVCP moved away from the collegial administrative model into a private sector approach. Therefore, new philosophies and ethos began to creep into university management: more emphasis on corporate governance, recognition of Vice-Chancellors as Chief Executives (Deem et.al, 2007), market competition (Sotiraku, 2004), strategic planning, programme evaluation, quantitative performance indicators and value-added services (Hardy 1991). Glennon et.al (2019) wondering why these ethos and philosophies as heralded by NPM are often regarded as the ideal model for business operation and service delivery; argues that public sector organisations are different in their service delivery especially how they are conceptualised, evaluated and managed.

As such, the Jarrat Report has often been accused of introducing private-sector ethos into university management (Hardy, 1991; Jones, 1986) with Alderman (2009, 2010) contending that it has forced universities to compete against each other for resources and students are now being seen as customers. This seem to be a far cry from John Henry Newman classic work “The idea of a University”, Newman (1907) believes an ideal University to be a group of thinkers brought together by a common goal of intellectual pursuit not for any outward desires or purpose but as an end in itself.

Again, poised with the drive to tighten the grip on universities, the Education Reform Act was passed by the government in 1988 which saw the University Grants Committee (UGC) abolished for being too soft on HEIs and replaced it with Universities Funding Council (UFC) for stricter policy measures (Anderson 2010) and it also brought an end to academic tenures – particularly for new staff –intake or those who either accepted new post or promotion (Deem

et.al 2007), thereby undermining job security of staff and thus making it more difficult to oppose these changes (Burnes et.al, 2014).

The Act also heralded some radical changes to the curriculum of schools, funding and assessment in addition to post-compulsory education (Flude and Hammer 1990) and also saw polytechnics and colleges of education becoming independent corporations thereby separating from the control of local government (Parry 2001) thus, Mackie and Williamson (2007) regards this detachment of polytechnics and colleges from the control of local government authorities as one of the major factors that led to NM in the educational sector.

The year 1992 witnessed another major shake-up in the educational sector with the Further and Higher Education Act replacing the UFC with separate funding bodies for England – HEFCE, Scotland – Scottish Higher Education Funding Council – SHFC (now Scottish Funding Council – SFC) and Wales – HEFCW. The Act also put an end to the ‘binary’ divide, thereby converting Polytechnics and Colleges of Education into universities – commonly referred to as ‘post-92’ universities (Deem et.al, 2007). Parry (2001) however reckons that this has very much exposed universities to much more competition as regards students’ recruitment, teaching and research activities.

Several authors (Bathmaker, 2003; Deem et.al, 2007; Anderson, 2010; Burnes et.al, 2014) reports that the educational sector witnessed a major financial crisis in mid 1990’s caused by the growing number of student figures against the budgeted and available resource funding. Hence this alarmed the Vice Chancellors who made threats to take actions on their own with proposals to charge students’ top-up-fees (Bathmaker 2003). Hence the government intervened with the Dearing Report of 1997 (Bathmaker 2003; Burnes et.al, 2014) and a separate but similar report in Scotland – Garrick Report (Deem et.al, 2007).

Some major take-away from these reports were the introduction of tuition fees to be borne by students, more emphasis on strong governance by governing bodies of universities and also greater focus or increased priority to teaching and learning. These according to Anderson (2010) and Bunce et.al. (2017) are partly or majorly responsible for seeing students as customers and also a ploy to distance research from teaching while some analysts contend that the Dearing Review of 1997 was constituted to help resolve the calamity of funds witnessed that period in the educational sector, but sadly did very little in restoring financial freedom and university management (Parry 1999; Trow 1997; Jary and Parker 1998).

2.6.2 Internal Factors

Over the years, HEIs have tried to compensate and adapt to diminished governmental revenues by focusing on the marketing of business and educational services through development of innovative products and private sector partnerships (Kinser et.al., 2010; Ball, 2017; Peters et.al., 2018; Hommel and Woods, 2018). Various literature (Beckmann and Cooper, 2013; Burnes et.al., 2014; Waring, 2017; Phrysor and Henley, 2018) evidences how such external pressures and changing conditions have enabled HEIs to successfully embrace various elements of private sector management in their governance which have altered the internal structure of the of the university system. As a consequence, Sotiraku (2004) and Phrysor Henley (2018) report that the UK HE sector has evolved from a system (prior to 1980) principally regarded as sovereign institutions operating in an internal terrain through a period between (mid-1980s and further) of strong central governance and subsequently onto the global market.

Pugh et.al., (2018) however contends that the resultant effect from the foregoing has made HEIs look more like a holding company designed to oversee and regulate the activities of its units or departments therefore reducing the authority of such departments in a bid to favour the institution. A very good number of literature are of the opinion that such is the reason that has led to a decline in collegiality in favour of entrepreneurship and corporate culture (Moodie 1986; McNay 1995; Ramsden 1998; Deem et.al, 2007; Burnes et.al, 2014) while Sotiraku (2004); Doyle and Brady (2018) argue that departmental heads faces a great challenge on how best to preserve quality, maintain viability, flexibility, autonomy of their various departments and ensure academic freedom in a bid to respond effectively and efficiently to a globalised market oriented educational sector.

2.7 HIGHER EDUCATION ENVIRONMENT AND RISK MANAGEMENT IN UNIVERSITIES

HEIs often consider themselves substantially different from other not-for profit and also for-profit organisations and even the outside world has also regarded them as such (Fraser et.al, 2014). However, lessons from Hurricane Katrina, gross misconduct and irregularities that affected colleges and universities in America have heightened awareness for risk exposures on higher institutions hence there are calls for greater accountability, student welfare and safety and increased awareness on risk management (Fraser et.al, 2014). Thus, regulatory authorities are calling on HEIs to implement RM frameworks for greater accountability. For instance, the

Higher Education Funding Council in England (HEFCE) called upon all HEIs in England to implement risk management framework (HEFCE, 2000) likewise the Scottish Funding Council (SFC, 2006) have also done same. Ever since, UK educational regulators have been constantly mounting increased pressure on HEIs under their watch to up their game in order to keep achieving societal goals efficiently and effectively. One of such significant consequence emanating from this development is the recommendation for HEIs to account for their risks. To achieve this objective, HEFCE and SFC both came up with a guidance on risk management for universities (Huber, 2009).

The growth in the HEI sector in the 1980s has always been linked to the New Public Management, thus, there were increasing calls to universities for accountability and efficient use of taxpayers' money by stakeholders (Mackie and Williamson, 2007). Over three decades ago, McNamara and Booth (1984: 175) once predicted that universities will *"come under the same pressure as the rest of the public sector to demonstrate that they provide value for money"*. To meet these expectations the authors suggests risk management to be a feasible governance approach.

However, there were some cynicism regarding the introduction of risk management into the British academic system in the early 2000 as some universities responded to this initiative by HEFCE with perplexity and criticisms. For instance, Cambridge University was highly critical of this new initiative describing it as *"alien to the character of the University and do carry pressures which could seriously damage the flexibility and diversity which is a particular strength of the institution; they would certainly be unprofitable for a University such as this"* (Raban and Turner 2003: p. 22). Such response highlights the concerns and cynicisms from some quarters as regards risk management and its introduction to the HEI sector.

The Turnbull report (Turnbull Committee, 1999) is seen as the UK's abridged version of the COSO risk-based-approach on internal control and has become a model or framework for managing risk across most public-sector organisations – including HEIs (Soin et.al, 2014). Part of educational regulator's objective is to promote and ensure accountability towards the use of public funds and thus through its funding mechanisms to HEIs, regulatory bodies often use "moral suasion" as a tactic of ensuring accountability in the higher education sector (Soin et.al, 2014).

For instance, the directives by regulators such as: HEFCE and SFC to all HEIs under their control to adopt a “risk-based-approach” to internal control. This approach should be a model or a risk management system that can identify/detect, investigate and control all types of risk which should be appraised and reviewed regularly. And in 2013, HEFCE again re-echoed the need for HEIs to maintain an effective internal control system that would guarantee the application of key objectives of a sound risk management framework. Therefore, HEIs would need to demonstrate that these controls are all encompassing as it relates to all risk types, but focusing on the most prominent risks, to produce a robust and balanced portfolio of risk exposure (HEFCE, 2013).

Therefore, this practice should be based on a clearly articulated policy, that would require regular review and monitoring and ensure that needed action is taken where appropriate. Hence an identified individual would be responsible for its coordination and management and the Board, Senior management and other officers must key-in and commit to this program. Furthermore, this risk management process should form and become a culture in the organisation by aligning it to the institutions’ strategic objectives and embedded into the daily business process (HEFCE, 2013).

HEFCE sees risk as *“The threat or possibility that an action or event will adversely or beneficially affect an organisation’s ability to achieve its objectives”* (HEFCE, 2008: p.4). Put succinctly, risk management as a process ensures that objectives are achieved, and adverse threats are controlled or reduced to barest minimum thereby ensuring maximum utilisation of opportunities. To this regard, it must be noteworthy to state that risk management is not necessarily about avoiding all risk, but a fundamental understanding of risk exposure and effective way of dealing with such (Soin et.al, 2014). Examples of some major risks identified by HEFCE include but not limited to: Financial, Strategic, Estates, Reputation, Health and Safety, Staffing, Students, Overseas operations and Research (HEFCE, 2005). Therefore, there should be a framework to an integrated approach to risk, with the aim for organizations to be more efficient and well equipped to seize opportunities. According to HEFCE (2005: p.5) *“Good risk management practice is about having a holistic approach, driven by a desire to balance stability and innovation.”*

Further realistic guidance on how HEIs can improve and align their risk management processes to their strategic objectives is to ensure a top-down and bottom-up approach of the risk

management process as proposed by HEFCE. Appendix 2.5 shows an illustration of the process of risk management objectives as recommended by HEFCE for institutions to adopt.

The risk management approach by HEFCE is one which derived its foundation from private sector ideas and HEIs are enjoined to enforce it as a form of imposed self-regulation. However, institutions are free to differ from HEFCE's model or templates but must be able to prove to the regulatory body that they are effectively able to manage their risk exposures (Soin et.al, 2014) and some of these risks have been discussed in section 2.10 below.

Sections 2.5 to 2.7 are essential to understanding the context and distinctiveness of the academic sector, how it has evolved over the years and the classification of UK HEIs into 'Ancient', 'Civic' and 'Post-92' Universities. These sections also discussed about the devolved educational powers, governance and legislation within the UK – reason this research is focusing only on Scottish HEIs. Finally, these sections also discussed about the debate or concerns on the introduction of 'New Public Management' or 'New Managerialism' to UK HEIs. The objective of these sections is to understand the environment, culture and the regulation of HEIs. It has also helped to understand the evolution of risk management within the HEIs and how they have adjusted to the new dynamic educational environment.

However, the next two sections discuss some of the major risk that threatens HEIs from achieving their goals and measures taken to mitigate such risks. These discussions would be essential to help understand the roles, responsibilities and practices of everyone responsible for the management of risk while also creating awareness of the design of a good risk management system for an effective risk management.

2.8 RISK AFFECTING HIGHER INSTITUTIONS

With globalisation and advancement in technology, HEI's are becoming more and more exposed to risk and uncertainties. According to Helsloot and Jong (2006), these risk and crisis may come from various areas such as: leadership or governance failures, partnership, consortium or business relationships, events from externalities, crisis as it concerns students' welfare, safety or other community members, violation of governmental or regulatory laws or a host of other factors. Also, the University Risk Management Association (URIMA, 2007) highlights various factors that leads to increased risk on higher institutions to include but not exhaustive: 'competition for students, staff and faculty, need for increased accountability, external government scrutiny, governing boards or public scrutiny, technological changes,

increased legislation and marketplace competition' etc. These risks if not mitigated urgently may lead to high profile or reputational risk. Appendix 2.6 presents a table of some risk potential categories and its associated hazard that affects HEIs.

Various definitions of risk as put forward by various bodies and school of thoughts is presented in Appendix 2.7 of this report. Although, there is yet to be a universal agreed definition of risk, however, most definitions of risk are either centred around loss event or uncertainties. Thus, the definition by HEFCE as presented below and as stated previously in chapter 2.1, has been adopted for the purpose of this discourse not just for the fact that it captures both the upside and downside risk in its definition, but because being *de facto* regulator of HEI's in most parts of the UK, using HEFCE's view of risk will present the opportunity to critically and holistically assess the implications of risk management in the educational sector.

HEFCE (2001, p.4) adopts the "*frequently used definition*" to define risk as '*the threat or possibility that an action or event will adversely or beneficially affect an organisation's ability to achieve its objectives*'. This definition allows HEFCE to offer a direct relationship between objectives and risk which according to them, "*objectives include taking opportunities such as launching a new course or winning a new research contract*". Hence "*the risk of taking or not taking these opportunities may significantly affect the achievement of the institution's objectives*" (HEFCE, 2001; p.4).

Furthermore, in HEFCE's analysis, these objectives and risks cut across various levels of the institution namely: Strategic or Corporate, Faculty level, Departmental and Personal levels. The table below represents some examples of the relationships between objectives and risk at these various institutional levels.

Table 2.2: *Some examples of links between risk and objectives at various institutional levels*

Level	Objective	Risk
Strategic	To be a reputable and world class institution	Unable to compete resourcefully with other world class institutions
Faculty	Able to attract, employ and retain world class academic staff	Inability to attract staff due to low faculty profile
Academic Department	Maintaining and continuous improvement of RAE rating	Departure of key personnel/staff
Estate Department	Effective and efficient in constructing new teaching blocks	Construction company going burst
Personal	To be seen by students as a top-notch lecturer	More time spent on research activities than anticipated.

Source: HEFCE (2001)

Besides the above relationship between risk and objectives as depicted above, the Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) have been relentless in its efforts to help organisations mitigate risk and it has so far successfully been able to help create a mutual language around risk controls which is now generally seen as risk management (NACUBO, 2007). COSO (2004) detailed five key risk types that can prevent an organisation from achieving its objectives except they are properly managed:

2.8.1 Strategic Risk

As shown already in ‘table 2.2’ above, organisations have their strategic or specific objectives. This type of risk is concerned with future key decisions that needs to be made, and the emphasis here is how these missions and values of the organisation are to be translated into corporate or strategic goals which may involve issues such as: where to invest, which policies to pursue or which to forego, whether to seek expansion and how etc. As policy makers, strategic risk is very important as every action or inaction in relation to this risk could either make or mar the organisation (NACUBO, 2007).

2.8.2 Financial Risk

Risk due to loss of assets. Hommel (2009) explains this by depicting with example of an institution that is historically conservative, decides to invest heavily in foreign and private equities with various investment managers, and at the same time entering into hedging agreements. How will this institution manage the potential market and credit risk which may affect them negatively? Will the market perform as predicted?

This type of risk is almost self-revealing. Assessment of this risk deals with both the overall financial resources and the necessary actions taken to protect and direct those funds. Therefore, it is a major concern for every organisation and their policy makers. Summers and Boothroyd (2009, p.12) pinpoint some areas of financial risk that every institution should consider, and these include:

- *‘Income generation and expenditure patterns’ – i.e., what are the major drivers, and can they be efficiently and effectively managed?*
- *‘The systems and key financial parameters across the HEI. Yes, the finance director may understand, but do other managers and governors? Are they all aware or do they all have an understanding of sensitive and major issues in the business plan?’*
- *Relating (in a not-for-profit environment) how non-financial objectives can be considered alongside financial issues?*
- *Accounting and security issues – avoiding fraud and ensuring that accounting statements meet legal, regulatory and wider stakeholder needs and expectations.*
- *Achieving value for money and efficiency. How can money go further or have a greater impact?*

Source: (Summers and Boothroyd, 2009: p.12)

Furthermore, there are also other areas as it relates to HEIs other than the above where specific financial risk abound which include: operational areas, e.g., human resource costs (which include cost on future pension of staff), and estates/infrastructure, e.g., cost on insurance. For instance, although HEIs are generally regarded as low risk by lenders, but for insurance purposes, they are seen to have a very high risk (Summers and Boothroyd, 2009).

2.8.3 Operational Risk

Operational risk is often widely regarded as “*the risk of loss resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems or from external events*” (BCBS, 2001; p.2). Management of this risk is often seen as a management function and also a major concern for governing boards to ensure and encourage a risk culture within the institution as risk from any of the factors listed in the definition above could result in the institution’s inability to achieve its strategic objectives or even become a threat to business continuity (Andersen, 2009). For instance, in all HEIs, people related risk are important factors of risk management that must never be overlooked. To this regard, Summers and Boothroyd (2009) highlighted some of these grey areas to include:

- The competence of staff at various levels of the institution in delivering academic expertise and/or meet the other needs of the institution.
- How effective is the succession plan for key staff and governors?
- Is the institution well equipped for the next planning phase as regards staff development and resourcing?
- What is the assurance that can be obtained from the recent staff recruitment exercise? i.e., is it an institution that the very best would want to join and what is the staff turnover rate? Etc.

Although answers to these key issues above should always be part of the HR strategy, but it will serve as a great influence on the way and manner the HEI approach its risk and how future investment opportunities are determined.

2.8.4 Legal/Compliance Risk

Summers and Boothroyd (2009) opines that this class of risk is gradually becoming very important in HEIs because of two key factors: increasing volume of ‘for profit activities by HEIs (such as: consultancy, spin out functions, etc). Although the common practise among some HEIs these days is to set up subsidiary companies (or engage in similar approach) so as to enable them to reduce legal risk to its barest minimum, institutions that are mainly research focused still tend to be faced with legal threat when contracts go wrong; and secondly in several HEIs the independence of teaching staff to get involved in external engagements with huge fundamental risk if no contractual agreements are in place or not clear. In this case, HEIs needs to ensure adequate procedures are well followed for instance, the requirement for proper documentation for staff engaging in any external activity. Furthermore, there is the compliance risks that the organisation may receive sanctions for failing to comply with regulatory, externally imposed laws as well as internal policies, procedures and processes such as safety, interest conflict etc. (Black and Baldwin 2012).

2.8.5 Project Risk

Project risk relates to any such risk that poses danger towards the completion of a project successfully thereby causing a harmonic effect on the accrued benefits from the said project such as the operational and strategic benefits. This type of risk may occur when a new service, product or provision are being developed, or when there are significant changes to an existing system, or a new system is being developed. When compared to operational and strategic risks,

project risk is usually considered as a short-term risk because upon completion of the project, these risks would either be categorised as operational or strategic risks (PKF, 2011).

2.8.6 Reputational Risk

All or any of these risks emanating from the aforementioned, may/can severely damage the institution's brand/reputation. They may also result in legal risk or litigation. Hommel and King, 2013). HEIs continuously seek to build and enhance their reputation as this a key tool for breeding more students, more service sales, more research income, more consultancy etc. Reputation generally like goodwill, are based on perceptions that are built-up over-time and cannot be easily measured or quantified though there is a possibility reflecting upon some reputational indicators. Reputation is not a permanent phenomenon as it is often said to be transient; whereas it takes several years to achieve a good reputation, however, it can be destroyed easily by the wink of an eye in the event of a negative event.

2.9 MEASURES TO CONTROL OR MITIGATE RISK

The above risks discussed in section 2.8 can be avoided, mitigated or controlled when there is a well-defined risk management framework and process embedded into the institution's culture. However, for the framework or process to be effective, it is the responsibility of the board and senior management or decision makers to oversee and direct the process. These oversight functions, roles and responsibilities should be captured in the RM policy document of the institution.

2.9.1 Tone from the top

Risk management just like every other governance process would be more effective and yield best results when senior executives and governing board strategically sets the tone and lead from the top. Although, for a risk management framework to be embedded successfully, there must be a top-down – bottom-up communication process, however, for effective results, there must be strategic level implementation (PKF, 2011.). It is therefore important that the board approves a risk policy for the institution and should have adequate knowledge of risk management to enable them to continuously and effectively direct the risk management process of the institution. Consequently, the risk management responsibilities of board members and management team should be clearly defined and articulated.

It has been advised that the administration of the risk management process is delegated to a 'risk champion' within the management team as this would yield an effective outcome because there is a clear responsibility for continuous development, monitoring and coordination of the University's risk management framework (Lam, 2000; Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2003; Aabo, et.al., 2005). However, PKF (2011), cautions that proper care should be taken in order not to take away the risk management responsibilities of the entire management team. However, it is usually the role of the audit committee to guarantee assurance as regards the adequacy and effectiveness of the risk management framework whereas the overarching strategic responsibility of oversight of major risks rests with the board (Adam and Shavit, 2009; Abraham, 2013).

2.9.2 Risk Management Policy

As previously discussed above, it is imperative for board to approve a risk management policy for the institution. This should be the first step towards instituting or the development of a risk management framework. According to PKF (2011), for best practice within the academic sector, the institution's risk management policy should at minimum include the following: 'Policy statement' – this refers to the general attitude and commitment to the risk management process; 'Risk appetite' – refers to the risk attitude and the amount of risk the institution is willing to accept; 'Roles and responsibilities' – states the various roles and responsibilities of everyone involved in the risk management process (e.g. the University board, audit committee, management team, risk manager, staff etc.).

Others according to PKF (2011) include: 'Internal control and assurance' – this should set out the link and relationship between the risk management process, internal control system and the function of both the internal and external audits; 'Monitoring and review' – there should be an obligation for a regular or periodic (stated in the policy statement) review and monitoring of the effectiveness of the risk management framework; 'Risk strategy' – institutions are expected to capture either in their policy statement, or within a separate strategy document, the following key considerations: i. risk categorisation and identification process, ii. Risk evaluation techniques – e.g., risk rating matrix, iii. Techniques for monitoring and measuring risks, and iv. Strategies and procedures for risk management training and awareness).

Having discussed the risk faced by institutions and recommended measures to be taken by management to mitigate these risks. Thus, discussion in this section is critical to understanding

the roles and responsibilities of the key actors in the risk management framework while also creating awareness on what constitutes a good risk structure for an effective risk management. Therefore, the next section takes a look at government's role and interest in HEIs as well as expectations while also ensuring HEIs continue to deliver on their strategic objectives. This brings us to discussion on the role of regulators or regulatory oversight and how they ensure compliance from HEIs, as well as some major challenges regulators may encounter while carrying out these oversight functions.

2.10 THE ROLE OF THE SCOTTISH GOVERNMENT IN HEIs

The Scottish Government over the last decade prioritised education as its defining mission and thus identified Universities as one of its key areas in achieving growth and securing sustained strategic economic development across the country. HEIs contribute through the provision of knowledge, innovation and necessary skills for the sustenance of development in the country. Universities according to the Scottish Further and Higher Education Funding Council – SFC contribute over £6.7 billion annually to the economy and over £1.3 billion making it the third largest industry in the country (SFC, n.d.).

2.10.1 Relationship between the Scottish Government and the SFC

There is a growing competition in the global academic terrain thus the Scottish government in a bid to ensure Scottish HEIs sustain their competitive edge in the international environment, charged the Scottish Further and Higher Education Funding Council (SFC) with accomplishing excellence and equity within the education and skills landscape across Scotland (Universities Scotland, 2019). The SFC is a non-departmental public institution which was formed by the merger of the 'Scottish Further Education Funding Council and the Scottish Higher Education Funding Council established through the 2005 'Further and Higher Education (Scotland) Act and key among its remit is funding research, innovation, teaching and learning among other activities in Universities and Colleges as well as other institutes of higher learning within Scotland (Scottish Executive, 2004).

The SFC although believed to have some degree of independence on statutory basis (Dickinson, 2019), however, its governing Board is appointed by ministers whereas the Board's Chief Executive Officer reports to the Scottish Parliament. The SFC at least once a year receives letter of guidance from the Cabinet Secretary outlining Government's strategic objectives and priorities for the coming year allows the board to set its strategic plans and

advice HEIs accordingly thereby ensuring that these HEIs are continuously able to align their missions and objectives to the strategic policies of the government.

2.10.1.1 The Scottish Universities Single Outcome Agreements

Therefore, the SFC in a bid to ensuring effective and efficient alignment of Universities' outcomes to government policies; introduced the University Outcome Agreements in 2012 which is believed to assist the Scottish HEIs to demonstrate and better enhance its contribution to government's strategic plans in exchange for funding receipts from the Scottish government which was famously referred to as 'something for something' by then First minister – Alex Salmond (Dickinson, 2019). Outcome Agreements serves as a mechanism for engagement between SFC and Scottish HEIs as well as a tool for oversight responsibilities by SFC on HEIs and enables the HEIs to be in alignment with the Scottish Government's mission while also presenting the opportunity for HEIs to present their contribution towards the achievement of this mission.

The SFC in consultation with HEIs via Universities Scotland developed a wide range of measures which it uses to monitor performance and progress of these HEIs as it relates to their expected outcomes. Every institution is obliged to present their strategy in line with the national and institutional measures to achieve their expected outcomes which is jointly agreed upon by the SFC and published annually on their website. Although it is the responsibility of the Quality Assurance (Scotland) Agency to ensure academic quality in HEIs, however, the SFC have a legislative responsibility to ensure quality, efficiency and effectiveness in the programmes it is funding as well as meeting the needs of end users.

Outcome Agreements since its introduction therefore has become a powerful strategy for the Scottish Government (albeit onerous and bureaucratic for Universities) in ensuring outputs delivered by HEIs in return for (arguably diminished) public investment is in alignment to their mission (Dickinson, 2019). This discourse is fascinating because HEIs in England are regulated explicitly based on 'outcomes' rather than 'outputs' whereas in Scotland, the quality of outputs and their improvements is thus jointly regulated. However, to get funded, HEIs are expected to separately and directly negotiate with the SFC government's desired outcomes.

Thus, this process according to the SFC have allowed it to recognise and fully understand the challenges encountered by HEIs as well as the opportunities (SFC, 2019) and with this closer engagement and facilitation with HEIs through OA, SFC are able to gain access to a huge range

of data, statistics and evidence that has been useful to support the government with vital information and advice on strategic policies and support where necessary during the budgetary process as well as providing advice and information in confidence to Ministers and parliament for the greater good of the educational system in Scotland (Universities Scotland, 2019).

In summary, it is expected the outcome agreements would be an avenue for HEIs through their diverse missions, demonstrate their implementation of Scottish Government priorities in return of funding from the government. The SFC refers to this approach as ‘relationship-based engagement’ which according to them guarantees for consistent reporting methods through outcome agreements statements, greater transparency and accountability and also presents the opportunity for HEIs to discuss their broader objectives as well as their strategic challenges with the SFC. However, there are fears that this process could risk being jeopardised in the foreseeable future as too much (outcomes) is being asked for from HEIs in comparison to what they are getting (funding).

2.11 PERCEIVED REGULATORY CHALLENGES

Risk-based regulation in Universities and Colleges presents a number of challenges for regulators. For example, there is the difficulty of deciding which institutions should be categorised as low risk or high risk. This categorisation could well be controversial, and regulators need to justify such decisions with evidence to all stakeholders such as: HEIs and the general public (Hommel and King, 2013). This challenge according to King (2011), is one that could easily generate prolonged controversy if not handled properly by regulators.

Reputation, prestige and to some extent – product is what defines HEIs and increases their marketability. There is no clear-cut relationship between prestige and quality (especially for teaching activities), and it is possible for high-repute HEIs to escape external scrutiny on non-quality grounds based on their reputational status. Such HEIs may maintain top-notch RM systems and could as well contribute to the growth of good RM practices within the sector; after all, quality assurance is all about positive development and diffusion of examples of best practices to other institutions and not just accountability. It is argued though, that the application of selective scrutiny may prove not so effective as a risk management control tool (Hommel and King, 2013).

With the relaxation of some controls and the encouragement for more competition in the higher educational sector by the government, there is a considerable growth in the number of private

owned HEIs which has further ensured the sector-wide growth of entrepreneurialism (DBIS, 2016; Buckner, 2017; Hunt and Boliver, 2020), therefore, regulators should understand that this ongoing trend of increased competition and entrepreneurialism that has crept into the educational system would only lead to heightened risk and thus effective regulation would require that every provider irrespective of type (public or private) are subjected to regular monitoring as well as ‘systems review’ for quick detection of ‘red-flags’ or early warning signs. However, selective enforcement can be applied based on their risk rating and this should involve the sanctions and penalties in the event of breach or noncompliance (Baldwin and Black, 2016; Borraz et.al., 2020).

Furthermore, the zeal to guarantee a highly transparent, exclusive and evidence-based risk assessments will rashly limit regulatory options. Precisely, this could culminate in a false selection or of some organisations as ‘risk carriers’, exposing regulators as prey to the dynamic and uncertain situations due to over-reliance of inflexible analytical tools for risk assessment (Baldwin et.al. 2012). Regulators may thus become too rigid in certain ways of risk assessment. While it may be justified to classify some institutions as ‘low risk’ because of their reputation and track records, this could mean that regulators may not frequently carryout oversight risk monitoring duties of a large number of institutions; and this could result in systemic failures over the inability to detect certain risks (i.e., warning signals) emanating from competitive pressures (Hommel and King, 2013; Hommel and Woods, 2018).

Finally, the practice of selective regulation thereby providing HEIs and their students with varying levels of protection due to their risk rating could in the long run lead to criticisms from stakeholders. Thus, regulators may likely react to public outcry with the avoidance of judgemental discretion (Baldwin et.al., 2012), this could however, lead to bureaucratic and rigid rule-following which is totally different from the objectives of risk-based regulation. Risk-based regulation entails that regulators are seen as undertaking a formalised set of tasks in a clearly stated and highly transparent manner (Hood, 2011; Hommel and King, 2013). Therefore, these and several other specific issues should be considered as likely factors of regulatory failure (Hood et al. 2001; King et al. 2007; Rothstein and Downer 2012). Edwards (2010) explained that lessons from other organisational sectors that have been subjected to risk-based regulation suggests the benefits of deregulation may be in the risk of never being achieved.

With the ‘Outcome Agreements’ (discussed in section 2.10 above), regulators are able to ensure compliance of their objectives from HEIs. However, a key issue lies with the fact that diminishing financial support from SFC (Dickinson, 2019) have contributed to HEIs being more innovative in order to be self-sufficient and less reliant on government funding. Thus, there are concerns that this may again lead to increased risk taking and less compliance on SFC guidelines with fears of some moral hazards or may even result systemic failures if not carefully managed by all concerned parties.

Therefore, there is danger that the positive relationship between regulatory oversight and perceived risk-taking by institutions within the context of risk-based regulation may never be achieved. Entrepreneurial business schools most importantly, may escape regulatory scrutiny because of their own market position with HEIs failure to institutionalise and translate regulatory guidelines and standards into their internal risk governance objectives (Hommel and King, 2013).

2.12. RISK CULTURE

Fundamental to influencing the collective attitudes of employees or people within an organisation is culture. As discussed by Barnabei (2008), the impact of culture in influencing the strategic decisions in an organisation cannot be undermined as it has been evident in various critical decisions of organisations ranging from how swiftly firms may respond to market changes to how their programs are designed. Cameron and Quinn (2011) regard culture as the element or factor that builds relationship among the units within an organisation and reflect the standards and objectives that improves the stability and guarantees success of the firm.

Thus, having a strong risk culture within an organisation will ensure general risk awareness and also provide guarantee for integrity regarding the everyday operations within the organisation. As previously discussed in section 2.9, it is important that all member of staff within the organisation from board to senior management and every other employee have clearly defined roles and responsibilities in line with the organisational standards. Specifically, risk culture involves all aspects regarding how risk management is affected by corporate culture thus, establishing the basis of risk identification, analysis and control. It is essential that the risk culture is supported and driven by senior management and there should be an effective internal communication framework in place to create awareness and ensure the Board are able to effectively make decisions (Brooks, 2010).

Furthermore, COSO (2004) encourages a common risk language which is important for a successful risk culture within an organisation. As such, Brooks (2010) advises organisations to regularly train and educate employees in order to create awareness of the often-changing social norms and also the emerging new risks and these training programs could also serve to provide feedback on management actions as well as a channel to report risks and concerns. Tonello (2007) encourages firms to also integrate reputation risk to their RM framework because it promotes a culture of risk awareness within the organisation. Finally, Thomya and Saenchaiyathon (2015) in their study found out that there is a positive relationship between risk culture and firm performance. Therefore, it is essential for decision makers to always consider their organisational culture as well as the risk culture in particular because it is vital to the achievement of their strategic goals and objectives (Brooks, 2010).

2.13 CONCLUSION

Presented in this chapter is a broad review of literature within the focus and context of the subject matter under investigation which is to '*Conceptualise the impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs)*'. Therefore, the key concepts (Risk, Risk Management and UK HEIs) and their relationships were critically discussed.

Summarily, sections 2.1 presented an overview of risk to help understand the dynamism of risk in order to fully comprehend the overarching purpose of this research. Critical examination to the definition of risk were discussed to enable the researcher to adopt a working definition for this study while sections 2.2 to 2.4 presented critical assessments on Risk, Risk Management as some major frameworks or models for managing risk to help evaluate and understand the structures and practices of RM within the HEI context. Furthermore, considerations regarding the selection of risk management models by organisations as well as the benefits and criticisms of risk management as presented by several academic literature were also discussed. This created an understanding of how key components of the risk management system have been coupled in order to have a solid background knowledge on the operability of these risk management architectures, structures and practices so the researcher could examine the risk management architecture of case HEIs.

Sections 2.5 to 2.7 are critical to understanding the context and uniqueness of the academic sector, how it has evolved over the years and the classification of UK HEIs into 'Ancient', 'Civic' and 'Post-92' Universities. These sections also discussed about the devolved

educational powers, regulation and legislation within the UK. These sections also presented discussions on the debate or concerns surrounding 'New Managerialism' in HEIs. The objective of these sections is to understand the environment, culture and the regulation of HEIs. It also helped to create awareness on the evolution of risk management within the HEIs and how they have adjusted to the new dynamic educational environment.

Sections 2.8 and 2.9 discussed the risk faced by institutions and recommended measures to be taken by management to mitigate these risks. Thus, discussion in these sections is critical to understanding the roles and responsibilities of the key actors in the risk management framework while also creating awareness on what constitutes a good risk structure for an effective risk management. The final sections (2.10 to 2.12) looked at government's role and interest in HEIs as well as expectations while also ensuring HEIs continue to deliver on their strategic objectives, the role of regulators or regulatory oversight and how they ensure compliance from HEIs, as well as some major challenges regulators may encounter while carrying out these oversight functions and finally, the risk culture within HEIs. The importance of these sections creates awareness on the implication of risk management practices within the HEI environment.

These discussions, however, will be used to evaluate the findings from this study as would be presented in the concluding chapters of this research. In conclusion, this literature review chapter present critical discussions and appraisal regarding the aim, objectives and research questions (see chapters 1.3 and 3.1 respectively) of this research which was vital to provide the background knowledge of the study, identify knowledge gaps, useful in formulating both quantitative questionnaires and qualitative interview questions (see figure 3.3) as well as ensured that the researcher is able to identify how the study has contributed to further knowledge. The next chapter (Methodology) presents the systematic practical approach or methods applied in this research for a valid and credible results.

Figure 2.7: Conceptual Framework – Linking Research Aims, Objectives, Literature Review to Research Questions.

Source: Author.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

INTRODUCTION

This chapter is an outline of the research methods and the rationale behind each method used in this study to seek answers to the research puzzle: ‘**Conceptualising the impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) – A focus on Scottish Universities**’. As earlier discussed in chapter 1, the scope and parameters of this study had been restricted only to HEIs in Scotland because of the different legislation that exists between Scottish Universities and Universities in other parts of the UK. As such, the scope and spectrum of the study (Marrelli, 2007; Baxter and Jack, 2008) entails the careful selection of some institutions as case reference based on their risk management profile (informed judgement from quantitative strand of the study), status, rating, location etc.

Therefore, based on the research objectives and research questions (section 3.1), the sequential mixed method (section 3.4.1) was adopted for the study which resulted in a flexible iterative two-phased approach of data collection and analysis. The first phase (section 3.5) of the study involved the collection of quantitative data through survey instruments with Likert-scale questions, while the second phase (section 3.6) informed by results from the initial phase involved an in-depth semi-structured interview with risk experts from the Universities selected as case studies. The uniqueness and objectives of this study (see section 3.5) meant that this research was exclusive to institutions with fully embedded risk management framework and thus a survey was carried out to ascertain such Universities, while participants for Interviews were selected based on results from the survey. This also meant that interviews were only exclusive to high-ranking risk officers (risk experts) in order to ensure that information obtained is reliable for a credible and valid result.

However, due to some challenges encountered (see section 3.6.2.2) during the selection of case institutions, Documents analysis (section 3.6.2.2) was included as an additional data collection tool in order to enhance credibility and validity of the research. Furthermore, the chapter discusses analysis of results and findings (section 3.7) for both the quantitative and the qualitative data. The quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics and presented in tables while the qualitative data was analysed thematically. Also discussed in this chapter is how analysis of results and findings from both strands of the study were successfully integrated

(section 3.7.3). Finally, and as a summary, this chapter evaluates the justification of every research method used in this study as it relates to mixed method approach, sampling techniques, document analysis, data collection techniques and data analysis thereof etc., while also outlining the ethical considerations (section 3.8) and providing needed clarifications to the delimitations of the study (section 3.10) in order to establish credibility and trustworthiness.

3.1 RESEARCH AIMS, OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS

The overarching aim of this research is to conceptualise the impact of Risk Management on the structures, practices and processes in UK Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) and to understand its adoption, integration, development, and changes in relation to its implementation. Initially, data was only sourced through the mixed (qualitative and quantitative) method and analysis thereof was proposed to be carried out statistically and thematically. Thus, going by these comprehensive aims, and challenges encountered, overtime, the researcher's thoughts were subsequently modified to include documents analysis as discussed in section 3.6.2.2 below.

3.1.1 Research Aim

The aim of this research is to critically assess the impact and effects of risk management on the structures and practices of Higher Institutions in the UK with a direct focus on Scottish HEIs only.

3.1.2 Research Objectives

As already set out in chapter 1 of this study, the research objectives for this study are:

1. To evaluate the structures and practices of risk management within the HEI context.
2. To analyse the patterns of adjustment subsequent to adoption, implementation and/or restructuring of the risk management framework.
3. To investigate the implications of risk management practices in HEIs.

3.1.3 Research Questions

1. How do HEIs structure and execute their risk management functions?
2. How do the different institutional and technical factors influence the adoption and implementation of HEIs risk management frameworks?
3. What are the impact and effects of risk management in HEIs?

4. How can HEIs advance and align their risk management architecture to better suit the needs of their business contexts?

The objectives of this research (which are the pillars on which the aim of this research would be achieved) as highlighted above were essential to the selection of literature reviewed in this study. Therefore, based on the awareness from literature review and the research objectives, the research questions have been carefully formulated (see table 2.7) and these questions were fundamental in justifying the methodology adopted for this research while also serving as indicators to ensure that the objectives and aim of the study had been achieved (see chapter 6). This justification of the methodological choices adopted for this study based on the research objectives and research questions are presented in subsequent sections of this chapter.

3.2 PHILOSOPHICAL POSITION

Generally, the views, knowledge and understanding of a researcher is habitually linked to the philosophy such a researcher may adopt in his studies. This is often said to be a natural phenomenon which occurs subconsciously (Wilson, 2014). Slife and Williams (1995) connotes that although it occurs intuitively, however it needs to be identified which is why Dainty (2007) stressed for an understanding and the need for a philosophical position when conducting a research because it is essential as it helps the researcher determine a suitable approach to the study.

Thus, the philosophical position of this study may not have completely been the views of the researcher but emanated due to the nature of the research problem and the research questions as outlined in section 3.1. Therefore, this research is underpinned by the pragmatist philosophical view because “*pragmatists place the research problem and research questions at the centre of the research and use the methods they consider to be the most appropriate in generating the most significant insights into their research*” (Wilson, 2014; p.19). Risk management in Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) is quite a new phenomenon and trend and as such research in this area is still in its preliminary stages. Therefore, “*Conceptualising the impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs)*”, requires an approach, method and/or strategy that is considered ‘best suitable’ (considering the research problem and questions) rather than adhering to a particular paradigm. Several authors refer to this as ‘relational epistemology’ i.e., the relationship in studies the researcher deems best-fit

method(s) for that particular research (Patton, 1990; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003a; 2003b; Creswell, 2003; Biesta, 2010; Alise and Teddlie; 2010).

A key benefit derived from ensuring that the research method is determined by the research questions is vital in guarding against adopting a ‘forced-selection’ technique but rather a ‘best-fit’ (Wilson, 2014; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Morgan, 2007; Creswell, 2003) and this helped to minimise perceived outcome of researcher’s bias. Creswell (2003) rightly observed that, a researcher’s philosophical position may lead to research bias since it may be bereft of all possible approaches needed to gain new knowledge and more so, may not be useful particularly when there are limited studies in this area. Therefore, to enable the researcher to adopt the ‘best-fit’ method(s) for this study, the research questions were paramount. Several methods that appeared suitable for this study were tested with the help of a framework by Mutch (2013) as shown in figure 3.1a and 3.1b.

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design according to several academic literature is an overall strategy or a unique ‘plan’ that integrates the various parts, components or sections of the research in a logical and coherent manner that ensures the research problem is effectively addressed by the researcher thus ensuring minimal bias and maximum validity (Burns 2000; Bryman 2001; Easterby-Smith). Several academic texts have classified research design differently. Some authors delineate it along the qualitative and quantitative research methods (Maykut and Morehouse, 1994; Burns, 2000; Creswell, 2009), some, fixed and flexible research designs (Adèr et.al, 2008), and yet others based on research type i.e., explorative, descriptive, experimental, etc. (Robson, 1993). While it may not be questionable to portray research designs along these various research taxonomies, however what seems absurd according to De Vaus (2001) is that some either confuse it with research methods or worse still, some have erroneously equated certain research design with certain data collection techniques thereby giving the wrong impression that they are intrinsic or mutually inclusive.

Therefore, to ensure the research problem is addressed effectively and unambiguously with minimal bias and a high degree of validity and reliability, it is imperative that appropriate research design(s) is/are selected based on the research question while at the same time utilising

the most appropriate method of data collection (De Vaus, 2001; Rowley, 2002; Blumberg et.al, 2005). According to De Vaus:

“We can always find some evidence consistent with almost any theory. However, we should be sceptical of the evidence, and rather than seeking evidence that is consistent with our theory we should seek evidence that provides a compelling test of the theory” (2001, p.11).

Reasoning from the above premise therefore, figure 3.1b below is a carefully structured framework adapted from Mutch (2013) used as a guideline for the construct of the research design of this study which allows for flexibility and ensures selection of the most appropriate research methods for this study based on the research. What gives credence to this approach is the judgement from various authors who conclude with their summary of the key features of a research design to include: ‘a well-defined research problem, data collection tools and techniques, the study population, and data analysis methods’ (Kotari, 1990; Rowley, 2002; Blumberg et.al, 2005; Bryman, 2006; Wilson, 2014).

Figure 3.1a: Framework for choosing an appropriate research design

Source: Mutch (2013)

Figure 3.1b: Research design Framework

Source: Own editing – Adapted from Mutch (2013).

Therefore, while the above framework was a very useful guide for the selection of the appropriate research strategy, research techniques and data analysis method – discussed below; however, there are instances where some overlap which resulted in more than one strategy being applied. For instance, the survey design initially was used to evaluate the structures and practices of risk management across Universities. However, during the interview process, participants were asked to make clarifications on certain areas regarding responses from their questionnaire.

It is vital to mention that although the design of this study is structured essentially based on the research questions, it is useful to note that it would have resulted in a wild-goose-chase if time-horizon were not also factored into the design selection process. ‘Time-horizon’ is a major factor that researchers often consider when considering the choice of a research design (Blumberg et.al, 2005; Bryman, 2006) because in academic research, student researchers are time-bound (often very limited) in their studies (Wilson, 2014). Therefore, because of the very limited time available for the completion of this academic research, it would not have been viable to use designs/approaches that is time consuming (e.g., observation) which would have been time consuming and doing so would have meant the study was not completed within the available time. Thus, the next section discusses the strategies applied in this research.

3.4 RESEARCH STRATEGY

The fundamental approach to selecting an appropriate research strategy for this study was particularly centred around the research questions. Creswell (2003) emphasises strongly on some specific conditions that would warrant a researcher to adopt a particular strategy. According to him, quantitative strategy would be best suited when: (a) *“the identification of factors that influence an outcome, (b) utility of an intervention, (c) understanding the best predictors of outcomes* (p.18). He further adds that the quantitative technique is best when a theory or an explanation needs to be verified or tested; whereas when the concept to be studied is a new phenomenon or research in that area has been minimal and more importantly when the investigator finds it difficult to ascertain or pinpoint the important variables to be studied and prevailing theories is not applicable to a specific sample or group that falls within the research, then it is best suited to use the qualitative strategy. Then when there is a phenomenon where either the qualitative or the quantitative technique becomes inadequate, a combination of both methods become inevitable (Morse, 1991; Creswell 2003).

The aim of this research as previously stated in section 3.1.1 above is to critically assess the impact and effects of risk management on the structures and practices of Higher Institutions in the UK. Therefore, since Risk management is quite a new phenomenon in the UK educational system, it was possible that not every institution within the boundary of this study (Scotland) would have fully adopted a risk management framework. Thus, to achieve a valid result on the research problem, it was vital that only institutions with a fully adopted risk management process were considered as case institutions for the study. However, considering the research

questions and the number of HEIs involved (16) within the boundary of this study coupled with the time limit for the completion of this academic research, cross-sectional survey (discussed further in section 3.5.1) was the most effective and efficient strategy (Check and Schutt, 2012; Saunders et.al, 2012; Wilson, 2014) which helped to determine those institutions with fully adopted risk management framework and further to identify participants (Risk Experts) for the phase 2 of the study.

Consequently, having identified the HEIs and the risk experts relevant to the study, follow-up interviews were conducted (discussed below) to seek clarification and validate information presented through initial responses from Phase 1 as well as eliciting more information necessary for validity and reliability of the study. Thus, this study had been conducted using a mix of both quantitative (Survey) and qualitative (Interviews and Documents analysis) techniques i.e., ‘mixed methods’ (discussed below in section 3.4.1) and was conducted in two phases which is discussed in sections 3.5 and 3.6 below.

3.4.1 Mixed Methods Rationale

Fundamental to adopting the mixed-method technique for this study was largely based on the research questions which significantly links to the aim of this study, that is to critically assess the impact and effects of risk management on the structures and practices of Higher institutions in the UK. As shown in figures 3.1a and 3.1b above, selecting mixed method for this study was purely driven by the research questions which resulted in both quantitative and qualitative methodology. Ridenour and Newman (2008, p.27) asserts that mixed method is a “*holistic methodology, where the methods are driven by the research questions linked to the purpose(s)*”. It involves the use of more than one method (i.e., qualitative and quantitative) in a study to seek answers to the research problem (Hesse-Biber, 2010; Ridenour and Newman, 2008).

Consequently, this research adopted a ‘sequential mixed-methods’ approach. This is an iterative two-phased follow-up approach (quantitative/qualitative) where data from the initial quantitative phase informed, contributed to and builds on the latter qualitative phase (see figure 3.2 and 3.4 below), while also being essential in the participant selection for the qualitative strand of the study and further assisted in corroborating, validating results, triangulation and generalise findings within the given population (Creswell and Plano Clark 2018; Creswell,

2009). Thus, this research was conducted in two phases (‘Phase 1’ being quantitative while ‘Phase 2’ was qualitative) as discussed in sections 3.5 and 3.6 below.

This approach presented the opportunity to evaluate the structures and practices of risk management within the HEI context (please see research question 1 above) quantitatively (results presented in chapter 4) by reaching out to a wider population using survey (Questionnaires). Survey questions were carefully designed majorly to elicit responses on “policies and procedures of risk management in HEIs” employed to manage risk and protect the institution” as well as informing on other objectives of the research (this has been enumerated in section 3.5 below). Based on this, the researcher was able to select relevant case institutions and gained more insight for the phase 2 of the study (qualitative) which is to (i.), analyse the patterns of adjustment subsequent to adoption, implementation and/or restructuring of the risk management framework, and (ii.), to investigate the implications of risk management practices in HEI. Please refer to objectives 2 and 3 and the relevant research questions in section 3.1 above.

The inherent advantages of the mixed-methods to this research is that it allows for data convergence (i.e. triangulation) which enhances the credibility of findings (Greene, et.al., 1989; Hesse-Biber, 2010; Bryman, 2006) and also complementarity (Greene et.al., 1989) and completeness (Bryman, 2006) which enhances better understanding of the research problem. More so, it provided a holistic understanding of the research problem being that results from “one method or phase helped developed or informed the other method” (Greene et.al., 1989, p.259).

Figure 3.2: Sequential Mixed Methods

Source: Wu (2011).

3.5 PHASE 1

At the start of this study, the researcher reviewed a wide range of literature, networked with experts in the field and carried out online searches to identify research gaps which was key to identifying the research problem. However, for better illustration and presentation, the narratives as regards phases 1 and 2 of this study were primarily concerned with the mode of data collection and analysis for both the quantitative and qualitative studies. As previously discussed, the first phase of a sequential mixed-methods research is the foundation on which the second phase is built. Thus, as highlighted in section 3.4.1, this phase was vital for participants selection and triangulation.

Triangulation

Triangulation refers to the use of several data sources and numerous approaches to analysing data thereby enhancing the study's credibility (Wilson, 2014). As discussed in section 3.6 and observed in chapters 4, 5 and 6 of this study, results from the quantitative analysis were used to verify, augment and integrated with the findings from the qualitative analysis of this research thereby enhancing the credibility and validity of the study.

Participant Selection

The aim and objectives of this research particularly as regards objectives 2 and 3 meant that it was exclusive to institutions with fully embedded risk management framework and participants with relevant expertise (risk managers or above) on risk management. Thus, to identify institutions and participants with these relevant criteria, it was vital to conduct a survey (section 3.5.1 below). Through this survey, the researcher was able to select case institutions and risk experts (section 3.6.2) for the second phase of the research. Thus, this process enabled the researcher to identify and select only the right participants for the study. Therefore, the following sections discusses in detail the mode and process of data collection for the phase 1 of this study while also explaining in detail the rationale behind each selected process.

3.5.1 Survey

Survey design is a suitable research methodology which is an essential research approach in describing, evaluating and exploring variables and inquiries of interest. According to Check and Schutt (2012), it entails "*the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions*". It is often used quantitatively (Saunders et.al, 2012), may be

used qualitatively or both (Singleton and Straits, 2009) to seek solutions to issues that have been raised or observed, ascertain if certain objectives have been achieved, to set standards for future references or comparisons, to evaluate set targets, analysis of trends over time and to define or conceptualise ‘what exists’, in what quantity and contexts (Isaac and Michael, 1997). Saunders et.al (2012, p.176) summarises that it is mostly used in answering “*what, who, where, how much and how many, questions*”.

Thus, after a careful consideration of relevant research designs against the research questions, time frame and objective rationale (see figure 3.1a and 3.1b above), cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the quantitative strand of this study. According to McIntyre (1999, p.74) “*Surveys are well suited in gathering demographic data that describe the composition of the sample. This is perfect for the intended objective which is to evaluate the structures and practices of RM within the UK HEI context (as per objective 1 above). Furthermore, due to want of time for this academic research, the cross-sectional survey design was also best suited for this objective and research question because it is inclusive and presents the capability of a wider reach compared to ‘observation’ (which is time consuming) while producing generalisable, empirical, quantifiable, standardised and statistically significant data with minimal resources i.e., limited time and budget (Groves et.al., 2009; Wilson, 2014). Additionally, surveys are generally more potent in eliciting information about thoughts, feelings and attitudes that may otherwise prove difficult to gauge through other techniques such as observation (McIntyre, 1999) thus, it also presented respondents the opportunity to remain anonymous (O’Leary, 2004) considering the nature of this study.*

There is often a misconception among researchers between **Survey** research design and ‘*survey tool*’ (De Vaus, 2013). Whereas Survey design as already noted entails the collection of information from a large group or population of humans about their ‘actions’, ‘opinions’ or ‘characteristics’, (Pinsonneault and Kraemer, 1993) and additionally useful in evaluating demand and impact assessment; but in contrast, *survey tool* is simply an instrument that is designed to support the survey design – e.g., data collection instrument (Salant and Dillman, 1994). Therefore, discussed below is ‘Questionnaire’ which was employed as the survey tool or instrument for data collection for this study.

3.5.1.1 Questionnaire

The cross-sectional survey design method usually gives the researcher the privilege to select from a wide range of data collection tools such as ‘questionnaire’, ‘interviews’, ‘observation’, ‘focus group’, unobtrusive methods etc. (De Vaus, 2001). Therefore, the questionnaire was regarded as the most suitable instrument to gather data for this strand of the study because of its inclusiveness and the potency to gather statistically significant data from a defined population and within limited resources (Groves et.al., 2009; Saunders et.al., 2012). Furthermore, considering the objective rationale (i.e., ‘what framework has been adopted, how long has the framework been in place, is it in compliance with regulatory directives, what are the challenges, who are the drivers of the framework etc. as shown in figure 3.3 below), the questionnaire instrument is best suitable to ascertain what exists, and in what context and quantity (Isaac and Michael, 1997) and according to Saunders et.al (2012, p.176) it is most suitable in answering “*what, who, where, how much and how many questions*”. Therefore, a closed ended - Likert scale questionnaire was used for this objective (see Appendix 3.1).

Sampling Technique

The purposive expert sampling technique was used to gather quantitative data for this research. Expert sampling is a subset of purposive sampling and it is a non-probability sampling technique employed by a researcher targeted towards only specific participants by virtue of their qualities, specialisation, experience or knowledge within a phenomenon of interest being studied by the researcher (Bernard, 2002; Patton, 2002; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Unlike random sampling techniques which involves sampling a cross-section of different ages, culture, background etc., the objective behind purposive expert sampling is to focus on people with specific characteristics who are willing and able to provide valuable contributions and insights to the study (Fray, 2018).

Thus, as discussed previously in chapter 1 and also highlighted in the introductory section of this methodology chapter, the scope of this study was only restricted to Scottish HEIs because of the separate legislation that exist between Scottish and other UK HEIs. Although it is often advised that managing risk should be the responsibility of everyone in an organisation (Arena, et.al., 2010), however, coordinating risk management activities is the responsibility of senior managers or executives with risk management expertise. Therefore, it was essential that only risk professionals responsible for coordinating risk activities within their institutions be

included in the sample study and as such, a careful and thorough analysis was carried out through the websites of the various institutions in the study population to identify staffs saddled with the responsibility of implementing and/or directing risk affairs as samples because, to ensure the study's credibility, reliability and validity; it is imperative that only people with the requisite knowledge of risk management are drawn as samples (Etikan, et.al., 2016).

A total of 90 questionnaires were distributed electronically using QuestionPro (an online software for distributing and analysing questionnaires) to named risk personnel across the 16 Scottish named Universities and the Glasgow School of Arts. Almost all Universities had more than one person listed as a risk personnel in their profile. Thus, to ensure the right persons were contacted, questionnaires were administered to every named risk personnel. This was keenly and actively monitored and fortunately, the researcher got feedback from most persons providing information and details of the right person to contact. Feedback was 16 (with 26 starting and 10 dropouts – dropouts were those who started but discovered halfway through that the questionnaire was designed for only risk professionals) with one from each University.

This feedback rate was either because some of these staffs named as risk personnel were actually not the right contacts, or some were no longer with the said institutions to which their websites had not been updated. Responses were analysed statistically and presented in tables and charts as presented in Chapter 4 of this study and this gave the researcher an informed judgement on the selection of the case institutions and specific interviewees for the phase 2 of this study as discussed below in section 3.6.

A major concern as it relates to 'expert sampling' is that anyone can claim to be an expert which may affect validity (Etikan, et.al., 2016). As already discussed, by making use of the various institutions' websites (and cases where information were not available, the researcher either contacted such institutions directly through email or phone or through snowballing i.e., referrals from colleagues) to get details of relevant contacts which successfully helped overcome such fears. However, this research is not ignorant of other seemingly challenges or pitfalls that have often been raised in some quarters regarding the use of survey design such as bias or errors of non-response, coverage, measurement, sampling etc. (Singleton and Straits, 2009; Check and Schutt, 2012; Dillman et.al, 2014). Therefore, necessary step taken to allay these fears have been discussed hereunder.

Sampling Error: Several authors advocate the use of probability sampling to ensure randomisation and help avoid sampling error (Creswell, 2003, Saunders, et.al., 2012; Wilson, 2014). However, due to the uniqueness of this study, selecting participants randomly would have questioned the reliability and validity of this research because not everyone in the population has the right knowledge of risk management. Therefore, as already discussed above, it was vital to carefully select participants that have the right knowledge of risk or are risk experts as this would not only guarantee the credibility of this research but also ensures uniformity and help to eliminate any error of coverage (Dillman et.al., 2014).

Non-response and measurement errors: Non-response or poor response of questionnaires from respondents affects the validity of research and as such it would be difficult to make needful generalisations (Check and Schutt, 2012). Avedian (2014) highlights that ‘missing information or data, inability to reach respondents or decline to participate’ as some reasons for non-response error and implied that any research sample with more than 20% non-response feedback would raise concerns. While measurement error refers to a situation whereby questions fail to reflect or falls short of the research interest or more still, instruments employed in gathering data fail to evoke truthful answers (Singleton and Straits, 2009; Check and Schutt, 2012; Dillman et.al, 2014). To this regard therefore, the following steps were taken to maximise participants response for this study.

Before starting this research, the researcher had already obtained an ethical approval from the relevant authority which is a mandatory requirement in academic research. After which the researcher initially contacted all respondents through emails and phone calls via their contact details which was obtained from various institution’s websites to obtain their buy-in and informed them on the benefits and contributions of the study to their institutions. More so, the researcher assured respondents anonymity and guaranteed that their feedback would be treated with utmost confidence (Bryman and Bell, 2007). Additionally, a carefully designed ‘cover letter’ was included which was personalised to every respondent, highlighting the relevance of the study and ethical obligations such as: guaranteeing confidentiality and anonymity of respondents and voluntary involvement (Saunders et.al, 2012). Contact details of the researcher and the Director of Studies (DoS) were also included to enhance trustworthiness and enable respondents get-in-touch if need be.

Despite employing electronic based questionnaire – ‘QuestionPro’ which have been proven to enhance survey response rate (Saunders et.al., 2012), necessary steps were taken to ensure excellent graphics and visual appeal by using suitable font size. Additionally, the researcher ensured that questions were carefully worded, clear and concise, and themes were logically ordered in order to minimise unintentional response bias. To achieve this, the researcher reviewed with DoS every item in the questionnaire to iron out grey areas before administering to respondents. Furthermore, the researcher designed a framework (see figure 3.3 below) that linked the research aim and objectives to the literature review and research questions which served as a guide in designing the questionnaire thereby not only ensuring that only relevant questions were included in the questionnaire, but also ensured the linkage of the research problem, research objective, literature review and methodology thereby minimising or eliminating any perceived error of measurement. Finally, the researcher monitored responses and followed-up on participants who were yet to respond to ensure minimal non-response error.

Conclusively, the overarching purpose of the survey design was to evaluate the structures and practices of risk management within the HEI context (questionnaire items 1-5; vital for objective 1 above;), and also help inform and complement the qualitative phase of this study. Therefore, the questionnaire was systematically structured to collect data to measure the institutions’ attitude towards risk management (questionnaire item 8; relevant for objective 2), and also, policies and strategies of risk management by the institutions (questionnaire item 6,7, 9-18; appropriate for objectives 2 and 3). Additionally, the survey was vital in gathering data regarding HEIs and the structure of their RM programs, staff saddled with such responsibility (e.g., risk management oversight responsibility, the necessary tools used in the risk management process and the level, degree or depth of implementation). Additionally, the survey instrument was carefully designed making use of features of various risk maturity models, principles and frameworks for managing risk to ask questions and elicit information on the risk management practices in the various institutions.

3.6 PHASE 2

As discussed earlier in the methodology section above, the importance of the sequential mixed-methods approach is that data from the initial phase of the study informs and builds on the latter phase (Creswell, 2009), it is helps identify participants for interviews and increases validity of the study as it helps to corroborate and augment results and findings from both the

quantitative and qualitative strands of the research (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). To ensure the aim and objectives (section 3.1) of this research is achieved with valid results, it was essential that only institutions with fully institutionalised and embedded risk management framework would be studied. Thus, having reviewed the information gathered from the quantitative strand of this research, fortunately, all sixteen institutions that were surveyed met this criterion. Interviews were to be conducted with the risk managers across these sixteen institutions, but some challenges occurred as at the time of conducting interviews as some initial identified respondents had either changed jobs (Epsilon, Rho, and Iota Universities) or were on vacation (Eta, Tau and Lambda Universities) and respondents from Omicron University and Upsilon University were not interested in taking part in the interview phase.

The researcher did not have luxury of time to wait for respondents who either went on annual leave or those that took up new positions – as they needed plenty of time to settle into their new roles. Thus, interviews were conducted with respondents from 7 institutions namely: Alpha, Gamma, Beta, Delta, Zetta, Theta and Kappa Universities. However, several attempts (emails and phone calls) to get feedback from respondent of Kappa University to clarify issues proved abortive as this also coincided with the lockdown. Therefore, it was in the best interest not to include data from Kappa University. Despite the challenges of not being able to include all proposed Universities in this phase of the study, these 6 universities selected as case studies for this strand of the study ticked all the boxes (in terms of geographical, structural and period established) relevant to the reliability, validity and success of this research as shown in table 5.1 in chapter 4 of this study. However, to ensure greater reliability and validity of this study, the researcher as discussed below, decided to include document analysis to this phase of the research.

Interviews were conducted with key risk experts in the various case Universities and documents were reviewed across these Universities. This interview data along with documents from case institutions sourced throughout the course of this research were carefully analysed using the reflexive thematic analysis method. Key contacts from various case institutions provided the researcher with further documents electronically and feedbacks and follow-ups were carried out where and when necessary via emails and phone calls. Section 3.6.1 and 3.6.2 below discusses the justification of case study for this research as well as data collection techniques that were employed in this phase of the study.

3.6.1 Case Study

As already highlighted in the preceding section, 7 Universities were selected as case studies for this strand of the research. However, unfortunately, data from Kappa was not included in the final analysis due to factors already discussed above. Harrison et.al., (2017) highlights that selecting cases for a case study research is either based on the purpose or condition of the study. Thus, the purpose and condition for the selection of cases for this research was based on the research aim, objectives and questions. As already discussed above, the purpose of this study meant that only Universities with fully embedded risk management framework would be selected for this study. Although, all the institutions had met this criterion, however, the prevailing condition (due to some factors beyond control – discussed in section 3.5 above) resulted in the selection of these institutions.

Robert Yin a leading and well-known guru in case study research refers to case study as: “*an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident*” (Yin 2003, p.13). Case study is the most suitable design in situations where behavioural events are not required (Patton, 2002; Yin, 2009) and Creswell (2007) adds that it enables the researcher to either investigate a case or several cases – bounded system(s) through a thorough, in-depth data collection which involves various mechanisms of information (such as: interviews, observations, audio-visual materials and documents and reports). It usually involves a thorough or an in-depth investigation to an inquiry as regards an “individual, a group of people, an organisation or a specific sector (Morris and Wood, 1991; Stake, 1995; Fisher, 2004; Wilson, 2014). Benbasat et.al, (1987, p.370) gives insights on problems where case study is usually suitable:

- “*It is necessary to the phenomena in its natural setting*”
- “*The researcher can ask how and why questions so as to understand the nature and complexity of the processes taking place*”
- “*Research is being conducted in an area where few, if any, previous studies have been undertaken*”.

Source: (Benbasat et.al., 1987: p.370)

Therefore, based on these evidences, case study design was adopted for the qualitative strand of this study because this study did not require any behavioural research but rather the aim of this research is to ‘*conceptualise the impact of Risk Management on the structures, practices*

and processes in Scottish Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) and to understand its adoption, integration, development, and changes in relation to its implementation’. More so, it presented the researcher the opportunity of a range of suitable information gathering mechanisms (i.e., interviews and document analysis) in order to conduct an in-depth investigation on the subject matter. Finally, risk management in UK Universities is an area where no or limited research has been carried out which also makes it most suitable for case study (Benbasat et.al., 1987). Thus, adopting case study for this phase of the study enabled the researcher to successfully investigate and build on results from the quantitative strand of this research. Thus, it has previously been highlighted that interviews and documents analysis were the tools used to gather information in the phase 2 of this study, therefore, the next section presents in detail the data collection mechanisms for this second phase of the research.

3.6.2 Data Collection Mechanisms

This section of the study focuses on the techniques used in gathering relevant information for the phase 2 of this study. According to Dadhe (2016), this is one of the most fundamental or important aspect of any research because, though studies can vary in several ways and even different in-terms of methodology, but every research is based on data. Therefore, the validity and reliability of any research is subject to the quality of data used and the mode through which such data were collected (Wilson, 2014). The data collection mechanisms employed for this research i.e., ‘Questionnaire’ (Survey) – already discussed above, ‘Interviews’ (Case study) and ‘Documents analysis’ (Case study) were the most suitable and appropriate considering the research design and the purpose of the study. Therefore, discussed below in detail are ‘Interviews and Document analysis’ as it relates to this phase 2 of the study.

3.6.2.1 Interviews

As mentioned above, employing a suitable data collection technique is a major factor to a successful completion of case study research. Case study research enjoys the benefit of several data gathering techniques and Yin (2003) highlights some of these as:

- *“Direct observation of activities and phenomena and their environment,*
- *Indirect observation or measurement of process related phenomena,*
- *Interviews – structured or unstructured,*
- *Documentation such as written, printed or electronic information about the company and its operations; also, newspaper cuttings,*

- *Records and charts about previous use of technology relevant to the case”.*

Source: (Yin, 2003: p.78).

From the above listed methods, the interview technique was best suited for this qualitative phase of this study because considering the purpose of this research (section 3.1) ‘Interviews as compared to other techniques, provides greater flexibility to ask questions and probe further for greater clarity and insights (especially when the purpose is to build and clarify areas of concern from same respondents through their responses from the phase 1 of the study) whilst being able to identify both verbal and nonverbal responses from interviewees and additionally, responses are instant, straightforward and are often taped thereby guaranteeing accurate information (Singleton and Straits, 2009; Wilson, 2014).

Therefore, semi-structured interview was employed to elicit relevant information from respondents involved directly in the design, process, operations and management of the RM framework. Thus, based on the research objectives, interview questions were carefully structured to capture information regarding the adoption, integration and implementation of the RM framework and also the clarify certain areas of concern from the initial quantitative phase of the study. The choice of semi-structured interview is the flexibility it provides to further probe on issues that need clarifications from respondents without straying away from the scope or initial design of the inquiry. Besides, it also allows interviewees the freedom to air their views in their own construct while also providing the benefit to compare data from other respondent thereby ensuring validity and reliability of results (Saunders et.al., 2007; Wilson, 2014).

Sampling Technique

This strand of the study as previously mentioned sought to build on the initial data collected in the quantitative phase of this research. As discussed earlier, from review of the quantitative data, all 16 institutions earlier surveyed met the criterion for a follow-up interview, however, only 7 interviewees were available as at the time interviews were conducted (see sections 3.5 and 3.6.1 above and Appendix 3.4 for events timeline of this research). Thus, these interviewees are risk experts earlier selected through ‘purposive expert sampling’ and were interviewed as follow-up on the first phase of the research.

However, the researcher is aware of pitfalls as regards the interview method such as: difficulty in scheduling appointments with interviewees; questions that may draw the ire of interviewees because such questions may be perceived to be provoking or embarrassing; respondents not willing to be part or answer questions; amount of time taken to transcribe and analyse data etc. (Wilson, 2014; Creswell, 2009; Saunders et.al., 2009; Bryman and Bell, 2007). Therefore, the following steps were taken to guard against any perceived shortfall that may come to the fore.

As mentioned earlier in section 3.4.1, purposive sampling was adopted which allowed the researcher to identify specific individuals selected for interviews. Based on the informed analysis from the first phase of this study, it was easy for the researcher to identify and follow-up on specific individuals for interview. The researcher contacted them immediately through emails and phone calls and thus it was easy and quick to get positive feedback on their willingness to participate in the research. Although some respondents opted not to participate in the interview phase of this research, however, the researcher was still able to conduct a very good number of interviews that is required for a valid and credible results and findings because the respondents were strategically drawn from institutions representing all indices such as geographical location, structure, date established etc. (section 3.6).

Furthermore, document analysis (discussed below) was included to this study in order to enhance validity and credibility. As with every semi-structured interview, questions for the interview were carefully designed and with the help of the framework (linking the research problem and objectives to literature, see figure 3.3 below) developed by the researcher, it was not difficult ensuring that only appropriate questions had been included. Furthermore, these interview questions were discussed with my DoS and together we analysed every item to ensure all questions were relevant and well-structured to meet its purpose (Check and Schutt, 2012).

Before the start of the interviews, the researcher would explain the importance of the study to the interviewees and the reason for soliciting their assistance for the interview and highlighted the benefits of the study when concluded to Scottish HEIs and with potential benefits to the entire UK HEIs (Wilson, 2014). Interviewees were guaranteed and assured utmost confidentiality and anonymity (Check and Schutt, 2012) as regards their feedback and were given the flexibility and option to decline answer to any question they may not be comfortable with (Bryman and Bell, 2007). Respondents were also provided with transcript of the interview

for their cross-reference to ensure no omission or commission was accidentally made during transcription. Doing this not only ensured genuineness but adds to the validity and reliability of the study (Saunders et.al, 2009; Bryman and Bell, 2007). Furthermore, with the consent of the respondents, interviews were taped and all equipment regarding this were securely kept under lock and key with only the researcher having access. This further guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents (Wilson, 2014) and showed that the researcher is fully aware of the code of conduct and ethical practices in research.

Figure 3.3: Framework linking Research Topic, Aims and Objectives to Literature and Questionnaires.

Source: (Author) – Framework designed for ensuring Research aims and objectives align with Literature Review, Survey and Interview questions.

3.6.2.2 Documents analysis

As earlier stated in chapter 1 and section 3.6 of this study, although the initial plan for the phase 2 of this study was only to source data through interviews, however, having concluded and analysed data from the first phase of this research, the researcher encountered some challenges as not every proposed interviewee (risk experts from institutions with fully embedded risk management framework) was available for interviews. Although despite the challenges encountered of not being able to include all proposed Universities in this phase of the study, these 6 selected institutions as case studies for this strand of the study ticked all the boxes (in terms of geographical, structural and period of establishment) relevant to the reliability, validity and success of this research as observed in chapter 5, table 5.1. However, for greater reliability and validity of this study, the researcher decided to include document analysis to this phase of the research. Thus, the review of documents provided a genuine and a very rich source of information to the research objectives and also important for interview data triangulation (Bowen, 2009).

As already stated above, document analysis is another useful case study mechanism for information gathering (Yin'2003; Creswell, 2007). Documents, manuscripts or "texts" provides one of the key sources of qualitative data. "*Often the first and easiest data to collect for an implementation study is contained in existing documents*" (Wener, 2004; p. 28). All of the documents reviewed for the purpose of this study were official and publicly available documents which were mainly frameworks and manuals, risk management reports, risk management policy guidance documents etc., of case institutions.

Several Universities have this information publicly available on their websites. Thus, the researcher was able to gain free access to these documents as well as requested additional ones where needed during and after conducting interviews. Information obtained from these documents were analysed thematically alongside interview data as discussed above in section 3.6.2. Documents used in this study were only sourced from participating case institutions because these documents presented the basis for corroborating the information obtained through interview from participants and where there were variations, participants were duly contacted through phone calls and /or emails for clarifications.

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS

As previously discussed above in section 3.4.1 the sequential mixed methods used in this study meant that data was collected and analysed in phases (see figures 3.2 and 3.4). Thus, analysis of both the quantitative and the qualitative data from this research were carried out separately and in phases as discussed below.

3.7.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

As discussed above in section 3.5, the quantitative phase of this research was essential to providing details on participant selection, to corroborate, validate and ensure results and findings are credible and valid. This means that apart from providing details regarding the selection of participants in the study, results from the quantitative phase were also used to corroborate, augment and validate findings from the qualitative phase. Therefore, survey results were statistically analysed through descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics is a perfect way to quantitatively describe or summarise important features in a study or a given data set (Mann, 2010; Trochim, 2006). Results were presented in tables and were analysed mainly using percentages. This provided the basis for comparison, corroborating and validating findings from the qualitative analysis.

However, analysis of results was organised and presented under three key themes: *'Policies and Procedures of Risk Management, Attitudes and Approach towards Institutional Risk Management, and Strategies to Manage Risk'*. These key themes are a summary of themes that were developed from the thematic analysis of the study and were retrospectively applied to discussions and recommendations regarding the quantitative analysis to allow for a uniform measure of analysis, discussions and integration of results and findings from both phases of the study. The rationale for these key themes is discussed in section 3.7.2 below.

3.7.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

Data from the qualitative strand (i.e., interview data and documents) of this study was analysed thematically. Thematic analysis (TA) happens to be one of the most common approaches in qualitative research analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Guest et.al, 2012). Its strong point is its flexibility with emphasis on identification, analysis, and interpretation of themes (or occurring patterns) within a context (Guest et.al, 2012). Unlike several other approaches for qualitative data analysis (i.e., Discourse analysis, Narrative analysis, Grounded theory, Interpretative

Phenomenological analysis, etc.) – that are often termed as methodologies or hypothetically informed frameworks for research because of their redlines or guiding principles as it relates to type of research questions, mode of data collection and even guidelines for conducting analysis, TA in contrast is often regarded as a technique or method mainly because of its flexibility (Braun and Clarke, 2019).

The researcher adopted TA for this study against other well-known approaches because it is best suited to the purpose and objectives of this research. For instance, Narrative analysis builds its strength on storytelling and retelling and is perfect for studies recounting experiences, assessing history of persons or events (Greenhalgh et.al, 2005), while Grounded theory although similar to TA (Braun and Clarke, 2006), but its major focus or aim is at developing a novel theory (Charmaz, 2006) whereas, TA enables a researcher to develop a narrative or provide an explanation that can accurately and critically describe and evaluate a phenomena. Furthermore, because this study apart from being a mixed-method research, information were also collated from other sources such as public domain documents thus, TA is well suited for such because of its flexibility, and its ability to synthesise data from different sources with a high validity of results (Aronson 1994; Ryan and Bernard 2000; Braun and Clarke 2006).

There are different approaches of TA such as: the code book approaches which includes – framework analysis (Gale and Heath, 2003), template analysis (King and Brooks, 2016), reflexive analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006), etc. This study adopted the Reflexive TA by Braun and Clarke (2006) not because of its popularity - as it ranked among the most cited academic papers published in 2006 with over 68,000 citations on Google Scholar, but because it allows for a coding flexibility (Braun and Clarke, 2006) which is important for the purpose of this study rather than the use of a ‘multiple independent coders’ and ‘structured book’ (Boyatzis, 1998; Joffe, 2011 and Guest et.al., 2012). Owing to the uniqueness and because Risk management is quite a new phenomenon in the academic landscape, it is quite essential that some degree of coding flexibility is applied to the qualitative data analysis to ensure that no key information is overlooked (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Thus, documents obtained from the various case institutions were thematically coded alongside interview data from participants. Data from these documents provided a good measure to corroborate transcribed interview responses, thus it was best to analyse both together. Themes

were developed from the coded interview data and other relevant documents obtained for the study. Thus, 22 themes were defined and discussed as findings in chapter 5 and also formed the basis of discussion and recommendations in chapter 6 of this study. These themes were grouped as it relates to each objective and research question of the study and this is clearly presented in chapter 5 and further classified into three overarching themes thus: '*Policies and Procedures of Risk Management, Attitudes and Approach towards Institutional Risk Management, and Strategies to Manage Risk*'. These overarching themes apart from presenting a uniform measure of analysis, discussions and integration of results and findings from both phases of the study, it also simplified the results, findings and recommendations of the study to each specific objective of this study.

Like every other analytical approach in qualitative research, TA also come with its seemingly concerns and has been criticised by some literature to lack clear explanation and conceptualisation, also some opponents of TA argue that its flexibility may prove daunting for greenhorn researchers who may find it confusing deciding what areas to focus on in their data context. Furthermore, they argued that because of TA's focus on 'themes identification' across data set, it may prove difficult to uphold or sustain sense of data continuity (Boyatzis 1998; Suddaby 2006; Braun and Clarke, 2006; Guest et.al, 2012). Therefore, adequate measures were taken to guard against these pitfalls by diligently following the six important phases to TA as highlighted by Braun and Clarke (2006) in comprehensively carrying out TA as: '*familiarisation, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and writing up*' (pp. 16-23).

At the start of this research, the researcher had a very limited knowledge of TA. However, to enhance the credibility and validity of this study, workshops were attended, and the researcher also engaged in self-learning through texts, journals, articles and learning videos. This presented the requisite knowledge and confidence to successfully carryout the data analysis for this research. It will be important to note that the researcher initially carried out this process manually (though time consuming but provided more understanding and comprehension of the data) and then used Nvivo which assisted greatly to organise and structure the research data in line with the relevant codes. Thus, using both manual and Nvivo provided additional confidence of data validity and reliability (Basit, 2003; Saldaña, 2013).

The data transcription phase of this study although challenging was a key part in familiarising more with the data. And as earlier stated in section 3.5.2 above, after confirming reliability with respondents of the transcribed data, the researcher invested enormous time by actively, analytically and comprehensively reading and re-reading (familiarisation) both the interview data and the relevant documents, and highlighting key items of importance; thus, the researcher was able to generate codes through the observation of how and where patterns occurred in the data.

3.8 INTEGRATION OF RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The combination of both quantitative and qualitative data can vividly enhance validity in a mixed methods study (Bryman 2006; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). There are numerous benefits to be gained from combining methods in a research (see section 3.4.1), however, researchers often encounter challenges because of the limited procedures of data integration in a mixed methods study (Bryman 2006; Lewin et.al., 2009). There are specific procedures of integrating, merging or combining results or data from both quantitative and qualitative phases in mixed methods study which could be implemented at any stage or all of the stages of the research either at the design stage, methods and/or interpretation and reporting phase (O’Cathain et.al., 2010; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Thus, integration in this research occurred in all three stages as discussed (see figure 4.4) below.

3.8.1 Design Stage

Integration at this stage can occur through the known basic designs – i.e., explanatory sequential, exploratory sequential and convergent designs (Fetters, et.al., 2013; Creswell, 2015). Usually, the quantitative and qualitative results in a convergent design are compared against each other whereas, one phase builds on the other in a sequential design (Ivankova, et.al., 2006; Fetters, et.al., 2013). Therefore, this study is an explanatory sequential design because it began with collecting data quantitatively and the analysis thereof was vital in informing and building on the qualitative phase of the study (see discussions in sections 3.4.1 and 3.6).

3.8.2 Methods Stage

Several literatures discuss that integration also occur through a connection between data collection methods and analysis (Creswell, et.al., 2011; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011;

Fetters, et.al., 2013; Moseholm and Fetters, 2017). Fetters, et.al., (2013) summarises that these linking approaches consist of ‘connecting, building, merging and embedding’ (see figure 3.4 below) and more so according to them, integration within this stage may occur through one or more of these listed approaches whereas, there is always a relationship between the type of design used in the study and the method of integration; for instance, ‘connecting’ is naturally used with sequential designs while embedding although could be used with other designs but it often is used in interventional designs though merging could be suitable with any design.

Therefore, this study is integrated through connecting because, as discussed earlier in sections 3.5 and 3.7.1 and also shown in figure 3.4 below, because data and the subsequent analysis of it from the quantitative strand of this research was vital in participant selection and case institutions for the qualitative phase of the study. For instance, participants for interviews were drawn from the initial participants earlier surveyed in the quantitative phase of the study. More so, apart from connecting, integration also occurred through ‘building’ because there were instances where during the interview, participants were asked to clarify on issues that were previously answered through quantitative questionnaires, but the researcher needed more clarifications (sections 3.2, 3.4 and 3.6).

Finally, results from analysis of both phases (quantitative and qualitative) were merged through some unique categories or overarching themes namely: *‘Policies and Procedures of Risk Management, Attitudes and Approach towards Institutional Risk Management, and Strategies to Manage Risk’* (see section 3.7). As previously discussed, these categories emanated from the categorisation of themes from thematic analysis of the qualitative data and these categories or *‘unique corresponding identifiers’* were applied retrospectively to the quantitative data set (as presented in chapter 4). Thus, this approach allowed for a successful merger of the quantitative and the qualitative database.

3.8.3 Interpretation and Reporting Stage

Integrating quantitative and qualitative mixed methods research data at the interpretation and reporting stage can occur in three approaches: narrative, data transformation and joint displays (Stange, et.al., 2006; Creswell and Tashakkori, 2007) or a combination of all these approaches (Fetters, et.al., 2013). Furthermore, integration through the narrative approach entails the researcher discussing both the quantitative and the qualitative either in a single or several

reports and this could be effectively done either through one or a combination of these approaches: ‘*weaving, contiguous, and staged*’ approaches (Fetters, et.al., 2013).

Thus, at the interpretation and reporting level of this study, the quantitative and qualitative data was reported through the *weaving* and *contiguous* approaches. As already discussed above, merging both the qualitative and quantitative data through unique corresponding identifiers or categories allowed for integration and reporting of both quantitative and qualitative data through unique themes (*weaving*) whereas analysis and findings from both quantitative and qualitative findings had previously been presented separately (*contiguous*) in chapters 4 and 5 of this research (Fetters, et.al., 2013). These different stages and approaches as discussed above provided the perfect mechanism which ensured the researcher was able to effectively and successfully integrate and mix both the quantitative and qualitative research designs at the necessary and required stages of the study for a valid and credible research. Figure 3.4 below presents how these stages and approaches occurred in the study.

Figure 3.4: Integration of (sequential mixed methods) quantitative and qualitative results/findings.

Source: Driscoll, et.al., (2007) – Own editing.

3.9 ETHICS

Before commencing this study, ethical approval was sought as stipulated under the awarding institution's (University of the West of Scotland – UWS) ethical policy guidelines, detailing and describing the research methods used in this study and this was duly approved (see Appendix 3.3 for approval copy) by the University committee on Ethics. However, although 'Document Analysis' was not part of the initial plan for this study, but as already discussed above, the documents used in this research were all publicly available on the websites of the various institutions thus because they are not linked to any individual, it would therefore not be of detriment or cause harm to any individual or organisation.

Researchers usually encounter challenges as regards complexities in ethical considerations when conducting research (King and Horrocks, 2010). Principles and guidelines on ethics have lately become inseparable from business and scientific research, thus it is essential that researchers are mindful of the ethical considerations as it relate to their studies and it is important that researchers should conduct themselves with integrity and hold the highest level of trust from participants (Resnick, 2015). Therefore, in conducting this study, the researcher adhered strictly to the principles and guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland – ethics committee guidelines i.e., “*Non-maleficence, Autonomy, Justice and Inclusiveness, Confidentiality, Anonymity, Honesty, Rigour, Transparency and Respect and care*” (UWS, 2016, p.1).

In addition to the ethical approval for this study, the researcher took further necessary steps in order to comply with the UWS's principles and guidelines on ethics. Therefore, participants of this study were guaranteed total commitment of confidentiality and anonymity. Table 5.1 in chapter 5 of this study highlights codes attributed to case universities and respondents as fulfilment of this commitment. Participants were also obliged the opportunity to decide against answering any question they were not comfortable with or to withdraw from the study should they change their mind during the surveys or interview.

A covering letter was attached to the survey to emphasise these points while the researcher reemphasised these points before the start of interviews with interviewees. Respondents were also provided with transcripts from their interview for their cross-reference to ensure no omission or commission was accidentally made during transcription. This was done to ensure

genuineness, validity and reliability of the study (Saunders et.al, 2009; Bryman and Bell, 2007). Furthermore, as agreed with respondents, results were aggregated, and reference to direct quotes from respondents as presented in this study were anonymised in order to further guarantee participant's anonymity and confidentiality. More so, with the consent of the respondents, interviews were taped and all equipment regarding this were securely kept under lock and key with only the researcher having access.

3.10 DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Limitations of the study have been broadly discussed in chapter 6 of this research. However, it is also important to set out in this chapter the study's delimitations – i.e., the parameters and boundaries guiding the research as set out by the researcher (Theofanidis and Fountouki, 2019). As earlier discussed in chapter 1 and also presented in section 3.5.1 of this chapter, the scope and parameters of this study is only restricted to HEIs in Scotland. Why the study had not been conducted across the UK universities was as a result of the separate legislation that governs Scottish institutions and other UK HEIs because doing this would have raised concerns regarding the validity and generalisability of the study. As such, the scope and spectrum of this research (Marrelli, 2007; Baxter and Jack, 2008) entails the careful selection of some institutions as case reference based on their risk management profile, (informed judgement from quantitative strand of the study), status, rating, location etc.

Additionally, purposive expert sampling (section 3.0 and 3.5.1) was employed to select participants for the interview. Other sampling techniques were not suitable because considering the research problem, it was vital to only source information from institutions with well institutionalised framework and furthermore dedicated risk managers (risk experts) with adequate knowledge of the risk management process and practices as well as the decision-making process within the institution. Thus, the purposive expert sampling was the perfect technique to actualise the aim for valid and credible findings.

3.11 CONCLUSION

This chapter informed by the prevailing business research methods, evaluates the justification of every research method used in this study as it relates to the mixed method approach, sampling techniques, document analysis, data collection techniques and data analysis etc., while also outlining the ethical considerations and making needed clarifications to

delimitations of the study in order to establish validity, credibility and trustworthiness. Thus, chapters 4 and 5 is a presentation of analysis results from the qualitative strand as well as findings from the qualitative phase as it relates to the application of this methodology chapter while chapter 6 discusses these findings and results and recommendations.

4.0 PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND ANALYSIS FROM THE QUANTITATIVE STUDY

INTRODUCTION

This chapter is a presentation of results and analysis from the quantitative strand of this research. As previously discussed in chapters 3, this study being a ‘sequential mixed-methods design’ (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003), was carried out in phases. Phase 1 of the study (quantitative) was vital in mainly evaluating the structures and practices of risk management within the HEI context (see both research objective 1 and research question 1), selecting case universities and participants for the qualitative phase and also informing and building on objectives 2 and 3 as well as essential for the construct of the semi-structured interviews. Thus, this approach enhanced validity, credibility and further assisted in data triangulation.

As discussed previously in chapter 3.7 and 3.8, the objectives of this study were founded and organised under the following overarching themes: ‘Policies and Procedures of Risk Management’, ‘Attitudes and Approaches Towards Institutional Risk Management’ and ‘Strategies to Manage Institutional Risk’ – thus, analysis from this phase of the study have been presented and classified using these key themes. These key themes apart from ensuring uniformity and ease of mixing of results and findings from both the quantitative and qualitative strands of this study, it has also enabled the researcher to structure, analyse and present results coherently as it relates to the research objectives/questions. Therefore, presented under each of these themes are graphical representations of responses from respondents from related questions in the survey questionnaire and a synopsis at the end of each theme that analyses and discusses the information from the graphs. These analysis and discussions not only present the key jumping off points, but also corroborates and builds the qualitative strand of this research.

4.1 RESULT FROM THE QUANTITATIVE SURVEY

Cross-sectional electronic survey was employed for the quantitative strand of this research and sixteen risk professionals from across sixteen Universities in Scotland completed the survey of 90 questionnaires that were administered (chapter 3.5.1) The low response rate was because questions were only designed for risk experts and it was initially difficult to identify the intended respondents (risk managers) of various institutions. Despite several efforts made to extract this information through the institutions’ websites, unfortunately, some of the listed

contacts were either not the right contacts – due to change of jobs or positions or some have retired or left the institution. Therefore, it was necessary to administer such a good number of questionnaires to anyone/everyone listed as risk manager while follow-ups were made through phone calls, emails and networking. Fortunately, at least one feedback was received for every institution. Thus, results from this phase was analysed using descriptive statics and presented hereunder in tables (see chapter 3.7.1).

4.1.1 Characteristics of Respondents

Respondents for the quantitative phase of the study as earlier discussed in chapter 3.5.1 are risk experts or high-ranking risk executives who are involved in the risk management policies and decision making and/or in the day-to-day risk management activities and coordination in their various institutions. Although there was no uniformity in their designated titles, respondents had titles such as: Risk and Insurance Manager, Head of Assurance, Risk and Resilience Manager, Director of Operations and Finance, Head of Planning, etc. Only institutions that met the criteria as already discussed in methodology chapter of this research were selected as Case Universities and although risk experts each from 7 case Universities had been interviewed as a follow up from the quantitative phase of the study, however, only result from 6 institutions were analysed and presented in chapter 5 of this research. This is because respondent from one of the universities interviewed was no longer available for feedbacks (please see chapter 3.6 for more).

4.2 POLICIES AND PROCEDURES OF RISK MANAGEMENT

Questions 1-5 of the questionnaire were carefully designed to elicit responses from respondents regarding the risk management model adopted by their institutions, its composition and implementation which is in accordance with institutional regulators advising that institution should put in place a risk management framework to allow for a rigorous and comprehensive risk management process. All of the respondents (100%) answered to the affirmative that they have put in place a risk management framework as proposed by the regulatory authorities.

Q1. In line with regulatory bodies (such as: Higher Education Funding Council for England – HEFCE and Scottish Funding Council – SFC) guidelines on internal control for a robust risk management framework, would you say your institution has a risk management program of framework in place?

Table 3.1: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 1.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Yes – Fully Adopted	16	100
Yes – But has not been incorporated	0	0
No – But Plans are underway (please go to question 4).	0	0
No – Have not given it a thought (please go to question 4).	0	0
Total	16	100

Q2. If yes to question 1 above, how would you describe your risk management framework?

Table 4.2: Statistical Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 2.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)	4	25
Strategic Risk Management (SRM)	6	37.50
Integrated Risk Management (IRM)	2	12.50
Other, Please State	4	25
Total	16	100

As a follow-up question, respondents were asked how they would describe their risk management framework and from the options provided, 25% of respondents opted for Enterprise Risk Management (ERM), 37.5% said Strategic Risk Management (SRM), 12.5% said they referred to their framework as Integrated Risk Management (IRM) while the remaining 25% however provided details such as: “Risk management”, “a “cross-section between ERM and SRM” and “IAA (International Actuarial Association) risk defined.

Q3. Which of the following risk management framework has been adopted by your institution?

Table 5.3: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 3.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
COSO ERM framework	1	6.67
ISO 31000 framework	6	40
Bespoke	8	53.33
Other please specify	0	0
Total	15	100

Furthermore, respondents were asked which institutional risk management framework they have adopted or modelled their risk management framework towards, 6.67% said “The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission” (COSO), 40% answered ISO 31000 “(International Organization for Standardization)”, while 53.33% said they use bespoke. However, there was one respondent that skipped this question.

Q4. What would you consider the major driver for adopting a risk management framework in your institution (please select all applicable)?

Table 6.4: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 4.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Response to regulatory requirement	11	68.75
Response to internal regulatory, legal or compliance failure	3	18.75
To improve decision-making	14	87.50
As a part of strategic planning	14	87.50
Enterprise-wide assessment of major risks	11	68.75
Board mandate	7	43.75
Chancellor/President mandate	0	0.00
Economic climate	2	12.50
ERM awareness from conferences, journals, readings, colleagues	2	12.50
Other please state	2	12.50
Total	16*	

*Multiple responses were allowed.

On what respondents considered the major driver for adopting a risk management framework in their institution (question 4), multiple answers were allowed and of the total response count, 68.75% said “response to regulatory requirement”, 18.75% of respondents said it was as a response to internal regulatory, legal or compliance failure, 87.50% said it was a measure to improve decision making, another 87.50% said it is imperative for strategic planning, 68.75% said to allow for an enterprise-wide assessment of major risks, 43.75% said it was a mandate from the Board, 12.50% said due to economic climate and another 12.50% said it was an outcome from risk management awareness from conferences, journals, colleagues etc., while

a further 12.50% who chose “other” highlighted that it was recommended by Audit and Risk committee.

Q5. What action steps did your institution take when it adopted a risk management framework (select all that apply)?

Table 7.5: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 5.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Consulted with colleagues at other institutions	13	81.25
Literature review	11	68.75
Attended conference sessions	5	31.25
Engaged the services of consultants	8	50
Other please state	2	12.25
Total	16*	

*Multiple responses were allowed.

Respondents were then asked in question 5 about the action steps taken during the implementation of their framework; multiple responses were allowed and of the total response count, 81.25% said they consulted with colleagues from other institutions, 68.75% said they reviewed literature, 31.25% said they attended conferences, and a further 50% said they engaged the services of consultants while 12.5% chose “other” and stated that “the knowledge of staff coming from private sector” and the “creation of risk and resilience department were extremely useful”.

4.2.1 Synopsis

The aim of this section was to aid understanding the risk management model, composition and implementation of HEIs. Thus, the researcher has been able to unravel the major factors influencing Universities’ RM framework implementation as well as approaches, procedures and policies adopted. Therefore, the following analysis from findings of the quantitative survey is a consideration of an interplay of factors affecting the design choices of HEIs RM systems as per their policies, procedures and composition which influences decisions and implementation of RM.

4.2.1.1 Institutional Factors

Complying with institutional norms is said to produce legitimacy (Castel and Fredberg, 2004) which findings from this section is seen as the major initiative for institutionalising RM.

Findings from this section is juxtaposed with the various institutional demands enforced on HEIs by their regulatory bodies and corresponding environmental, social and cultural pressures (see chapter 2). DiMaggio and Powell (1983) opine that under (neo) institutional concept, the environment is perceived as a location of institutional rules exerting major influence over organisational practices and structures. They observed how institutions operating within their institutional setting become isomorphic with their organisational environment. This explains how and why actors within organisations are often influenced to act in accordance with institutional dynamics (Scott, 2010). Thus, the following analysis reflects on coercive, mimetic, normative, institutional and other external pressures as indicated by respondents from the quantitative survey.

Coercive pressures

Responses from respondents of this survey suggests the presence of some major types of coercive pressures influencing the framework design of HEIs RM policies and procedures. Some of these pressures stem from regulatory requirements and enhancement of strategic decision making.

Prevailing Regulatory Requirements and Strategic Decision Making

Evident in the survey responses of this study is the impact of regulatory requirements for risk management on HEIs which is part of the major reason that has influenced the adoption of RM by HEIs as observed in Table 4.4 above. Other major drivers as shown above could be termed as strategic planning and decision making. As detailed in chapter 2.10 of this study regarding the Single Outcome Agreement, it is understandable that strategic planning and decision making coupled with regulatory requirements are amongst the key drivers of the adoption and institutionalisation of RM in HEIs because embedding RM within the institution ensures that regulators are better able to get a grips on the activities of HEIs likewise ensuring compliance that HEIs are able to align their objectives with that of the Government through SFC within the Outcome Agreements.

Mimetic pressures and implementation of RM framework

Although some Universities in this sample claimed to have a bespoke RM framework, however, results from findings presented above (Table 4.5) demonstrates that majority of the institutions agreed to consulting with other institutions as key steps taken towards the adoption

of their RM framework. While there is absolutely nothing wrong with this approach, but such could have influenced their RM framework's design, policies and practices. Additionally, half of the respondents reported engaging the services of consultants towards the development of their RM framework. While again this is a welcome idea, however, there should be due diligence while doing so because RM being a new phenomenon in academia, there is every likelihood that third-party consultants coming from the private sector may likely implement frameworks that may not exactly align with the University environment.

Normative pressures

The survey findings also indicate major influence on the choice of RM framework, policies and practices by HEIs emanating from professionalisation of the risk management sector. These professional bodies relevant to the HEIs under study were evidenced to be significantly related to the growing popularity of normative control within the risk management sector heralded by organisations like ISO and COSO. These two organisations were reported by the respondents as providing the foundation of the RM framework. Even those that have initially reported to have a bespoke model, further investigation by the researcher revealed modelling their frameworks on either COSO or ISO.

Apart from the factors already discussed above, another important factor influencing the RM policies and procedures of HEIs stems from pressure of globalisation. This has brought about increased competition among Universities and as a result, HEIs are perceived to be competing globally for students (now seen as customers) thereby further embracing the private sector cultures (see chapter 2).

4.3 ATTITUDES TOWARDS RISK MANAGEMENT

The purpose of this section was to measure the institutions' attitudes towards risk management which was a vital source of inference for informing and designing part of the questions for the qualitative strand of this study precisely objective 2 and 3 (please see Section 3.1.2). Analysis of responses from this section was also essential in corroborating qualitative findings from corresponding themes. Therefore, question 8 comprised of questions which were carefully structured to gauge institutional risk management attitudes in HEIs.

Q8. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

Table 8.6: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 8.

Answer Options	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Response Count
The tolerance and risk appetite of the institution are clearly understood and are part of the institution’s decision-making culture.	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	3 (18.75%)	11 (68.75%)	1 (6.25%)	16 (100%)
In pursuing business objectives, decision making in my institution is guided by events as they occur without much regard to the amount of risk the institution is willing to take.	2 (12.5%)	12 (75%)	0 (0%)	2 (12.5%)	0 (0%)	16 (100%)
Operational and strategic decisions of the institution are guided by the institution’s risk tolerance.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (25%)	12 (75%)	0 (0%)	16 (100%)
I regard oversight of (enterprise) risk management as a priority at my institution.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (25%)	12 (75%)	0 (0%)	16 (100%)

As presented in the above table, 6.25% of the respondents strongly agreed that the risk appetite and risk tolerance of their various institution are clearly understood and are part of their decision-making culture, while more than half of the respondents agreed, while 6.25% disagreed with the statement. On whether decision making is dependent on occurrence of events regardless of the amount of risk the institution is willing to take when pursuing business objectives, 12.5% of the respondents agreed, while 75% and 12.5% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. 75% of the respondents agreed that their institution’s risk tolerance play a vital role in making operational and strategic decisions while equally 75% also agreed that oversight of risk management is a priority in their various institutions.

4.3.1 Synopsis

As a general practice, every organisation’s approach to risk management is usually stated in their risk policy as approved by the board. As previously discussed in chapter 2, this should be the essential first step towards the development of an effective risk management process that should not be ignored. Thus, it is essential that for risk management process to be effective, the policy framework should include at minimum, considerations such as: ‘policy statement’, ‘risk

appetite’, ‘risk tolerance’, ‘internal control and assurance’, ‘roles and responsibilities’, ‘monitoring and review’, and ‘risk strategy’ as well as a proper understanding of these by users of the framework. Findings from some of the institutions’ documents reviewed by the researcher in phase 2 this study showed that some institutions confuse both risk tolerance and risk appetite or use them interchangeably; while results from the survey of this study also corroborated this fact showing that some institution do not clearly understand these risk terminologies neither do they inform the institutions’ decision making culture.

Furthermore, it was observed that some HEIs do not regularly carryout update of their policy manuals. While Institutions often state their desire to regularly review and update their risk management policy, this unfortunately has not been the case among many institutions. It was however observed that only 16.67% of case Universities in this study have actually carried out an up-to-date review of their risk management policy. Not frequently reviewing and updating risk management framework could lead to serious danger of the framework being no longer effective – as it may no longer be able to control/mitigate new and emerging risk.

However, this overwhelming attitude of neglect or failure by a significant number of HEIs in carrying out regular update of their risk management framework and policy statement tends to mirror the argument of some scholars earlier presented in chapter 2.4.5 of this study that organisations out of compulsion from regulators normally adopt risk management practices and processes as a mere tick in the box or compliance tool without embedding it into the organisation’s core business objectives (Arena, et.al, 2010; Esaides, 2013).

While HEIs state that the overarching objective of risk management is to improve their decision-making, findings from this research indicate that this goal has not been fully achieved. However, managers agree that risk management has presented their institution with a more comprehensive view of risk across board while presenting them opportunities to proactively focus on risk that were before now undocumented and unmitigated thus reducing uncertainties. They also believe that risk management has brought about an increased awareness of risk within the institution and enabled senior management to incorporate risk into strategic discussions and meetings which is gradually guiding their policy making decisions. Thus, there is optimism that these increased awareness and discussions would soon translate into visible

positive outcomes such as integration with strategic goals, other planning processes and management practices.

4.4 STRATEGIES OF INSTITUTIONAL RISK MANAGEMENT

Similar to previous sections, questions under this segment of the questionnaires were vital and responses were complimentary to the qualitative strand of the study such that knowledge of the institutions' procedures, policies and strategies to manage institutional risk was relevant towards the analysis of their risk management frameworks and investigating the HEI's risk management practises (please see objectives 1 and 3 in chapter 4.1.1 and research questions 1, 3 and 4 in chapter 4.1.2). Questions 6, 7, 9 – 18 are questions pertaining to this segment in the questionnaire.

Q6. Do you have a documented risk management policy?

Table 9.7: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 6.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Yes	16	100
No (please go to question 8)	0	0
Total	16	100

Q7. If yes to question 6, does your risk management policy include any of the following (please select all that apply)?

Table 10.8: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 7.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Risk appetite	16	100
Risk tolerance	9	56.25
Risk criteria	10	62.50
Risk target	0	0
Risk limit	1	6.25%
None of the above	0	0
Total	16*	

*Multiple responses were allowed.

Q9. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statement:

Table 11.9: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 9.

Answer Options	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Response Count
Senior administrators and Board members keenly and actively engage in discussions regarding risks affecting the institution.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	10 (62.50%)	5 (31.25%)	16 (100%)

Q10. Discussion and consideration of institutional risks occur primarily in (check all that apply):

Table 12.10: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 10.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Full Board meeting	7	43.75
Finance committee meeting	0	0
Audit committee meeting	7	43.75
None of the above	0	0
Other	8	50
Total	16*	

*Multiple responses were allowed.

All of the respondents (100%) as regards question 6 agreed they have a documented risk management policy and they responded thus to question 7 that their risk management policy covers the following: Risk Appetite (100%), Risk Tolerance (56.25%), Risk Criteria (62.50%), Risk Target (0%) and Risk Limit (6.25%). On risk affecting the institutions as presented in question 9 above, more than half of the respondents (62.50%) agreed that senior executives and board members are actively engaged on discussions regarding such risks and a further 31.25% strongly agreed while 6.25% were indifferent. Respondents were further asked in question 10 where discussions and considerations of institutional risk would primarily occur? 43.75% said ‘Full Board meeting’ and a further 43.75% answered ‘Audit Committee meeting’. Multiple responses were allowed, and respondents were allowed to include answers not previously on the options given. As such half of the respondents (50%) included answers such as: ‘Risk Group meetings’, ‘Senior Management Group meetings’, ‘Partnership Council’ and ‘Court’.

Q11. Major risks to success of your institution’s mission are identified through comprehensive, strategic risk assessments.

Table 13.11: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 11.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Yes	12	75
No (please skip to question 13)	4	25
Total	16	100

Q12. If yes to Q11, when was the most recent comprehensive assessment carried out?

Table 14.12: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 12.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Less than a year ago	12	100
1-2 years ago,	0	0
3-4 years ago,	0	0
Over 5 years ago	0	0
Total	12	100

Respondents were asked in question 11 if they regularly carryout comprehensive and strategic risk assessments to enable them to identify major risks to the success of their institutions’ goals and three-quarter (75%) of the respondents answered yes while 25% answered no. All of those that answered in the affirmative further confirmed such assessment was carried out less than a year ago as shown in question 12 above. Asked on the frequency on the evaluation of major risks identified by strategic risk assessment by senior administrators and board members in question 13, 25% reported ‘Every board meeting’, 37.5% said annually, 18.75% said that such evaluation is carried out when needed. Multiple responses were allowed, and respondents were also allowed to include additional options not captured on the list and 37.5% therefore included options listed herein: “Bi-annually”, “Quarterly” and “Monthly senior management group meetings”.

Q13. Board members and senior administrators regularly evaluate major risks identified by the strategic risk assessment (please check all applicable options):

Table 15.13: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 13.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Every board meeting	4	25
Every year	6	37.5
Every other year	0	0
As needed	3	18.75
None of the above	0	0
Other	6	37.5
Total	16*	

*Multiple responses were allowed.

Q14. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

Table 16.14: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 14.

Answer Options	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Response Count
The likelihood of expected and unexpected events are regularly assessed and considered by senior administrators and Board members.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	13 (81.25%)	2 (12.5%)	16 (100%)
Senior administrators and Board members will consider strategies such as: risk avoidance, risk mitigation, risk sharing and risk acceptance when responding to major risks relating to mission success.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	12 (75%)	3 (18.75%)	16 (100%)
Board members and senior administrators identify activities needed to ensure that controls for major risks are put in place.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	14 (87.50%)	2 (12.50%)	16 (100%)
Senior administrators and board members use monitoring tools and carry out activities to determine the effectiveness of the institution's risk management framework.	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	5 (31.25%)	8 (50%)	2 (12.50%)	16 (100%)

From the scenarios presented in question 14, over three-quarter (81.25%) of respondents agreed that senior management and board members regularly assess the probability of expected and unexpected events and a further 12.5% strongly agreed while 6.25% were undecided. Furthermore, 75% agreed that Senior management and Board members evaluate risk strategies (i.e., avoidance, mitigation, risk sharing acceptance etc.) when responding to major risks in relation to their objectives, a further 18.75% strongly agreed while 6.25% were undecided. More so, all the respondents were in agreement that senior administrators and board members create measures for control of major risks – 87.5% agreed and a further 12.5% strongly agreed. Half of the respondents (50%) agreed and a further 12.5% strongly agreed that management executives and board members use analytical tools to monitor the effectiveness of the institution’s risk management framework. 31.25% were undecided while 6.25% disagreed.

Q15. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statement:

Table 17.15: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 15.

Answer Options	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Response Count
The risk management philosophy of the institution is captured in policy statements, oral and written communications, and decision making.	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	3 (18.75%)	10 (62.50%)	2 (12.5%)	16 (100%)

Q16. How often are the following risks usually discussed during board meetings?

Table 18.16: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 16.

Answer Options	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Routinely	Response Count
Operational	0 (0%)	1 (6.67%)	4 (26.67%)	6 (40%)	4 (26.67%)	15 (100%)
Legal and Regulatory	0 (0%)	1 (6.67%)	4 (26.67%)	5 (33.33%)	5 (33.33%)	15 (100%)
Financial	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.67%)	8 (53.33%)	6 (40%)	15 (100%)
Reputational	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (20%)	8 (53.33%)	4 (26.67%)	15 (100%)
Strategic	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (13.33%)	9 (60%)	4 (26.67%)	15 (100%)
Political	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (40%)	5 (33.33%)	4 (26.67%)	15 (100%)

In response to question 15, over half of the respondents (62.5%) agreed that policy statements, decision making, as well as oral and written communications captures the risk management philosophy of their institution, 12.5% strongly agreed while 6.25% disagreed. Respondents were asked in question 16 about the frequency of the following risks being discussed at board meetings: For ‘Operational risk’, 26.67% said it was routinely discussed, 40% answered frequently, 26.67% reported it was discussed occasionally while 6.67% said it was rarely discussed. For ‘Legal and Regulatory risk’, routinely – 33.33%, frequently – 33.33%, occasionally – 26.67% while 6.67% said it was rarely discussed. ‘Financial risk’ was reported as follows: routinely – 40%, frequently – 53.33% and occasionally – 6.67%. ‘Reputational risk’: routinely – 26.67%, frequently – 53.33% while 20% of the respondents answered occasionally. For ‘Strategic risk’, routinely – 26.67%, frequently – 60%, and occasionally – 13.33%. And finally, ‘Political risk’ was reported thus: routinely – 26.67%, frequently – 33.33% while 40% of the respondents said political risks were occasionally discussed at board meetings.

Q17. Who has been assigned with the primary responsibility for institutional risk management by the governing board?

Table 19.17: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 17.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Principal	4	25
Financial Officer	1	6.25
Provost/VP academic affairs	0	0
Chief legal Counsel	0	0
Chief Compliance/audit officer	1	6.25
Chief risk officer	0	0
None	0	0
Other	10	62.50
Total	16	100

Responding to question 17, 25% of respondents replied that the ‘Principal’ has been assigned with the key responsibility for institutional risk management by the governing board, 6.25% said such was the responsibility of the financial officer, another 6.25% said it is the chief compliance/audit officer that has been given such mandate while more than half of the respondents (62.5%) gave other opinions such as: “Senior Vice Principal”, “Head of Planning”, Chief Operating officer”, “Heads of Colleges and Professional Group services”, “University Secretary” and “Director of Corporate Services”.

Q18. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

Table 20.18: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 18.

Answer Options	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Response Count
The governing board monitors the institution’s risk through regular and formal reports by the officer assigned with risk management responsibility.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.25%)	7 (43.75%)	8 (50%)	16 (100%)
As a governing board member or senior administrator, I am adequately furnished with enough information on developments within the institution that may impact upon the risk profile of the establishment.	0 (%)	1 (6.25%)	2 (12.5%)	8 (50%)	5 (31.25%)	16 (100%)
The risk reports include consideration of emerging and/or changing risks.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (12.5%)	10 (62.5%)	4 (25%)	16 (100%)

Question 18 asked if the governing board monitors the institution’s risk management through regular and formal reports by the officer assigned with risk management responsibilities. Half (50%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 43.75% agreed while 6.25% were undecided. Furthermore, 31.25% of the respondents strongly agreed that board members and senior administrators are adequately furnished with information on developments within the institution that may affect the risk profile of the organisation, 50% agreed, 12.25% were undecided while 6.25% disagreed. Additionally, on whether considerations of emerging and/or changing risks are included in the risk reports, 25% strongly agreed, 62.5% agreed while 12.5% were undecided.

Q19. Overall, how would you rate your institution's approach to, and management of, major risks to the success of your institution's mission and objectives?

Table 21.19: Tabular Presentation of Analysis – Survey Question 19.

Answer Options	Response Count	Percent (%)
Exemplar	1	6.25
Above average	12	75
Average	2	12.25
Below average	1	6.25
Poor	0	0
Total	16	100

Finally, in question 19, respondents were asked to rate the success of their institution's risk management approach in relation to the success of their mission and objectives. 75% of the respondents answered theirs was above average, 6.25% think theirs is exemplar, 12.25% think theirs is average while 6.25% of respondents submitted that their approach was below average.

4.4.1 Synopsis

This section of the survey considered the strategies in relation to the framework the case institutions have employed to manage risk. Analysis to responses in this section enabled the researcher to have some level of understanding as regards some of the strategies of RM employed by various HEIs which was vital in designing more probing questions during the interview stage for a better understanding of the subject. Analysis of these have been presented below.

Risk rating matrix

It is common practice for institutions to adopt a risk scoring matrix (i.e., probability multiplied by impact) to enable them measure risk and allow for comparative analysis of key risks. Findings from the review of documents of case Universities in chapter 5 of this study revealed that 66.67% of the institutions evaluates risk with the help of a probability/impact rating matrix. There are several classifications of a risk rating matrix – the level of risk matrices could either be a 3x3, 4x4, 5x5 etc., depending on the choice of an organisation. As observed in chapter 5 of this study, case institutions adopt a risk matrix which they believe work best for their risk management model. However, as discussed in chapter 2.4 of this study, risk rating matrix could be problematic if not fully understood or when applied wrongly as it could lead to some key

risks being overlooked or regarded as irrelevant and this may be dangerous to the organisation's risk management efforts.

Institutional Risks deliberations

Good practice recommends that senior administrators and board members should be actively engaged in deliberations and considerations as regards institutional risks. Findings from this research revealed that only 31.82% of institutions were currently doing so, whereas 31.82% revealed that these deliberations usually occur primarily in Audit committee meetings and a further 36.36% revealed that such discussions would usually occur primarily at other committee meetings such as: Risk group meetings, Partnership council meetings etc. Therefore, for best practice, considerations for institutional risks should as a responsibility be discussed by full board and every other risk management committee.

Risk monitoring

Institutions internal and external environment is increasingly becoming dynamic thus creating lots of uncertainties. Therefore, regular and comprehensive monitoring of risk is needed to ensure early detection of new and emerging risk. While it is definitely a welcome development that most (75%) institutions carry out periodic strategic and comprehensive risk assessment to identify major risks to the success of their missions and objectives as findings revealed in this research. However, some institutions (25%) still depend on an ad-hoc basis risk assessment (i.e., as prompted by events).

Risk Manager

With the adoption and implementation of risk management models and practices within HEI's, staff have either been deployed and trained or risk experts have been appointed newly to oversee and coordinate the risk management process. Previously, the Audit divisions were tasked with overseeing compliance. But with risk management which involves protecting the organisation from uncertainties, HEIs have had to create a new position of 'risk manager' (the title may differ slightly across institutions). These risk managers have a unique reporting line across HEIs – usually directly to the Risk Management Committee (these committees may vary in name depending on institutions) with the remit of not only overseeing the process and in some instances instituting the framework, but also act as a link between the board, management

and other staff members as well as creating awareness, organising trainings and retraining of the risk management process.

Risk Oversight

Apart from the risk manager, Universities have constituted committees – as discussed in chapter 5 of this study and part of their remit is to oversee the risk management policy and framework and also to advise the board on matters relating to key risks that may affect the institution's strategic objectives. These committees (committee names vary slightly across institutions) include – Risk group, Audit and Risk committee, Executive management committee, the Board etc. These committees together with the risk management strategy and policy, constitute the risk management framework of the individual Universities. These committees work to ensure there is proper risk management oversight functions and that there is a proper flow of communication (top-down and bottom-up) across board. Apart from these committees, 16.67% of the case institutions further assigned risk owners to act as additional pair of eyes to every key risk within the institution.

Risk registers

Risk register is key to the management of risk within organisations as it serves as a repository for all risks identified by the establishment. In their day-to-day business, HEIs encourage every unit within the institution to document any risk identified on the risk register. Every risk identified is evaluated and treated accordingly by the relevant authority and any risk above the threshold would be escalated to the next level of authority. Regular review of the risk register is carried out within set time frames as specified in institutions' policy guidance by various committees and this enables HEIs to document and monitor key risks that may threaten their strategic objectives and present such to the board for necessary action. This is a generic process across all case HEIs in this study, however, the approach is slightly different across institutions.

4.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter presents results and analysis from the qualitative survey carried out across 16 Scottish institutions. Drawing inference from the 'research question' – '*How do HEIs structure and execute their risk management functions?*', the chapter presented results and analysis covering several factors to aid understanding of the composition of HEIs risk management system – ranging from composition, implementation, roles and responsibilities of key actors of

the risk management architecture etc. Thus, analysis from this chapter was vital in providing answers to the research question on the structure and practices of risk management architecture in HEIs. Furthermore, this chapter also served as building blocks or foundation on which the qualitative strand of this study was built. The next chapter, therefore, is presentation and discussion of the results and findings from the qualitative phase of this study.

5.0 RESULTS FROM QUALITATIVE INTERVIEW AND DOCUMENT ANALYSIS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter present findings from phase 2 (qualitative) of this research. As discussed already in the methodology chapter of this research, documents sourced from case Universities were thematically analysed together with interview data. The reason for analysing both the transcribed interview data and information sourced from case institutions' documents together was because these documents provided a good measure to corroborate and validate the results and findings of the study as it was discovered after transcribing the interviews that a good proportion of responses from respondents were also contained in these relevant documents.

Thus, findings from the analysis of the qualitative data have been presented in this chapter and summarised in accordance with the key themes previously discussed in chapters 3 and 4 namely: 'Policies and Procedures of Risk Management', Attitudes and Approach Towards Institutional Risk Management' and Strategies to Manage Institutional Risk' – thus, results and findings from both the quantitative and qualitative strand of this study respectively have been presented and grouped using these key themes. These key themes ensured uniformity and ease of mixing of results and findings from both the quantitative and qualitative strands of this study. Additionally, a brief history and an overview of some key details and their risk management framework or process regarding the case institutions is also discussed to enhance understanding.

5.1.1 Selection criteria for case Universities

Discussed in chapter 3.9 of this study was the need to guarantee interviewees confidentiality and anonymity. Thus, presented in table 5.1 below are anonymised codes for case universities as well as corresponding codes respondents and their designations. Having conducted and analysed the survey results, the objective was to include only institutions with fully adopted risk management framework in phase 2 of the study as case institutions and fortunately, all sixteen institutions as observed from the quantitative analysis met this criterion. However, as at the time of conducting the interviews, some challenges occurred as some initial identified respondents had either changed jobs (Epsilon, Rho and Ioata Universities) or were on vacation

(Eta, Tau and Lambda Universities) and respondents from Omicron and Upsilon Universities were not interested in taking part in the interview phase.

The researcher did not have luxury of time to wait for respondents who went on vacation or those that took up new positions – because they needed plenty of time to settle into their new roles. Thus, interviews were conducted with respondents from 7 institutions namely: Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Zeta, Theta and Kappa. However, as discussed previously (chapter 4.6), data for Kappa University was not included for analysis because feedback needed for clarifications to some issues observed were not received. Despite the challenges of not being able to include all projected Universities in the second phase of the study, the selected universities for this phase of the study ticked all the boxes – in terms of geographical, structural, date established etc. – relevant to the reliability, validity and success of this research as shown in table 5.1 below. However, to ensure greater reliability and validity of this study, the researcher as already discussed in chapter 4.6.2.2, decided to further research on RM documents of case institutions of this study which is vital for triangulation and increased validity of results.

Interviews were conducted with key risk experts in the various case Universities and documents were reviewed across these Universities. This interview data along with documents from case institutions sourced throughout the course of this research were carefully analysed using the reflexive thematic analysis method. Key contacts from various case institutions provided the researcher with further documents electronically and feedbacks and follow-ups were carried out where and when necessary via emails and phone calls.

Table 5.22: Characteristics of Case Universities

Case Universities	Alpha	Beta	Gamma	Delta	Zeta	Theta
Respondents Designation	Risk Manager	Risk and Insurance Manager	Risk and Resilience Manager	Policy Officer – Risk and Audit	Head of Resilience and Safety	Director of corporate Governance
Respondents code	Alpha-RM	Beta-RIM	Gamma-RRM	Delta-PO-RA	Zeta-HRS	Theta-DCG
Classification*	Ancient	Ancient	Civic	Civic/Ancient	Post-92	Post-92
Structure*	Centralised	Centralised	Centralised	Centralised	Decentralised	Decentralised
Registered no. of students (2018/2019) session.	34,275	10,570	22,640	15,915	17,025	9,525
Risk Management Framework	Bespoke (adapted from ISO 31000:2009)	Bespoke	Bespoke	Bespoke (adapted from ISO 31000:2009)	Bespoke (with some ISO:2009 characteristics)	Bespoke (adapted from International Actuarial Association (IAA)).

*Classification: (see chapter 2.5)

*Structure: ‘Centralised’ structure refers to institutions with campuses situated in same city while ‘Decentralised’ structure refers to institutions with campuses located in more than one city.

5.2 CASE PRESENTATIONS

To allow for a better illustration and useful comparison, presentation of cases in this research have been grouped based on the institutions’ classification of ‘Ancient’, ‘Civic’ and ‘Post-92’.

5.2.1 Ancient Universities

As earlier stated in chapter 2, Ancient Universities are medieval institutions founded before the 15th century. There are 7 of these known Universities in Britain and Ireland and four of these are in Scotland. These Universities enjoy a unique form of governance different from the governance structure in more recent institutions. In Scotland, there are further distinctive features or laid down arrangements by ‘Universities (Scotland) Acts’ allowing for a tripartite governance structure comprising of the ‘General Council’, ‘University Court’ and the ‘Academic Senate’. Two of these four Ancients HEIs in Scotland (Alpha and Beta) were selected for the qualitative strand of the research with the researcher conducting interviews with the risk experts from these Universities.

5.2.1.1 Case 1: Alpha University

Overview of Organisation and key risk personnel

Alpha university is among the four ancient universities in Scotland with five major campuses across central Scotland (Von Prondzynski, et.al, 2012). It is one of the oldest Universities in the anglophone world and is credited to have played a key role during the ‘Enlightenment age’. The institution is one of the UK’s most prestigious institutions and a renowned university globally for its research excellence and academic prowess. A member of both the League of European Universities and the prominent Russel Group, the Alpha University is structured across three (3) colleges and twenty-one (21) schools which on the average, receives over 60,000 applications each year across the globe with latest available information showing a total number of 34,275 registered students as of 2018/2019 academic year (HESA, 2020).

The successes, achievements and growth of the university over the years can be attributed to its ability of taking advantage of opportunities, and in pursuance of its strategic objectives, the institution cannot circumvent risk-taking. Therefore, to increase understanding and risk awareness of the institution, the University has entrenched Risk management throughout the organisation in order to ensure proper risk taking in a controlled, regulated and conscious approach. Though the University enjoins everyone to be involved in the risk management process, however, there is a risk management governance structure in place to ensure a successful and coordinated practice.

The drivers of this risk management governance process consist of the ‘Court’ – whose main aim is to chart the course and influence the institution’s risk management culture, the ‘University Executive’ – responsible for the application and realisation of the court’s risk management policies, ‘Heads of Colleges, Schools and Professional Services’ – part of their task is the identification, evaluation and management of operational and strategic risk as well as ensuring compliance of the institution’s policies. Additionally, there is an ‘Audit and Risk committee’ - whose role is to monitor the overall institution’s risk management process and also to advise the court on suitability measures for assessing and managing risk.

There is also the ‘Risk management committee’ – responsible for assisting and advising the ‘Audit and Risk committee and by extension the Court, on effective monitoring and application of risk management policies such as: identifying and evaluating major risks that endanger the

accomplishment of the institution's objectives. Also, the University recently appointed a 'Risk manager' who is also part of the 'Corporate Services Group' and reports to the Risk management committee, whose remit is but not limited to – facilitate and implement the 'risk management framework', support with the analysis of risk at operational level escalate significant risks to the strategic level and assist and advice the institution on risk management.

More so, there is the 'Internal Audit' with the mandate of regularly and independently reviewing overall risk management process of the institution and report findings to the 'Audit and Risk committee as well as advise and/make recommendations to 'Senior Executives' and 'Risk Management Committee where necessary. Finally, every 'Faculty and Staff' have a crucial responsibility in managing risk. At the very least, every member is expected to be effective in managing risk within their remit as stipulated in the risk management policy of the institution and report to the managers areas of concern particularly risks beyond their scope and authority.

5.2.1.2 Case 2: Beta University

Overview of Organisation and key risk personnel

Beta University have a very rich history, and it is one of the oldest universities in the Anglo-phone speaking world. The University is situated in the east coast of Scotland (THE, n.d.). Beta University was founded by a group of Scottish graduates from Paris due to the precarious situation Scottish students found themselves in – finding it nearly impossible advancing their academic studies due to the Anglo-Scottish independence wars and the western schism, it was necessary to establish an institution of international repute in Scotland. Around the 15th century, the school had been well established and a charter of incorporation and privileges was given by the Bishop where Beta is located – Henry Wardlaw. However, the conferment of University status and degree awarding powers was the sole prerogative of the then Pope.

Following a successful application by the Bishop and with the support of King James of Scotland, a series of Papal Bull was issued by the Pope which conferred full University status on the institution. The School which not long ago celebrated 600 years of existence still houses till date some of its buildings and colleges from the medieval age. The University is home to 10,570 registered students for 2018/2019 academic session coming from over 130 countries (HESA, 2020). With Alpha University located in a small town of about 17,000 total population

means students and staff of the University accounts for more than half of the town's population (THE, n.d.).

The University is organised across four faculties (Arts, Medicine, Divinity and Science) offering over 900-degree and 100 Masters' program (THE, n.d., Scotland.org, n.d.), is a member of the renowned Russel group and it boasts of over 96% student employability within first six months of graduation. According to Guardian University rankings, the University ranked overall best in Scotland and second best in the UK in its 2020 rankings (Guardian University Guide, 2020). It also ranked first in student satisfaction in the 2019 National Student Survey (Scotland.org., n.d.).

Achievements recorded by the University over the centuries is only possible as a result of its commitment to achieving its goals and objectives through a coordinated management structure and a well-articulated risk management process. While the institution however has a strong dedication to controlling, mitigating or even avoiding (when necessary) adverse events; however, in order not to stifle innovation, the University accepts and welcomes some degree of risk and continue to pursue activities that will enable it to maximise its opportunities and achieve its strategic goals. However, such actions are guided by the risk tolerance and risk appetite of the institution which is set by the University Court and guided by other risk management committees and personnel as discussed hereunder.

Risk Management Group

The University's Risk Management Group (RMG) chaired by the VP Governance meets quarterly and with representatives drawn from senior staff across various key units within the institution, it provides a forum for a wide-ranging discussion and assessment of current and potential risk across the University. The RMG reports to and advises the Audit and Risk Committee and by extension the Court on the Risk Management Policy assessment and implementation. In summary, the primary oversight function of risk management activities across the institution is vested on the RMG who in turn advises the Audit and Risk Committee on significant risk that is not within the risk appetite or tolerance of the University.

Audit and Risk Committee

The Audit and Risk Committee based on assurance reports on key risks and other related information received from the Risk Management Group, take action to examine the risk and advise the court on the risk profile of the institution and the general risk management framework's effectiveness of mitigating current and emerging risk. The Committee would usually recommend improvements where necessary.

Risk Adviser

The University Risk Adviser is usually seen as the custodian of the institution's Risk Register and it is his responsibility to ensure that the register captures every key risk immediately it has been identified. It is also his responsibility to provide guidance on risk assessment, planned actions and risk mitigation. The Risk adviser also renders support and frequent trainings as needed from any unit within the institution. He reports to the Risk Management Group, Audit and Risk Committee and Risk and action owners.

Risk and action owners

These are key persons that have been identified on the risk register as having the responsibility of overseeing certain significant risks. They work closely with the Risk adviser and part of their remit is to monitor and assess the risk event they oversee and regularly update information regarding such on the institution's intranet system for relevant action to be taken if necessary.

5.2.2 Civic Universities

The 19th century witnessed a major expansion to the growth of HEIs in the UK with the establishment of a good number of Universities through royal charter – as a response to the growing technological economy and increasing demand for university places by the growing population. Thus, Universities that were established by royal charter between 1900 leading up to 1992 are commonly referred to as Civic Universities. However, Among the Civic Universities, those established between 1900 and 1963 are often referred to by some as 'Red-bricks' Universities while those established between 1963 and 1992 are often referred to as 'Plate-glass' institutions. These are so-called because of their physical pattern of structures or buildings. Just like the Ancient Universities, two of these Civic Universities were selected for this research with one each from 'red-bricks' and 'Plate-glass'.

5.2.2.1 Case 3: Gamma University

Overview of Organisation and key risk personnel

Gamma University is a public funded research institution located in the west coast of Scotland. It is among the oldest universities within the city. Gamma University was conferred a University status in the mid twentieth century through a royal charter and became the first technological institute in the entire United Kingdom. The institution is the largest University in Scotland based on student numbers with about 22,640 total enrolled number of students in 2018/2019 academic session (HESA, 2020) and has twice been named 'University of the year' (2012 and 2019) by Times Higher Education (THE, 2019), achieving the feat as the only institution in the UK to have earned this award twice including several other awards too numerous to mention here (Gamma University, 2020).

According to the Gamma-RRM, the University's commitment and dedication towards its founding vision, goals and objectives have been made possible over the years due to its ardour to good governance and quality leadership made possible by a well-developed risk management process and practices. The drivers of this risk management process consist of 'The Court' with the oversight responsibility of the general risk management framework. The University's Court ensures that risk management practices across the institution are understood and well implemented. Also, part of their remit is to delegate the authority for the implementation of the Risk Management framework to the Principal of the institution as well as annual presentation of the University's Corporate Governance statement to the Scottish Funding Council.

The Principal of the institution with authority from the Court, ensures the creation, implementation and maintenance of a risk management framework and in line with the institution's policy for delegation of duties, the Principal has the prerogative to direct and delegate risk management responsibilities, which most of the time, the Chief Operating Officer of the University is the first contact by the Principal for such actions. Accordingly, the Chief Operating Officer is mandated to regularly keep the Principal abreast of any essential issue concerning the risk management practice of the institution. Part of the Chief Operating Officer's role is to ensure that the daily activities of the establishment conform to the University's goals and objectives and these are carried out effectively in accordance with the risk management framework and within the available resources. He is also the chairperson of

the institution's Risk Group, convener of the University's Emergency Management Group, and also has the responsibility of ensuring an effective disaster recovery and business continuity plans are in place for the University. Finally, he reviews annually the effectiveness of the institutions risk management framework.

Also, the University's Executive Team play important role in the risk management framework of the institution. They assist the Principal to discharge his risk management functions as they put in place necessary risk measures for controlling and monitoring the universities risk exposures and changes in its risk profile. They are also responsible for an all-encompassing review of the University's corporate risk register every quarter. The Team also ensure proper documentation of significant risks and ensuring that the risk management framework is capable of managing such. The Executive Team on an individual basis, is required to provide adequate and timely information to other team members regarding the risk management practices in their respective units which is vital to their annual review of the University's risk management practices.

More so, there is also the Risk Group chaired by the institutions Chief Operating Officer and part of its remit is supporting and advising the Executive Team and by extension the Court, regarding the risk management's monitoring and implementation process. The Risk Group is also responsible for carrying out risk audit on faculty Risk Registers and through the Chief Operating Officer, renders feedback to the Executive Team on any strategic risk identified. They are also vital in creating awareness of general risk across the institution while also carrying out the maintenance of the University's risk management profile as well as ensuring availability of web resource to staff members. Also, very important to the risk management process are: Heads of Schools, Departments and Directors of Professional Services.

These group of personnel ensure adherence to the risk management process, ascertain certain risks that may impede activities especially when seeking for new opportunities or developing new projects, ensure that major risks are well captured and documented on the risk register relevant to their unit and necessary mitigating measures and/or contingencies are available for dealing with such risk and uncertainties. Also, they are expected to communicate and escalate developing corporate risks to the Executive Team. Also, the University's Audit Committee have the remit to examine the risk management, governance and control framework and inform

the governing body of their effectiveness. The committee aside advising the court of the effectiveness of the institution's risk management policies and processes, also carry out yearly examination of the University's general approach to risk management, and where necessary, advise on necessary improvements or changes needed.

Finally, every staff of the institution is extremely important to the success of the risk management process. The University expects every member of staff to identify risk especially within their domain and where necessary abide by the principles stipulated in the institution's risk management framework. Every member of staff is encouraged to identify risk and promptly and appropriately communicate such to their line manager particularly when there are changes in operational practices or processes. Furthermore, the University directs that every staff must take responsibility of managing risk within their unit. However, in practice, each unit or department is expected to nominate a team lead that should report and escalate both positives and areas of concerns observed during practical implementation of the risk management policies to the Risk Group.

5.2.2.2 Case 4: Delta University

Overview of Organisation and key risk personnel

Delta University came into existence in in the late 19th century through donations from a prominent family in the eastern coast of Scotland. Their donations help set up the institution as and was fully incorporated into one of the ancient Universities in Scotland as a constituent college whereby students could be conferred a degree the parent University. After some frayed relationship between the parent university and the college coupled with continuous surge in students' numbers and the 'Robins report' of 1963 (see chapter 2.6), saw the college granted a University status through a Royal Chapter in the mid-twentieth century to become Delta University and retained much of the ancient tradition as a result of its previous alliance with the parent university.

Delta presently have ten Schools with several disciplines as well as several associated research units or centres attracting top-ranked students and academics globally, its current total registered number of students for the 2018/2019 academic year currently stands at 15,915 (HESA, 2020). The University won the 2020 University of the year for student experience ranked by The Times and The Sunday Times (2019). According to the institution, this is made

possible by its outstanding teaching quality and student experience. Its successful achievements over the years, is made possible by the successful execution of its strategic plans through a dedicated risk management practice and in keeping with this practice, the University have a proven risk management process which has enabled them to identify and manage its risks and as such able to meet its strategic goals.

This risk management process which is orchestrated by the University's risk management framework is governed by the 'Risk Management Oversight group', 'Academic and Corporate Governance', 'Deans, Directors and Managers of various Schools'. Their roles and responsibilities are discussed hereunder:

The Risk Management Oversight Group

Membership of this group include: The University's Secretary who is the Convener, Director of Corporate and Academic Governance, Vice Principal of the University, Nominees representing School Managers, Nominees representing School Deans, Finance Manager, Directors of Professional Services, Head of Safety Services and Assistant Policy Officer serving as Clerk to the Committee. The remit of this group which is expected to convene at least twice a year includes but not limited to identification of significant risks that either affect or have the potential to affect the institution; oversee the general activities and performance of the institution and also of individual schools and directorates through identification; evaluation and the mitigation of major risks relating to the University's activities; Evaluate action plans relating to risks that falls outside the University's risk appetite; Making adequate and effective plans proactively across the institution for business continuity, disaster recovery and crisis management and rendering needed advise to Audit Committee and the University's Court as regards the organisation's risk appetite.

Academic and Corporate Governance

The University's Academic and Corporate Governance through its Director have the responsibility to coordinate and direct the University's risk management process in terms of directing the risk management strategy and objectives, maintenance of the institutional risk management register and development of standardised procedures consistent with the identification, evaluation and reporting of major risks that can hinder the University from achieving its goals and objectives.

Directors, Deans and School Managers

Every level of authority in the University such as Schools and Directorates and Professional Services are obliged to have and maintain their individual risk registers which should be regularly reviewed. The heads of these units i.e., School Managers/Deans/Directors, are tasked with identifying significant risks within their domain and evaluating the effect such risks poses. They have the authority to implement strategies to mitigate or prevent the occurrence of such threats and also proactively implement plans for sustainability. However, they are expected to escalate any risks that is above their authority.

In summary, while the risk management policy details the objectives of the risk management framework, roles and responsibilities of key personnel of the risk management framework, the risk management guidance relates to implementation strategies, whereas the tools necessary to implement this framework are the risk registers. The University expects schools and professional services groups to have and maintain their individual risk registers while there is an institutional or central risk register that is jointly reviewed by the 'University Executive Group,' 'Professional Services Group', 'University Executive Group' and the 'University Court' at least on a bi-annual basis.

The institution has the sole responsibility to develop and enact procedures and guidance for implementing an effective risk management practices and processes and also ensure the sustainability of a robust risk management culture across the institution whereas the University's Court has the remit for the oversight of this risk management process and through delegated authority to the Audit Committee, ensures the oversight of this process is in compliance with best practice. It is expected also that every employee of the institution forms part of this risk management process through a good understanding of the nature of risk faced by the institution, taking ownership and the ability to manage risk within their area of authority.

5.2.3 Post 92 Universities

Following the 1992 Further and Higher Education Act as previously discussed in chapter 2 of this study, there was another significant expansion in the academic sector with the British government converting about 35 polytechnics and other institutions mainly colleges of higher education to university status (Burnes et.al., 2014). Several of these Polytechnics though given University status in 1992 had roots dating back mid 19th Century. Furthermore, between 2001

and 2013, there was again an increase to the number of HEIs with the establishment of a further 31 universities and thus, these universities established after 1992 are often referred to as ‘post-92’ or ‘modern’ universities (Wyness, 2010).

Among the Universities established between 2001 and 2013 which are the newer of the Post-92 Universities and probably did not have Polytechnic roots, two are in Scotland. Thus, for the enhancement of validity and generalisation of this study, the researcher carefully selected from among the post-92 Universities one each from among those established with the 1992 Act and those established between 2001 and 2013. The researcher also ensured that these selected HEIs for this study ticked all the boxes in terms of geographical, structural and date of establishment as already discussed in section 5.1.1 above.

5.2.3.1 Case 5: Zeta University

Overview of Organisation and key risk personnel

Zeta University is regarded as one of Scotland’s largest post-92 institution by population with student enrolment for 2018/2019 academic year totalling 17,025 (HESA, 2020). Although Zeta is considered as a new University, its history dates back to the late 19th century when it was established as a Technical Institute through the assistance of some renowned local entrepreneurs who found it useful to the booming industrial town in the west of Scotland. In early 20th century, the institution was able to award degree qualifications through the University of London. Recognising its impact to education.

In mid twentieth century, the institution was endorsed by the Council for National Academic Awards (CNAA) and degrees and Honours degrees were awarded for the first time by the institution. However, in 1992, following the Further and Higher Education Act, the Institute was granted a University status. By the start of the 21st century, through a merger with another college, the University became known as Zeta (Zeta, 1898 - 2004). Zeta University is renowned as one of Scotland’s best vocational institutions with over 140 established relationships with commercial, industrial and business partners (Scotland.org, n.d.). Guardian University Guide rankings (2020) ranked Zeta University number one in the UK for Teacher Education in 2020 and also ranked among the top three Universities in Scotland for teaching quality in 2019 (The Times and Sunday Times, 2018).

Zeta University currently have five campuses – four located across the South-West and West of Scotland and one in London, England: four academic schools and a good number of departments. While the University enjoys enormous opportunities from its decentralised campuses – benefiting from a wider outreach; it also presents significant risk compared to less decentralised institutions. Therefore, the University regards risk management as a fundamental part its decision-making process. Most part of the schools and departments have a remit across more than one campus and accordingly, organisation and risk management reporting are carried out on a structural basis for the schools and departments rather than geographical based. This approach according to the institution allows for a coordinated management of risk and an effective oversight activity. Below is an overview of the institution’s risk management organisation and key personnel:

The Court

The University’s Court as regards to risk management is saddled with the ultimate responsibility to implement and oversee control systems and accountability which includes operational as well as the assessment of risk. It is also the responsibility of the Court to implement a suitable risk-based strategic approach for planning and decision making. It is also the remit of the Court to determine the risk appetite of the institution as well as ensuring regular review of the risk appetite and ensure that risk taking by the University are constantly reviewed and within the university’s risk tolerance as set out in the policy statement.

Audit and Risk Committee

The Audit and Risk Committee of Zeta University carry out the oversight functions of the Annual Risk Statement as well as risk registers for the ‘Consolidated School’, Department, Project and Corporate. This committee is also responsible for assessment of significant risks identified and its management thereof through the feedback it receives at every meeting. The committee informs or escalates significant risk that threatens the University’s sustainability to the Court.

Executive Group

The University’s Executive Group receives updates on key risks regularly and as part of their oversight responsibilities, they ensure that such risks are effectively managed and captured in the Corporate Risk Register. As part of their responsibility, the Group act as the first line of

action to endorse the various risk registers i.e., Corporate and the Consolidated School, Department and Project risk registers before submission to the Audit and Risk Committee.

The Principal and Vice Chancellor

The University's Principal and Vice Chancellor has the oversight responsibility for all of the institution's corporate risk and has the remit of delegating responsibility to corporate members of the Executive Group for their day-to-day oversight risk management functions.

The University Secretary

The institution's Secretary who is also the Secretary to the Court, have the remit to assist the Principal and Vice Chancellor of the University to implement procedures for effective risk management within the University. The University Secretary also ensures effective corporate governance within the institution and provides necessary support and advice to the Court and Principal and Vice Chancellor on governance related activities.

Risk Group

The Risk Group comprises of the University Secretary, Head Strategic Planning, Head of Resilience and Safety, representatives of Senior Academic and Directorates and Senior Risk and Insurance Officer. This group holds its meetings quarterly with the Head of Internal Audit also in attendance. Part of their responsibility is to assist the University Secretary on implementing risk management procedures and also assist towards ensuring that risk management is effectively entrenched into University's culture. The Risk Group also provides assistance on the review of project and operational risk registers and also assist in escalating relevant risk to the Audit and Risk Committee where and when necessary as well as providing useful advice on and escalation of corporate risks to the Executive Group.

Head of Resilience and Safety

The Head of Resilience and Safety of the University is regarded as the custodian of the risk management framework within the institution with the remit to ensure that risk management is effective and regarded as a culture by every member of staff within the institution.

Senior Risk and Insurance Officer

It is the responsibility of the Senior Risk and Insurance Officer to provide guidance and support on risk management to every member of staff and ensures that there is feedback mechanism for effective communication of risk and also influences non-risk-experts on identification and evaluation of risk through the provision of risk management trainings. The goal is to ensure schools and departments successfully integrate risk management practices in all of their operational activities and decisions.

Deans/Directors/Heads

Deans/Directors/Heads have the mandate to implement risk management practices across their control areas while escalating strategic risks above their risk appetite to the next level of authority. It is their responsibility to ensure effective risk management within their area of authority and ensure that every risk is captured on the risk register, ensure that every member of staff within their unit is aware of key risks within the unit.

Head of Internal Audit Service

The Head of Internal Audit Service in Zeta University is responsible for the overall risk management practice within the institution and the frequent and independent review of the entire risk management process as required by regulatory authorities. The Internal Audit also provides support to the University's Audit and Risk Committee by rendering valuable advice and recommendations on risk management. As part of its assurance function, the Head of Internal Audit is required to come up with annual report and should include opinions regarding the effectiveness and capability of the University's risk management and internal control framework as this will inform the Audit and Risk Committee's annual report which is submitted to the Scottish Funding Council as a mandatory requirement.

All Members of Staff

The University expects every staff member to have adequate knowledge of risks within their area of operation and able to manage their own risk as well as document and escalate any risks beyond their authority through the relevant channel to the appropriate department.

5.2.3.2 Case Six: Theta University

Overview of Organisation and key risk personnel

Theta University awarded University status only in the 21st century by the Privy Council, is one of Scotland's newest University (BBC, 2011). It operates a very unique structure with a partnership covering 13 independent Colleges and over 70 research centres (Uartic, n.d.) with a landmark three times the size of Wales but is brought together through technology. Zeta University though a new institution, some of its partner colleges dates back to the 17th Century (BBC, 2011; Independent, 2014).

Before it was granted a university status, Zeta University had partnerships with University of Strathclyde, University of Aberdeen and Open University Validation Service which helped to authenticate its degrees. However, following recommendations from Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA), Zeta was granted taught degree awarding powers (tDAP) which was a major step closer to its obtaining full University status (Independent, 2014).

Despite only being granted University status in in the 21st century, UHI in 2014 had over 69% of its research rated as 'world leading or internationally excellent' by the Research Excellent Framework review (Uartic, n.d.). The University had a total of 9,525 registered students for the 2018/2019 academic session from over 51 countries (HESA, 2020; Scotland.org, n.d.) and in 2018, was ranked in the top 5 Universities across Scotland for overall student satisfaction (THE, 2018) with over 97% of its graduates being employed or progressing with studies (Scotland.org, n.d.). These achievements within this short period could only be attributed to good governance and a well thought out strategic plan. With the institution's unusual structure, it is worthwhile to have a look into the organisation and key personnel within the institution.

The University Court

The University's Court plays an important role in the management of risk across the institution. It is the responsibility of the Court to set the tone of risk management and establish the risk culture across the institution. They provide a guiding framework to help determine the acceptable level of risk exposure the University is willing to take at certain circumstances, i.e., the risk appetite of the institution and it is also their responsibility to review and approve any major evaluation or decision impacting the risk profile of the University or its risk exposure. Following advice from senior management, both internal and external audit and the Audit

committee, it is also the responsibility of the University's Court to present an annual statement of corporate governance to the Scottish Funding Council as required.

Finance and General-Purpose Committee

The Finance and General-Purpose Committee of the institution ensures that key risks regarding specific proposals presented to them have been thoroughly screened and can be managed appropriately in line with the context set by the Court. They also have the remit to ensure an effective management of corporate risks and its result evident across the institution.

Audit Committee

The University's Audit Committee ensures a proper oversight and a holistic risk management approach across the institution. The committee is responsible for monitoring the policies and procedures of risk management and risk assessment within the institution and advises the Court on their effectiveness. The risk management structure of the University is reviewed annually by the Audit committee and where or when necessary, the committee recommends changes for improvements to the risk management process or framework. It is also within the remit of the Audit Committee to present a statement of corporate governance to the Court on an annual basis with particular reference to risk management.

Internal Audit

The Internal Audit through its Head carryout annual risk review of the institution in accordance with recommendations and guidelines of relevant professional bodies and governing authorities through which an audit plan is developed. The internal audit also advises and provide recommendations to senior managers on strategic risk where necessary and they also communicate their findings to the audit committee on a regular basis.

Risk Review Group

The Risk Review Group which reports to the Finance and General-purpose Committee, meets quarterly and the part of the Group's remit is to examine the risk registers of the University including the risk registers of strategic projects which allows for an independent review and findings will be communicated to the relevant project board.

Senior Management Team

The University's Senior Management Team play a key role as regards risk management. They oversee the implementation of and ensure compliance to risk management policies and procedures as directed by the Court, ensuring that these policies are clearly understood by staff, subsidiary organisations and relevant external partners. They regularly carry out reviews and evaluations of strategic and operational risks within the institution and communicate any developing corporate risk identified to the Risk Review Group for necessary action. It is also the responsibility of Senior Management to ensure that the risk management policies and procedures are clear and well understood by every staff member in order to effectively carry out their duties.

5.3 DISCUSSION

The case studies in this research reveals that the risk management frameworks adopted by HEIs are dependent upon the organisational context and strategic objectives. There is no 'one-size-fit-all' approach neither is there a 'comprehensively appropriate' approach to adopting a risk management system or framework. Thus, chapter 4.2 of this study previously reviewed a variety of contingency factors affecting the design choices of HEIs RM systems as per their policies, procedures and composition which influences decisions and implementation of RM. This section, therefore, presents pragmatic appraisal of the designs of HEIs risk management frameworks.

Judging from the assessment of institutional economics as discussed by Burns (2000), HEIs risk management systems are presented in this research as a composition of formal activities, procedures, manuals, formal and informal rules which are established as institutionalised practices. This study evaluates risk management rules, practices and procedures and conceptualises the actions of stakeholders. For a clear understanding of this context as regards the evaluation of the composition of case institutions' RM framework, the components of HEIs RM framework are enunciated comparatively in this study through these two main categories:

- Characteristics of HEIs RM systems i.e., 'the design and structure of RM frameworks, roles and responsibilities regarding the RM model across the institutions, as well as the RM process i.e., methodologies and tools assigned in delivering these processes and
- Maturity and advancement of HEIs risk management models.

5.3.1 Characteristics of HEIs risk management systems

All the institutions within the case study of this research claimed to have fully adopted and implemented RM across their enterprise. This claim is evidenced in responses from the quantitative strand of this research and also made available in publicly available documents of these institutions. However, it may not be objective to rely solely on the perceptions of the respondents and the institutions documents in general as it is based upon their levels of expertise and knowledge of best practices in risk management developed across institutions. Besides, there are possibilities that some organisations may claim to have fully adopted RM in the quest of reputation and global reach whereas the level of RM implementation or the RM maturity may actually be low. Therefore, the researcher conducted a thorough assessment on the maturity levels of RM among the case institutions and contrasted such with perceptions from both their publicly available manuals and responses from interviewees.

Formalisation

Formalisation is observed through the translation and understanding of risk appetite and risk tolerances and are well-defined for varied risk exposures such as but not limited to safety incident or maximum acceptable ratios. There were no noticeable differences on the formalisation levels of HEIs RM systems irrespective of the size, structure or date of establishment. Findings reveals that risk management frameworks are captured in several documents detailing roles, responsibilities and accountabilities in the RM process coupled with processes, procedures and policies for risk identification, evaluation, treatment and reporting.

Interviewees along with HEIs publicly available risk manuals have reported to have modelled their RM frameworks to the propositions and guidelines of either COSO (2004) or ISO 31000 (2009), which may have impacted positively on the congruence level of HEIs RM models. This level of coherence is obvious in the governance structures amongst others particularly with regards to the three lines of defence (i.e., appointment of RM professionals, risk committees or maintenance of institutional risk registers). However, despite seemingly similarities of RM frameworks among the case institutions, there are noticeable differences in the RM practices as reported by the interviewees from the various HEIs of this study. One of such practices is the process of risk identifying and/reporting (see section 5.4 below).

Roles and responsibilities

As outlined above, there are no noticeable key differences as regards the roles and responsibilities of key risk management staff or committees within the HEIs under study. Thus, there is a similar approach as observed in the case institutions above on the roles and responsibilities across institutions. The generic approach shows that the role of the ‘Court’ is to set the tone of risk management and define the risk appetite of the institution. In other words, the Court influences the risk culture of the institution. ‘The University Executives’ are responsible for directing and ensuring realisation of the Court’s risk management mandates. Furthermore, Heads of Schools, Colleges, Departments or Professional services as the case may be, have the remit to identify and evaluate risk and communicate such to executives or risk committees while also ensuring compliance of the institution’s policies.

Additionally, there is an ‘Audit and Risk committee’ – whose role is to monitor the overall institution’s risk management process and also to advise the court on suitability measures for assessing and managing risk. There is also the ‘Risk management committee’ – responsible for assisting and advising the ‘Audit and Risk committee and by extension the Court, on effective monitoring and application of risk management policies such as: identifying and evaluating major risks that endanger the accomplishment of the institution’s objectives. Also, there is a common trend of risk champions appointed or employed with the remit but not limited to; – facilitate and implement the ‘risk management framework’, support with the analysis of risk at operational level escalate significant risks to the strategic level and assist and advice the institution on risk management.

More so, there is ‘Internal Audit’ with the mandate to regularly and independently review overall risk management process of the institution and report findings to the ‘Audit and Risk committee as well as advise and/make recommendations to ‘Senior Executives’ and ‘Risk Management Committee where necessary. Finally, every ‘Faculty and Staff’ have a crucial responsibility in managing risk. At the very least, every member is expected to be effective in managing risk within their remit as stipulated in the risk management policy of the institution and report to the managers areas of concern particularly risks beyond their scope and authority.

While this is a generic approach across all HEIs, however, there are a few variations as observed among the case HEIs outlined hereunder:

- The role of the Principal/Vice Chancellor in the risk management framework is prevalent only in the Gamma and Zeta Universities. Unlike other HEIs where the Court directly commissions the University Executives to direct and implement the risk policy and culture of the institution, this is slightly different in Gamma and Zeta. The Principals in these institutions act as links between the Court and the Executives. The Court tasks the Principals on their RM strategies who in turn directs the Executive Group of the risk management policies of the Court.
 - However, in Zeta University, the Principal is assisted by the University Secretary in the implementation of risk management procedures while this responsibility is fulfilled by the Chief Operating Officer in Gamma.
- There is a separate line of defence in both Beta and Zeta Universities (Risk Owners) responsible for overseeing key risks. These risk owners are assigned individually to oversee corporate risk and they serve as an additional pair of eyes (oversight) on key risk they are assigned to and ensuring that it is effectively managed and documented. While in Zeta University they report to the Vice Chancellor and the Executive Group, however, in Beta University, they work closely with the Risk Adviser.
- The role of the Risk Manager is very prevalent and influential as they are responsible for coordinating and ensuring the risk management framework effective in mitigating the institution's risk. However, this responsibility is part of the remit of the Chief Operating Officer (COO) at the Gamma University. Unlike other institutions where the Risk Manger reports to the RMG/RMC, the COO in Gamma University is the Chair of the institution's RMG and reports to the Principal.

Risk management process

All of the institutions appeared to have an acceptable level of formalised methodologies guiding their RM framework as highlighted below:

- RM methodologies are well spelt out in their risk manuals as regards the procedures, practices, risk identification, assessment, treatment, reporting, etc.,
- There are varieties of risk identification strategies in place including but not limited to:
 - Bottom-up approach – everyone within the institution is involved in the risk identification process and feeds up any concern to the relevant authority.

- There are feedback loops for communicating specific risk exposures such as strategic or emerging risk to the relevant areas once identified.
- Key Risk indicators are clearly defined in designated operational areas.
- Engage in both qualitative and quantitative risk analysis.
- Utilises a variety of RM tools and technologies to facilitate the RM process, such as: Risk registers, risk map and matrices, RM software, etc., which contribute to the efficiency and effectiveness of processing and reporting of risk data.

However, it was observed in Beta, Gamma and Delta Universities that although there are procedures for the management of specific exposures, however, the risk policy manuals of these HEIs seemed to be outdated and thus, which may result in less effective tools to support the RM process as they are not regularly reviewed and updated.

5.3.2 Maturity and advancement of HEIs risk management models

The researcher also reviewed HEIs RM models in relation to their practices and procedures to evaluate and understand the maturity and advancement of HEIs risk management systems in line with best practices based on the criteria for assessing the degree of risk management as postulated by COSO (2004) and Arena et.al., (2011). The level of assessment of these models is independent of the perceived risk management status by interviewees and the Universities – as contained in their risk management manuals. These criteria are founded on four key considerations:

- RM models are appraised based on the comprehensiveness of the organisation's risk portfolios and how each of these specific risks are prioritised within the portfolio.
- The degree to which RM has been successfully embedded across the institutional hierarchical structure.
- The degree to which RM processes and practices has been successfully integrated within the organisation.
- The assignment of roles and responsibilities of RM functions across the organisation.

Comprehensiveness

The variety of risks being considered by organisations is known as comprehensiveness (Arena et.al, 2011). A comprehensive risk management system would encompass organisational intra

and extra exposures including vital strategic and emergent risks (DeLoach, 2000; Olson and Wu, 2007). According to the interviewees across the HEIs under this study, their risk portfolio comprises of every risk (both new and emerging) the institution is faced with. These risks are recorded using the risk registers maintained at departments, units and schools within the HEIs which ultimately feeds up to the central or institutional risk register. Some institutions in this study have adopted the use of electronic risk registers. Zeta University maintains its risk registers electronically through the University's 'intranet' while Theta University maintains its registers through the institution's 'SharePoint'.

Embeddedness of risk management

The embeddedness of RM within the investigated HEIs were found to be dependent on RM responsibilities and accountabilities across the various units and departments within the institutions. From the respondents' accounts and documented institutional manuals, it was gathered that while RM ownership is spread across various units and departments across HEIs with centralised structure, however, it was more challenging for HEIs with decentralised structure to harmonise the RM system across the decentralised units, departments and schools because operating from a different environment could lead to different risk exposures that would need different and unique measures to manage.

Integration of Risk Management

Evidence from interviews and risk management manuals across case institutions suggests a good level of risk management integration in few of the HEIs under this study (see section 5.4 below). However, approaches and strategies have adopted to ensure a thorough integration of risk management across the various HEIs in this study have been found to be similar – this could be as a result of similar RM frameworks adopted by these institutions. Other than Theta University– whose RM framework is adapted from the International Actuarial Association – IAA, every other institution's RM framework had its root from either ISO 31000 (2009) or COSO (2004). Part of these strategies of ensuring RM integration within these institutions is discussed hereunder:

These Universities' have designed policies and strategies to ensure an effective and a wide-ranging risk management across the institutions. For instance, there is a well-defined communication strategy with clear-cut feedback loops which involves a 'top-bottom' and

'bottom-up' approach of communication. The Universities' Courts set the tone such that they determine the risk appetite and risk tolerance of the institution thereby creating a risk culture within their various establishments. Once this has been established, the Court delegates monitoring and oversight to risk management committees, groups and heads of various schools and units which is actualised by staff members within the University. On the other hand, in the event of actualising these plans, any potential risk encountered is fed back through the relevant channels and to the Court ultimately and such would form part of its decision-making review and also inform its corporate governance report submitted annually to the Scottish Funding Council.

Through the Audit Committee, risk management policies, processes and practice are reviewed annually and when necessary, they make recommendations for changes and/or improvements to the risk management approach of the institution. This ensures that the various institutions' risk management approaches and frameworks is up to date and able to effectively manage or mitigate any existing or new and emerging risk. Also, through the Risk Management Committee, the University is able to maintain and monitor the risk profile of the University and ensure that risks are managed actively and effectively using the right tools and strategies as well as sustaining the risk culture of the institution through creating awareness of general risk across the University. The Committee also ensure that any significant risk that poses threat to the University's goals and objectives is identified, evaluated and documented properly using the Risk Register(s).

Also, every unit within these HEIs have a risk limit and by extension every member of staff. In order words, any significant risk that is above the limit of the unit is documented and escalated to the next level of authority. Therefore, it is the responsibility of Heads of Colleges, Schools and Support groups to ensure that staff within their authority understands their obligations towards risk management and the extent to which they are empowered to take certain risks. Finally, the Risk Manager is saddled with the responsibility of disseminating information to external partners, subsidiary organisations as well as educating every member of staff, about the University's risk management policies.

Although the strategies discussed above is a sound practice to ensure risk management is fully integrated across board, however, this is sadly not the case with some of the HEIs in this study.

For instance, Beta University since 2015, have not carried out an update to their risk management framework and policy manuals although they have a mandate to have them reviewed bi-annually. Also, the Delta University's framework was last updated in 2017 while Gamma University have not carried out an update to its framework for over a decade. The ability for a risk management framework to meet the demands and challenges of the present-day dynamic risk-environment, is vested on dynamism of that risk management framework i.e., the framework must be reviewed and updated frequently (ISO, 2009).

5.4 FINDINGS

Risk management policy guidance of some institutions do not capture all relevant considerations

As a general practice, every organisation's approach to risk management is usually stated in their risk policy as approved by the board. As previously discussed in chapter 2, this should be the essential first step towards the development of an effective risk management process that should not be avoided. Thus, it is essential that for risk management process to be effective, the policy framework should include at minimum, considerations such as: 'policy statement', 'risk appetite', 'risk tolerance', 'internal control and assurance', 'roles and responsibilities', 'monitoring and review', and 'risk strategy' as well as a proper understanding of these by users of the framework. Findings from this study showed that some institutions confuse both risk tolerance and risk appetite or use them interchangeably; while results from the survey of this study indicates that only 44.44% of the population had risk appetite included in their risk management policy, while even fewer 25% only had risk target included.

Some institutions do not regularly update their risk management framework and policy statements

Institutions often state their desire to regularly review and update their risk management policy, this unfortunately has not been the case among many institutions. Gamma-RRM have this to say as regards the review of their institution's risk management framework and policy guidelines, "...as an organisation, I think the system's framework is quite old, so we need to look at that and get the latest version of the risk management guidelines...". It was however observed that only 16.67% of case Universities in this study have actually carried out an up-to-date review of their risk management policy. Not frequently reviewing and updating risk

management framework could lead to serious danger of the framework no longer fit for purpose – as it may no longer be able to control/mitigate new and emerging risk.

However, this overwhelming attitude of neglect or failure by a significant number of HEIs in carrying out regular update of their risk management framework and policy statement tends to mirror the argument of some scholars earlier presented in chapter 2.4.5 of this study that organisations out of compulsion from regulators normally adopt risk management practices and processes as a mere tick in the box or compliance tool without embedding it into the organisation's core business objectives (Arena, et.al, 2010; Esaides, 2013).

Most institutions evaluate risk using probability/impact risk rating matrix

It is common practice for institutions to adopt a risk scoring matrix (i.e., probability multiplied by impact) to enable them measure risk and allow for comparative analysis of key risks. Findings from case Universities in this study revealed that 66.67% of the institutions evaluates risk with the help of a probability/impact rating matrix. There are several classifications of a risk rating matrix – the level of risk matrices could either be a 3x3, 4x4, 5x5 etc., depending on the choice of an organisation. As earlier discussed in chapter 2 of this study, case institutions adopt a risk matrix which they believe work best for their risk management model. However, as discussed in chapter 2.4 of this study, risk rating matrix could be problematic if not fully understood or when applied wrongly as it could lead to some key risks being overlooked or regarded as irrelevant and this may be dangerous to the organisation's risk management efforts.

There is a thin line between excessive control and not enough precaution to risk management

As previously discussed in chapter 2.4 of this research, risk mitigation and control could be seen as any action taken by management and board of an organisation to manage risk and achieve their strategic objectives. The universal and general strategy organisations use to mitigate, and control risk is centred around five approaches namely: 'Accept', 'Transfer', 'Terminate', 'Tolerate', or 'Treat'. This strategy is also common with all the case institutions in this study as they have all directly or indirectly adopted these approaches of risk mitigation and control. All case Universities in this study have reported that excessive risk control could stifle competition and limit the opportunity to achieve their strategic objectives. The major problem, therefore, is striking a balance between excessive risk management as a result of too

much precaution and not enough precaution to risk management which are both dangerous to the institution's strategic objectives.

Deliberations and considerations of institutional risks do not primarily occur at full board meetings

Good practice recommends that senior administrators and board members should be actively engaged in deliberations and considerations as regards institutional risks. Findings from this research revealed that only 31.82% of institutions were currently doing so, whereas 31.82% revealed that these deliberations usually occur primarily in Audit committee meetings and a further 36.36% revealed that such discussions would usually occur primarily at other committee meetings such as: Risk group meetings, Partnership council meetings etc. Therefore, for best practice, considerations for institutional risks should as a responsibility be discussed by full board and every other risk management committee.

Some institutions monitor risk on an ad-hoc basis

Institutions internal and external environment is increasingly becoming dynamic thus creating lots of uncertainties. Therefore, regular and comprehensive monitoring of risk is needed to ensure early detection of new and emerging risk. While it is definitely a welcome development that most (75%) institutions carry out periodic strategic and comprehensive risk assessment to identify major risks to the success of their missions and objectives as findings revealed in this research, however, some institutions (25%) still depend on an ad-hoc basis risk assessment (i.e., as prompted by events). This could be dangerous as not conducting a comprehensive and regular risk assessment could lead to some new or emergent risk not being detected on time. Also, there are some risks that may have low probability and low impact initially but could develop to a high impact risk and if not regularly monitored, this could be catastrophic for the organisation.

Enhancement of decision-making is the overarching objective while HEI's have embraced risk management.

Risk management in Universities' though quite a new phenomenon as compared with public sector organisations started gaining momentum when it became a regulatory mandate for all HEI's by the SFC (see chapter 2.7). However, survey from this study reveals that improving decision-making (21.21%) and strategic planning (21.21%) were the overarching objectives

for HEI's imbibing the culture of risk management as against response to regulatory directive (16.67%) or compliance failure (4.55%). Further analysis and qualitative findings show that majorly, the ancient and civic (or red brick) Universities had adopted and instituted a formal risk management framework as against some of their post-92 counterparts prior to SFC's mandate and presently, HEI's recognise the benefit of risk management to their strategic planning, business continuity and attainment of business objectives.

There is a general increase and acceptance in the organisational placement and position of a risk manager within the HEI sector.

With the adoption and implementation of risk management models and practices within HEI's, staff have either been deployed and trained or risk experts have recently been appointed to oversee and coordinate the risk management process. Previously, the Audit divisions were tasked with overseeing compliance. But with risk management which involves protecting the organisation from uncertainties, HEIs have had to create a new position of risk manager (the title may differ slightly across institutions). These risk managers have a unique reporting line across HEIs – usually directly to the Risk Management Committee (these committees may vary in name depending on institutions) with the remit of not only overseeing the process and in some instances instituting the framework, but also act as a link between the board, management and other staff members as well as creating awareness, organising trainings and retraining of the risk management process.

A summary of this is a quote from Zeta-HRS in this study. *“When I got here maybe 3 or 4 years ago, there was something in place and it wasn't consistent across the University...but we went about putting a one University risk system in place so that everyone is talking in the same language when it comes to risk... It was a new system and I worked with the IT to put it together... and because it was brand new to people, my team and I had a great deal of responsibility talking to people, explaining and training them on what this was all about...”*.

In addition, Alpha-RM also enthused: *“...my position – the position of Risk Manager was created and I'm the first to assume that position. So, I guess there were a number of internal and external audit recommendations that recommended the establishment of a formal Risk Manager position ... to start with, the steps I took was to start with an examination of the risk management measures ... another major recommendation that I was tasked with following up*

on was to ensure that the methodology used across the University for reporting risk was made to be more congruent. It was seriously inconsistent, so I was asked to implement a system that ensured better consistency and reporting across the University.

There is an organised structure for risk management oversight within HEIs

Apart from the risk manager, Universities have constituted committees – already discussed section 5.2 of this study, and part of their remit is to oversee the risk management policy and framework and also to advise the board on matters relating to key risks that may affect the institution’s strategic objectives. These committees (committee names vary slightly across institutions) include – Risk group, Audit and Risk committee, Executive management committee, the Board etc. These committees together with the risk management strategy and policy constitute the risk management framework of the individual Universities. These committees work to ensure there is proper risk management oversight functions and that there is a proper flow of communication (top-down and bottom-up) across board. Apart from these committees, 16.67% of the case institutions further assigned risk owners (discussed in section 6.2 and 6.3 above) to act as additional pair of eyes to every key risk within the institution.

More than half of HEIs use a bespoke framework to manage their risk – a contrast to what is obtained in public and private sector organisations.

The University environment is very unique as compared to corporate organisations (see chapter 2.6 and 2.7), this explains why HEIs adopts a bespoke framework (53.33%) as against other frameworks – ISO 31000 (40%), COSO (6.67%). Among the 40% of HEIs that have opted for the ISO 31000 framework, qualitative findings from this study shows that they have modified it to fit their environment and culture. According to Zeta-HRS, “*we have lined up with standards i.e., the ISO 31000 but not completely aligned to it... but I think it’s more important to find something that works for the University as opposed to standard A says this and we are going to do everything exactly as it says*”. This is a sharp contrast from what is obtained in the corporate industries with COSO more popular in the financial industries while ISO 31000 is popular among non-financial firms (RIMS, 2011). As at the time of writing this report, COSO and ISO 31000 released updated versions of their frameworks (briefly discussed in chapter 2) though it is yet to be seen how organisations would embrace these new versions.

Risk registers

Risk register is key to the management of risk within organisations as it serves as a repository for all risks identified by the establishment. In their day-to-day business, HEIs encourage every unit within the institution to document any risk identified on the risk register. Every risk identified is evaluated and treated accordingly by the relevant authority and any risk above the threshold would be escalated to the next level of authority. Regular review of the risk register is carried out within set time frames as specified in institutions' policy guidance by various committees and this enable HEIs to document and monitor key risks that may threaten their strategic objectives and present such to the board for necessary action. This is a generic process across all case HEIs in this study, however, the approach is slightly different.

Some HEIs have risk registers for departments, schools, projects and a corporate risk register which holds information on corporate risk and other key risks escalated from lower divisions, some maintain just a central or institutional risk register for recording key strategic and operational risks, but have separate registers for individual project risks, while yet, others maintain just a corporate risk register but hold a central system for recording risk on the intranet which is overseen by the risk manager. A key trend that is observed among case Universities, however, is that ancient Universities prefer one central risk register for strategic and operational risks and separate registers for individual project risks, while civic and post-92 Universities preferred to keep a corporate risk register and separate risk registers for every unit or level within the University. It was also observed from the qualitative study that HEIs with decentralised campuses are more inclined to electronic (Sharepoint or Intranet) mode of recording risk within units, departments and schools. The reason for this could be to allow risk managers or risk owners timely access and monitoring of risk events emanating from departments, units or schools (campuses) out of their geographical domain.

Risk management is yet to be fully entrenched into the University-wide governance and decision-making.

While HEIs state that the overarching objective of risk management is to improve their decision-making, findings from this research indicate that this goal has not been fully achieved. However, managers agree that risk management has presented their institution with a more comprehensive view of risk across board while presenting them opportunities to proactively focus on risk that were before now undocumented and unmitigated thus reducing uncertainties.

They also believe that risk management has brought about an increased awareness of risk within the institution and enabled senior management to incorporate risk into strategic discussions and meetings which is gradually guiding their policy making decisions. Thus, there is optimism that these increased awareness and discussions would soon translate into visible positive outcomes such as integration with strategic goals, other planning processes and management practices.

HEIs notwithstanding their category or size, are have a common structure as regards risk management implementation and integration.

At the start of this research, the researcher was eager to ascertain how HEIs differ with their implementation and integration process with the belief that there would be much differences depending on their categories (i.e. ancient, civic and post-92; type, size, research focus and other elements) as with corporate organisations. However, findings from the case Universities in this study have revealed that there is not much difference with the organisation of their risk management models and processes as observed from the qualitative findings of this research and in their policy guidelines and procedures. Though there are slight differences due to their geographical regions and institutional structure, but they all have a common approach in terms of risk management practices such as reporting and monitoring framework and risk culture. The common theme that is eminent among HEIs is their risk reporting structure (Top-down, bottom-up). For instance, as a generic approach, there is usually a ‘Risk management committee’ responsible for day-to-day management of risk and reports to the Audit and Risk Committee – an executive committee of Court, which report to and provide Court with the assurance that risk is being managed effectively.

HEIs with a decentralised structure find it more challenging to manage their risk

Some of the HEIs among the case institutions in this study, have a decentralised geographical structure and findings revealed that their risk management process was much more challenging, and complex compared to others with centralised structures. Because most HEIs tend to use a bespoke risk management framework and modify it to suit their unique culture and environment, therefore, if the risk management framework is geared towards structural rather than geographical based, there could exist a dilemma of environmental and geographical differences because what is unique to one region may be different to the other. However, should the risk management framework be geographical rather than structural, this could lead to complex oversight problems. This is brilliantly captured by Theta-DCG thus: “...our biggest

challenge was really agreeing a consistent approach and getting people to buy-in...because we are dealing with so many different people and places and different systems, it is one of the most difficult thing...it was one of those things I think, where we put two or three steps forward and then one back because somebody would change and they were not aware of the new processes, or they didn't like it ..so, it's quite difficult for us and there's a complex sort of oversight and control mechanism".

Staff sometimes tend to be ambivalent towards risk management and there is always this misconception that risk management is all about downside risk.

Embedding a risk management culture into an institution can be a very daunting task particularly in an HEI environment that has been used to the collegiate style of administration and with some bureaucracies that comes with risk management, it will not be a surprise for some form of resistance to be encountered from certain quarters. Also, people are yet to fully appreciate that risk and the management of risk is not all about negatives; they are often misconstrued to thinking that managing risk is all about safety, financial and insurable risk. This has led staff to actually focus more on the negative impacts of risk while often neglecting opportunities it presents. Qualitative findings from this research show that risk managers are indeed having quite a difficult time creating awareness as regards the importance and benefit of risk management.

According to Gamma-RRM, "... we do try and encourage people to include opportunities, but we don't see it very often than that in the risk register, it tends to be the more negative impacts. ... People are going to say no we don't see risk, we don't want to do that anymore ... we are trying to meet with the people and trying to weigh-in the purpose of doing this because it turns impact on not just the area they are but the entire University. So that's why it's important when I see a new head of department coming-in, I try to get them earlier on to explain the reason for doing these things".

Also, Zeta-HRS have this to say: "...to get people into thinking about it in a slightly more structured formalised approach... and ensure that it has been thought about methodically and here's what we are doing to manage risk and here's what we will do in the future, that takes a little bit of time to get through to people, sometimes people are very busy and it's an ongoing challenge. I think for risk management to be reviewed actively regarding the use by people as

decision-making aid and which ultimately it is – as opposed to here comes the risk manager again chasing me for risk reviews ...”.

However, there are suggestions that the attitude or ambivalence shown by some staff towards the risk management process may also be as a result of the drivers of the process. This reflects the argument by Lin et. al., (2012) earlier presented in chapter 2 of this study that RM with all its accrued benefits “*when blindly following the wave of ERM adoption, managers are likely to underestimate the difficulty and cost of initiating and maintaining ERM programs or overestimate their own abilities to coordinate and aggregate various IRMs and risks*”. (p.12). And according to the authors such could result in a further bureaucratic process and become counter-productive if applied wrongly. Buttressing this point, Henry (2007) stressed that such bureaucracies usually result from red tapes that the framework presents, resulting in unnecessary cataloguing of events which leads to neglect of some major activities and other pitfalls that could impact negatively on the organisation.

Uncertainties regarding Brexit affecting HEIs strategic planning, administration and implementation programs.

With the uncertainties about Brexit still lingering on and with no clear roadmap at the moment, HEIs are faced with challenges regarding the unknown as they are finding it increasingly difficult carrying out medium to long term administrative and strategic plans; and implementation regarding student recruitment because students are either thought to be customers, products or citizens or a combination of these (depending on which spectrum one look at it from) and this is having a knock-on effect on other areas and activities of the institutions.

Put succinctly, Delta-PORA have this to say: “*Another big challenge Universities have is the uncertainty over the status of students and actually, overall uncertainty of UK leaving the EU and what’s going to be happening there. It makes it very difficult for us to plan student’s populations and to plan recruitment and that type, because we simply don’t know what the status of EU students would be, and we don’t know how we would be linking European research framework as well... In any uncertainty going forward, it makes quite difficult to plan and part of the reason Universities exist is to recruit students and to provide students with supported*

learning experience... and that become an increasing challenge when policies going forward are uncertain.”

Also, Zeta-HRS adds that; *“UK leaving the EU by the look of it is potentially going to have a big impact across the sector..., but also as other Universities maybe adjust the way they operate slightly to deal with the uncertainties of leaving the EU, that then changes the position we are in because everyone does something slightly different... other risks around us generally, some of this ties into the potential of leaving the EU as around attracting students and around the University’s reputation, ranking and various league table and other various things can affect our success of attracting students to come to this institution.”*

Institutions focus more attention on financial, strategic and reputational risks

Habitually, financial risk usually receives more attention from HEIs than any other risk category (strategic, financial, operational, compliance and reputational). The survey result showed that HEI board members are more concerned about financial, strategic and reputational risks than any other type of risk. While financial, strategic and reputational risks are no doubt definitely a threat to all institutions, other types of risk notwithstanding, also have potential negative effect as much as financial risks to the strategic objectives of institutions if not monitored and mitigated.

There is an increased level of confidence from stakeholders on HEIs brought about by risk management

With globalisation and increased uncertainties surrounding both the internal and external environment, all organisations routinely encounter risk. The only way for organisations to completely avoid risk is when they cease to operate. The level and nature of risks faced by HEIs is becoming more and more dynamic and through a carefully planned risk management process, institutions are able to map out key challenges and uncertainties threatening their strategic mission and objectives and able to design and implement controls to mitigate any key risks. This has brought about increased levels of assurance and confidence to the board, senior management and other stakeholders.

Risk assessment and risk evaluation enable boards and management executives to make better strategic decisions

Results from this study revealed that 87.5% of respondents that took part in the survey admitted to the fact that the key drivers responsible for their institutions' risk management adoption were majorly to improve decision-making and strategic planning. This contradicts with claims raised in chapter 2.4.5 by some critics that organisations merely adopt risk management as a mere compliance tool or an internal control event with no meaningful impact on the organisation's objectives. However, findings from this research reveal that boards and senior executives through effective risk reporting and risk management practices such as risk assessment, evaluation and monitoring, are able to have a greater understanding and analysis of their strategic planning and a better knowledge of the actual impact of their decisions.

Risk management process have enabled HEIs to quickly detect potential risks and the ability to forestall its impact

Risk management have provided HEIs needed tools – to detect new and emerging risks that may have threatened the achievement of their strategic goals and objectives and enabled them map out control strategies to effectively prevent or mitigate their impact. It has also helped to eliminate any duplicate measures or controls that would have necessarily been in place in areas of inconsequential risk impacts. Thus, it has helped HEIs to effectively focus their resources on key or top-priority risks thereby making up for resources being used effectively and value creation.

Through effective risk management, HEIs are able to detect opportunities and take measured risks

As part of an effective risk management framework, HEIs usually define their risk appetite and this have enabled HEIs to envisage planned developmental areas and giving management and staff the assurance to take more calculated risk in areas that would yield significant results. Institutions have always stated in their policy statement the need to take calculated risk when there is an opportunity to do so thus, risk management is not all about managing negative effects but rather detecting opportunities and supporting innovation and encouraging such users.

HEIs engaging in more partnerships and internationalisation

Another fundamental finding from this study that cannot be ignored is collaborations and internationalisation. Internationalisation is often referred to as “*the process of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of post-secondary education.*” (Knight 2004, p.11). Universities in the UK although are notably famous for their cutting-edge academic and research prowess, however, world leading researchers are not exclusive to the UK. Thus, international partnership is fundamental to the sustained success and the advancement of the UK’s academic, research and innovative sector.

Evidence from this study suggest that HEIs are seeking to take opportunities of internationalisation and partnerships in order to either maintain or have a global reach and according to Gamma-RRM, “*there is a line between the risk appetite which ties with the fact that...the University, we want to be global, so it ties with that and we want to make our risk appetite to align with this strategy and integrate it with the risk management framework*”. Internationalisation is shaping the goals, objectives and strategies of HEIs not just in the UK but across the globe as it has contributed significantly to the economic growth and social development to the UK.

5.4.1 Summary of Key Findings

A summary of key findings of this research as it relates to the research objectives are highlighted below based on unique identifiers or key themes (discussed in chapter 3.8.2 and chapter 6.3.1). These key themes – ‘Policies and procedures of risk management’, ‘Attitudes and approaches towards institutional risk management’ and ‘strategies to manage institutional risk’, ensured the researcher have been able to successfully integrate both phases (quantitative and qualitative) of this research for a greater comprehension and clarity. Thus, the following highlights a summary of some key findings of this study which is the foundation and bedrock for the recommendations in the concluding part of this study (Chapter 6).

Policies and Procedures of Risk Management

- Risk management policy guidance of some institutions do not capture all relevant considerations

- Some institutions do not regularly update their risk management framework and policy statements
- Deliberations and considerations of institutional risks do not primarily occur at full board meetings
- Some institutions monitor risk on an ad-hoc basis
- Risk management is yet to be fully entrenched into the University-wide governance and decision-making.
- HEIs notwithstanding their category or size, have a common structure as regards risk management implementation and integration.
- Institutions focus more attention on financial, strategic and reputational risks

Attitudes and Approach Towards Institutional Risk Management

- Most institutions evaluate risk using probability/impact risk rating matrix
- There is a thin line between excessive control and too much precaution to risk management.
- There is a general increase and acceptance in the organisational placement and position of a risk manager within the HEI sector.
- There is an organised structure for risk management oversight within HEIs
- More than half of HEIs use a bespoke framework to manage their risk – a contrast to what is obtained in public and private sector organisations.

Strategies to Manage Institutional Risk

- Enhancement of decision-making is the overarching objective while HEI's have embraced risk management.
- Staff sometimes tend to be ambivalent towards risk management and there is always this misconception that risk management is all about downside risk.
- Uncertainties regarding Brexit affecting HEIs strategic planning, administration and implementation programs.
- There is an increased level of confidence from stakeholders on HEIs brought about by risk management
- Risk assessment and risk evaluation enable boards and management executives to make better strategic decisions

- Risk management process have enabled HEIs to quickly detect potential risks and the ability to forestall its impact
- Through effective risk management, HEIs are able to take detect opportunities and take measured risks

5.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter is built on the results and analysis from the quantitative study (Chapter 4) as well as on the findings from the qualitative phase of this research as presented above in the context based on the theoretical models and academic literature guiding this research. These findings ensured the researcher had been able to fully comprehend HEIs risk management framework and thereby pointing the reader's attention towards concerns observed and putting forward useful recommendations (chapter 6) which should be considered when designing and implementing HEIs risk management systems.

The analysis and discussion presented in this chapter revealed some key varied systematic practices of HEIs risk management systems despite being guided by common risk management standards. These variations as well as similarities in the HEIs risk management frameworks were discussed while also the configurations of individual HEI risk management framework were critically analysed based on their risk document manuals and interviewees' accounts. Finally, discussed in this chapter, is maturity and roles of the varied HEIs risk management frameworks. The next chapter is the concluding chapter of this study and it reviewed the research questions – to ensure that they have been successfully addressed, while recommendations have also been made based on findings of this research, the next chapter also discusses the study's contribution to stakeholders as well as implication of the study beyond Scottish Universities.

6.0 CONCLUSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This study aimed to critically assess the impact and effects of risk management on the structures and practices of Higher Institutions on Scottish HEIs. This research considering the under-explored field of risk management in HEIs, was founded on a critical review of literature and mixed-methods research therefore revealing some shortcomings of HEIs risk management frameworks and thus making needful recommendations for more comprehensive and dynamic risk management practices. This study also fulfilled the growing need for organisational risk management studies (Power, 2009; Gephart, et.al., 2009), adopting and implementing a more comprehensive methodology to organisational risk management practices while also considering risk management within a wider cultural framework as well as investigating the organisational setting of risk management (Lounsbury, 2008; Mikes, 2009).

In order to accomplish the aim and objectives of this research (see chapters 1.3 and 3.1), the researcher critically reviewed a wide range of academic literature and industry publications on HEIs risk management while the sequential mixed-methods research was employed to investigate the risk management frameworks across HEIs. The first phase of the study (quantitative) conducted across all Scottish (sixteen) HEIs evaluated the structures and practices of risk management within the HEI context (objective 1), vital for selecting case Universities and participants for the qualitative phase, essential for the construct of the semi-structured interviews as well as informed, built on and served as a bedrock on which the qualitative phase rests. Thus, six HEIs from the sample were selected as case studies in the phase 2 of this research which enabled the researcher to holistically examine HEIs risk management frameworks and the alignment of these models to their overall strategic business contexts (objectives 2 and 3). Thus, this approach enhanced validity, credibility and further assisted in data triangulation.

In this final chapter however the research questions guiding this research were revisited and thus discussions around the findings have also been presented. It also presents the limitations to the study and identified areas for further research as well as discussions on the originality, contribution to knowledge, and implication of the study to stakeholders.

6.2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS REVISITED

This study was guided by a set of research questions which are readdressed in this section in conjunction with the key empirical findings to demonstrate its relationship and contribution to how the research questions have been addressed.

RQ1: How do HEIs structure and execute their risk management functions?

The first research question focused on the features of risk management within the HEI context and factors that influence the risk management systems of HEIs. Chapter 2 of this research provided an understanding into the operating environments within the HEI context and critical analysis of literature as regards some considerations influencing the implementation and adoption of risk management in HEIs. Chapters 4 and 5 however, presented analysis and empirical findings of the driving factors regarding risk management adoption and implementation in HEIs. An examination of both technical and institutional determinants of risk management structures and practices was carried out using contingency and institutional approaches within the internal as and external environments of HEIs.

The empirical analysis regarding the HEIs risk management frameworks presented how the key components of the risk management architecture have been developed to aid the management of every strategic risk that may be encountered while at the same time, regular reviews of this risk management framework is said to be performed to guarantee maximum assurance though it was found out that some of the HEIs were guilty of not conducting regular reviews of their risk management architecture despite this being clearly stated in their risk management manuals. The study suggested that there were no noticeable differences on the formalisation levels of HEIs RM systems irrespective of the size, structure, date of establishment or complexity. Thus, the study evidenced HEIs in this research to have modelled their RM frameworks to the propositions and guidelines of either COSO (2004) or ISO 31000 (2009), which may have impacted positively on the congruence level of HEIs RM models.

Consistent with past studies, this research found that effective risk management framework is majorly dependent on risk management cultures and the level of integration of risk management principles and practices as against formal rules or bureaucracies to managing risk within the institution. Also, it was also observed that a generic approach in the structure of key roles and responsibilities in the coordination of risk management activities within the HEIs

except for only a few minor variations. However, this study finds that HEIs with a decentralised structure may find the risk management process more challenging. Furthermore, it was evidenced from this study that HEIs with the adoption and implementation of risk management systems, institutions have had to create a new role of a ‘risk manager’ to coordinate the risk management process and ensure compliance.

RQ2: How do the different institutional and technical factors influence the adoption and implementation of HEIs risk management frameworks?

This research question focused on the dynamics, structures and practices of HEIs risk management systems. Thus, to address this question, Chapters 2, 4 and 5 reviewed and evaluated the risk management structures and practices within the HEI setting. The empirical study as it relates to this objective and research question analysed the risk management systems, culture, rules and routines of the various institutions within the context of the study, thus demonstrating both their internal and external qualities in a bid to evaluate how these factors contribute and influence the risk management culture and attitudes in HEIs.

Evidenced in this research was that regulatory authorities and HEIs institutional environments exerts pressures on institutions as regards efficiency and legitimacy. This research documented how a combination of several factors – institutional and regulatory, coercive, mimetic normative pressures etc. (see chapter 4.2.1), influence the choice, adoption and implementation of HEIs risk management frameworks. These institutional and contingency pressures and factors were found in this study to influence the adoption, modification and implementation of risk management practices and framework in HEIs. Thus, in line with the proposals of structural contingency theory, the study highlighted how HEIs adapted their risk management frameworks, structures and practises to conform with various drivers of RM such as: regulatory, technical, internal and external environments and pressures.

This therefore reveals that based on several regulators demanding compliance and also with their several risk exposures from both their internal and external environments, HEIs have majorly had to design a bespoke risk management system that conforms to all their risk exposures within their internal and external environments while at the same time complying with the various regulators’ demands. However, this research recommends the need for a

further research into a unique and an ideal risk management framework for HEIs to assist in ensuring efficiency and legitimacy across the HEI context.

RQ 3: What are the impact and effects of risk management in HEIs?

The assessment of HEIs risk management architecture was the focus of the third research question. Chapter 2 of this study provided preliminary insights into this discourse, while chapters 4 and 5 provided discourse on the empirical research into the assessment and evaluations of the HEIs risk management architectures in order to conceptualise the implications of risk management in HEIs.

In order to fully understand the implications of risk management in HEIs this study assessed the maturity and advancement of the risk management architecture in line with best practices based on the criteria for assessing the degree of risk management systems in organisations such as comprehensiveness of the organisation's risk portfolio, the degree of risk management embeddedness within the organisational structures and the degree of integration of the risk management architecture (see chapter 5.3) within the institution as well as the roles and responsibilities of key actors of the risk management framework.

Thus, this assessment revealed several generic implications of risk management across the HEIs involved in this study. HEIs are increasingly under pressure to meet the needs of their several regulators and other stakeholders. An example of such is the 'Universities Single Outcome Agreement' – (see chapter 2). The study evidenced that effective risk management can enable institutions to make better strategic decisions, achieve their objectives and comply with regulatory as well as stakeholders' needs. The study also evidenced that risk management has brought about better strategic planning, ensured that HEIs are able to detect early warnings from potential risk and put in place measures to eliminate such or reduce its potential impact. It has also enabled them to seek out opportunities and take measured and calculated risks thereby creating an enabling environment to become more innovative and these have been found to have increased the level of confidence of stakeholders.

However, the study did not find much negative impact of risk management on HEIs except there were indications from the study which highlights that as a result of some bureaucracies occasioned by practices and procedures of managing risk, staff sometimes tend to show

ambivalence towards the risk management process which if left unchecked could be detrimental to the entire process. While risk management had played a pivotal role towards ensuring HEIs are able to demonstrate compliance and legitimacy for regulators and stakeholders as well as enhancement of decision making, increased level of confidence from stakeholders and providing a global reach, there are concerns though that uncertainties surrounding 'Brexit' which has affected most industries are beginning to affect strategic planning and implementation process within the HEI context.

RQ 4: How can HEIs advance and align their risk management architecture to better suit the needs of their business contexts?

As referenced above, HEIs have various regulators exerting influence and authority over them with several obligations and requirements to fulfil. Chapters 4, and 5 of this study analysed and discussed application of various risk management practices and processes appropriate for organisation-wide risk typologies. But considering the unique environment Universities operate in, and the multiplicity of institutional and technical (sometimes diverging) requirements from regulators and stakeholders, thus, this study conveyed that these factors needs consideration in the design and modelling of the HEI risk management architecture as against the generic frameworks designed for other public and private organisations which HEIs have adopted. Although, HEIs in this study all reported to have fashioned these frameworks to their specific needs, but there is a different risk culture in HEIs generally, therefore, there is need for a risk management system designed specifically for the academic environment.

From a quantitative survey of 16 universities and a further qualitative survey of 6 universities, this study conducted analysis of varied methods along the spectrum of the maturity and advancement of risk management. The empirical findings brought to limelight the bedrock for the identification of key features of effective risk management in HEIs. Therefore, responding to this research question, the researcher is confident that empirical findings from this study would guide the design of the development of a risk management system that would meet the specific needs of HEIs as discussed above.

6.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings from this research revealed some concerns in the risk management system of HEIs that would need to be addressed for it to effectively achieve its objectives. While these concerns

have been discussed, it is essential that this research also provide recommendations to address these concerns. Therefore, the following paragraphs below are suggestions researched from a wide spectrum of both academic literature and professional bodies.

There should be a broad and comprehensive characterisation of risk

While there is no generally accepted risk definition, risk measurement is even more controversial. Risk should not only be quantified monetarily but rather all risk consequences must be considered. Consider a lawsuit over tenure denial as an example, although there are some financial implications, but more damaging effects would be the non-monetary consequences such as: negative publicity, productivity losses, distraction from mission etc. Therefore, it is essential to consider the total cost of risks. Also, it is traditional that insurable financial risks usually receive more attention by institutions, although not every risk can be captured, HEIs must endeavour to broaden their scope of risk identification capturing financial, project, strategic, compliance, operational and reputational risks (see chapter 2.8).

HEIs ought to continuously monitor their internal and external environment

Regular changes and uncertainties within the internal and external environment expose institutions to greater risks. Thus, there is need for HEIs to have a full knowledge of both its internal and external risks. Boards and top-level management need to frequently review and ask questions (at least once a year) regarding any downside risk or opportunities they might be missing out on. While setting strategic goals and objectives for the institution, they should as well prepare for the worst and consider extreme uncertainties – an unexpected significant change to the economic climate, closure of campus for at least a year due to natural disasters, terrorism, changes to regulation and/or funding by regulatory authorities etc. These events though have a significantly low probability of occurrence, but the magnitude of impact is great. Therefore, regular horizon scanning (chapter 2.9) should be carried out in order to detect emerging or risks that may have been previously unidentified.

HEIs should encourage inclusiveness and buy-in of risk management among all levels of staff within the institution

For risk management to be successful in any organisation, there has to be a culture where everyone within the establishment does not only have an awareness of the risk policies and objectives but must also be in agreement and work towards delivering the set objectives.

Boards and top-level management rarely notice the initial warning signals of risk but rather employees with less or without fancy titles on several occasions would be the first to identify major risks (for instance, ‘a student being unruly to fellow students, buildings developing mould or mildew problems, or security flaws to a donor database’ etc.) to the institution. Therefore, for an all-inclusive risk management framework, there is need for everyone within the institution to be involved. To encourage buy-in, HEIs need to regularly provide awareness training (relevant to their employee roles and also ensure their job description includes references to risk management) on risk management to staff. Doing this would help foster a culture of risk identification and evaluation at all levels across the institution and also give assurance of early detection and escalation of critical risks to top-level management.

HEIs should ensure that the designated risk owner’s responsibility does not conflict with the general management team

As common with corporate organisations, designating or appointing a risk owner is gaining more popularity within the HEI sector. While appointing a risk owner or risk manager as the case may be, is an excellent way in driving the risk management process forward – because risk champions help to coordinate the institution’s risk management framework and ensure regular improvement. However, institutions should ensure that the responsibility of the risk champion does not overlap with that of the entire risk management team. Normally, it is the responsibility of the University’s audit committee (or similar) to ensure assurance over the effectiveness and competence of the risk management framework while strategic oversight responsibilities rest with the board. Therefore, the position of risk owners should be more of process driven rather than compliance driven.

HEIs need to strike a balance between risk taking and risk avoidance

Every organisation is routinely surrounded by uncertainties and organisations cannot avoid risk taking except it ceases to operate. Most HEIs have categorically stated in their policy statement the need to take measured risk even if outside their risk appetite should such an opportunity arise. While it is brilliant to recognise opportunities and downside risk, care should be taken since most rewarding opportunities usually involve high risk. Thus, there is need to strike a balance between risk taking and risk avoidance. HEIs should also note that excessive control over and above its set risk appetite may lead to an ineffective and unproductive risk management and could amount to excessively complex procedures or bureaucratic process for

staff and thereby may result in control failure. As previously discussed above, HEIs need to regularly train and retrain employees to obtain their buy-in and also to enable them to identify and successfully report risk events – both downside risk and opportunities.

HEIs – depending on the adopted risk scoring matrix, should provide detailed guidance on the scoring technique applied within the matrix

Risk scoring matrix is popular among organisations to evaluate identified risk and make decisions. As already discussed in chapter 2.4.4.4 and in chapter 5.4 of this study, risk scoring matrix may lead to a situation of key risk being overlooked or undervalued if applied wrongly. Therefore, decision-makers and the board need to deliberate and conduct a critical assessment on the type of matrix to be adopted and how it should be applied in order to ensure it captures a full representation of their policy. This would entail considering the potency of the matrix adopted to the overall risk management process and the ease of its application by staff. Thus, HEIs should ensure that there is optimum level of knowledge and understanding by staff and depending on the risk matrix adopted, detailed guidance on the scoring techniques within the matrix should be provided in order to ensure that risk is being categorised effectively.

Senior administrators and Board members ought to engage in active deliberations as regards institutional risks

For best practice and commitment to the risk management process, institutional risk management should be a priority for board and senior administrators while discussions and considerations regarding such should occur at full board meetings and at every risk committee meeting within the institution. Also, boards and senior executive need to monitor risks that could hinder the institution's strategic goals. They should set priorities for top-risks and decide based on risk their tolerance level, decide what need urgent attention at the top level. More so, to ensure that administrators remain committed and stay focused, the board should always encourage them to produce annual reports on top-priority risk that are being monitored; such reports also provide boards and management executives additional information on development, progress or changes to such risks.

Develop a culture and a disciplined process of regular monitoring of risk

Developing a risk management framework is part of the initial step and part of the solution to an effective risk management process but not entirely the solution. Institutions need to adopt a

culture and a disciplined process of regular risk monitoring to guarantee that key risk critical to achieving their goals and objectives are identified and escalated to strategic level discussions by board and senior management. Monitoring risks on an ad-hoc basis – as prompted by events is best seen as a reactive measure. Thus, there should be a culture of routine risk assessment to identify any new and emerging risk for immediate action.

HEIs need a regular review of their control framework in order to always have the assurance that it is fit for purpose

HEIs would usually need to determine and identify an effective control strategy to enable them to successfully manage their risk. This strategy is considered to be any action or combination of actions taken by management and board to enable them to mitigate or control their potential risk in order to achieve their objectives and such controls include policies and procedures ranging from authorisation, detective, preventive etc. (For instance, physical and/or logical restrictions of access to IT systems, segregation of duty and delegating authority, performance management etc.). Once these controls have been put in place, management should regularly review this strategy and control mechanism and once perceived not to be in line with the institution's risk appetite, necessary action must be taken to ensure that it does not lead to a situation of counter-productivity where staff may begin to circumvent these controls as a result of an excessive set of bureaucratic controls.

Also, captured in chapter 2 of this study are updated versions of COSO and ISO 31000 risk management frameworks. Although this research is suggesting the design of a tailored risk management framework for HEIs (which realistically would take quite some time to come up with), however, in the absence of that, it would be essential for HEIs to also update their frameworks in line with the updated versions of their parent's risk management frameworks in order to be effective and fit-for-purpose.

There should be a risk management architecture to suit the unique and specific needs of HEIs

As discussed earlier in this study, HEIs operate in a very unique environment and have a unique culture different from any other public or private organisation. More so, HEIs across Scotland as well as the entirety of UK are subject to the control of several regulators demanding multiplicity of institutional and technical (albeit diverging and sometimes contrasting) requirements. Therefore, findings and discussions from this empirical research brought to light

the need for a tailored risk management framework for HEIs. Thus, this research provides the foundation for the identification of key features of effective risk management in HEIs. Therefore, the researcher is confident that empirical findings from this study would guide the design of a development of a risk management system that would meet the specific needs of HEIs as discussed above.

HEIs should ensure a holistic management of every key risk within their environment

Findings from this research acknowledged that most HEIs and their board members focus more attention towards managing and deliberate more on financial, strategic and reputational risk than other risk types such as operational, compliance, legal etc. While these risks (financial, strategic and reputational) are no doubt very important and seen as key risks in every organisation, it should be noted however that every potential risk in any organisation could be detrimental if not given attention. As previously discussed in chapter 5 of this research, some initial low risk left unchecked may have the capacity to develop into high risks with serious consequences which could have negative implications to the reputation of that organisation. HEIs pride themselves through their status and reputation, therefore, it is important that there is a holistic management and focus on every identified or potential risk within and around the HEIs environment.

HEIs should ensure that risk management becomes a vital and fundamental part of the institutions' operational, corporate strategy and decision-making activities

Risk management is only adjudged to be fully embedded into an organisation's culture when it becomes an intrinsic and a vital part of the operational, decision-making and corporate strategies of that establishment. A well-designed risk management framework that is unique to structure and environment of an institution is the first step to a successful approach of embedding risk management into an institution's culture. When a risk management framework is unique to an institution, it would require less intervention from management and could easily be aligned to the institution's operational activities and corporate strategies. However, despite its uniqueness to an institution, the risk management framework and the entire risk management process should be regularly reviewed and updated or refined to ensure its effectiveness since risk as well as the university's internal and external environments are dynamic.

Other techniques according to PKF (2011) that may be useful to ensure that risk management becomes wholly embedded into an institution include but not limited to:

- *“Providing risk management awareness training to staff, relevant to their roles,*
- *Including reference to risk management within job descriptions,*
- *Explicitly minuting discussions held during management team meetings,*
- *Linking governing body agenda items and papers to institution’s strategic risks”*

Source: (PKF, 2011: p.24).

The above points are useful and would act as guide to a successful integration of a risk management framework. Fundamental to the success of a well-integrated risk management lies in adopting a framework that is unique to an institution’s environment and structure and ensuring that there is buy-in, awareness and understanding of the entire risk management process. When a risk management framework is fully entrenched, it allows institutions to anticipate and successfully plan for uncertainties. Thus, having a robust and resilient risk management framework does not necessarily entail an effective risk management process and practice. For risk management to be successful, considerations such as perceptions, attitudes and behaviours of the persons involved and their reaction to risk is relevant. Therefore, it is safe to say that for risk management to be successfully embedded, there must be a total commitment from everyone involved (top – bottom) in the process coupled with adoption of the right approach.

Create a wider cross-functional Risk Management Group/Committee

The Risk Management Group or Committee (depending on what it is called by various institutions) is the internal group that reports to and advises the Audit and Risk Committee who in turn advises the Court. This committee is typically drawn from senior executives across various key unit within the institution. These units may include the Vice Principal, (often VP Governance), senior staff from finance, risk management, legal, IT, internal audit or compliance etc. The remit of this group is to provide a wide-ranging discussion and assessment of current and potential risk across the institution. Thus, the primary oversight function of risk management activities across the institution is vested on this committee. Therefore, this research recommends wider inclusion from every unit or department (such as student affairs, human resources, legal unit etc.).

A key advantage of a wider inclusion in the Risk Management Committee is that it brings together people with comprehensive and practical knowledge of specific risks with policy and decision makers in order to foster and encourage effective communication and feedbacks and allows synergy between every unit and staff as they cooperate to mitigate risks to the advantage of the institution.

HEIs should develop and encourage a common risk language

When there is a common risk vocabulary across campus, it promotes and fosters creativity and risk culture, sharing in the management of risk and more so guide the risk identification and management process. Staff and executives in different offices and disciplines or even in different campus may have a different view of risk. For instance, the President/Vice Chancellor may view risk in relation to the university's reputation and donor support while an officer from finance unit may be concerned with investment and cash flow risks. Compliance risk would be the focus of internal audit whereas a traditionally focused risk manager would be pre-occupied with eliminating hazards risks.

Thus, it is recommended that management encourage a common risk language developed by the risk manager or the risk management committee in order to foster a mutual understanding of terminologies that describe the risk management process. These terminologies along with definitions would need to conform with the risk culture of the institution and ensure vocabularies are unique across the institution. An example could be the acronym 'ERM' which could mean 'Enterprise Risk Management' to a risk manager or 'Electronic Records Management to the Librarian. Therefore, it would help to harmonise these vocabularies across the university.

A proactive approach across the sector, at both an individual and institutional level, will allow institutions to realise the benefits of diverse international research collaboration. The ability of the higher education sector to provide greater assurance on the security of its international research collaborations, will have a positive impact on the prosperity and security of the UK.

HEIs should develop strategies to mitigate possible threats from internationalisation and partnerships.

As previously discussed in chapter 5.4, there is a growing trend of internationalisation and partnerships among HEIs in the UK and world over in order to have a global presence. Although the UK educational sector has in the past effectively managed risks associated with internationalisation and partnerships, however, these risks are becoming more dynamic and complex. These risks can range from but not limited to intellectual property and data theft, safety and security within and around university campuses, threats to academic freedom, freedom of speech and autonomy of the institution.

While majority of these risks are not new to HEIs, however, with growing risk complexities and dynamism across the globe, there is need to be proactive in ensuring effective risk management and governance in order for HEIs to protect stakeholders (i.e., students, staff partners etc.) from the consequences of legal, financial and reputational related risks. Therefore, this study recommends the following:

Need to protect reputation and values

The risk exposure of HEIs is unique and depends on several factors. It is dynamic and dependent on environmental changes. Thus, establishing security-related risk management is essential for HEIs which should include policies and processes alignment with the risk profile of the institution, encourage and empower individuals to detect and report security-related threats, continuous review to the risk management architecture to ensure its appropriateness.

Therefore, HEIs should ensure prospective and current partners are made aware of their obligation to freedom of speech, academic freedom and the consequences working in partnerships and they should also continuously review and improve policies and legal agreements on academic freedom and freedom of speech. More so, there should be a process and a sustainable culture in place that should encourage staff raise concerns regarding current or potential collaborations with partners.

Need to Protect Stakeholders

HEIs in the UK operate in a diverse, dynamic and multi-culturally diverse setting – bringing together students, staff and visitors from across the world all year round. HEIs often provide

communal and open spaces to visitors as part of their civic role in supporting communities. Therefore, it is essential that institutions develop strategies to educate visitors on data usage policies as well as strategies to protect their assets and cybersecurity. More so, recent months due to Covid-19 have seen teaching being delivered online – this has presented new risks the personal data of staff and students alike – this is more reason for HEIs to continuously monitor and review their data protection policies and implement effective strategies to safeguard against hackers and data breach.

Finally, with the increase in globalisation among HEIs, it is expected that there would be increase in unsolicited attempts to inappropriately gain access to research and other intellectual properties. Therefore, HEIs map out strategies to mitigate these threats and ensure that proper checks are carried out on all foreign partners, implement policies and contractual agreements to protect intellectual properties and ensure compliance with legislations and other legal obligations regarding export control. Ensuring a proactive approach across board (within the internal and external environments) would ensure that HEIs are able to harvest the benefits accrued from internationalisation and collaborations. This will depend on the ability for HEIs to provide credible assurance on the security of their international research collaborations.

Keep the process going

It should be noted that risk management is not a one-off venture. A successful and effective risk management practice is by nature a cyclical process and therefore, boards and senior administrators must continuously and regularly be involved in the cycle of ‘identifying’, ‘assessing’, ‘evaluating and re-evaluating’, ‘monitoring’ and ‘treating’ key risks (see chapter 2.4.4) while also at the same time reviewing and continuously improving the risk management process and framework for effective results. Just as risk is dynamic, the risk management approach must also be dynamic.

6.3.1 Summary of Recommendations Based on Key Themes (Unique Identifiers)

As earlier discussed in chapters 4 and 5 of this study, the objectives of this research were founded on some vital considerations – Overarching themes or unique identifiers (see chapter 3.8) which are: ‘Policies and Procedures of Risk Management’, Attitudes and Approach Towards Institutional Risk Management’ and Strategies to Manage Institutional Risk’. Based on these key themes, the researcher was able to simplify or integrate the findings (both

quantitative and qualitative) of the research to achievement of specific research objectives for greater understanding and clarity. Recommendations from above are highlights of key findings which have been presented as a summary under these considerations.

Policies and Procedures of Risk Management

Institutions are expected as a matter of policy and general practice to capture in their risk management policy guidelines, their risk management philosophy and approach which should capture as a minimum, considerations such as: ‘policy statement’, ‘risk appetite’, ‘risk tolerance’, ‘internal control and assurance’, ‘roles and responsibilities’, ‘monitoring and review’, and ‘risk strategy’. Also, institutions should always remember that aside financial, strategic and reputational risks, other risks such as operational, regulatory, legal and political are also quite important and should equally merit significant recognition, consideration and discussion at board meetings. Furthermore, boards and senior management should ensure a sound structure of reporting lines to allow for easy communication, escalation and monitoring of key institutional risk and boards and senior executives should always demand regular updates on major risks and efforts taken to control them.

Attitudes and Approach Towards Institutional Risk Management

There should be knowledge and understanding of the risk appetite and risk tolerance of the institution and should be relevant to the decision-making culture of the institution. Also, strategic and operational decisions should be guided by the institution’s risk tolerance. For these attitudes to be fully entrenched into the culture of the institution, the board and top-level management (tone from the top) need to be at the forefront to impact the change because to achieve best results, there must be an inclusive process. Another excellent way this could be achieved would be through a thorough risk assessment which presents a good opportunity to educate and create awareness on risk management.

Strategies to Manage Institutional Risk

There should be a regular comprehensive assessment and consideration of risk by board members and senior executives to enable them to evaluate the probability and impact of events (expected and unexpected) before making strategic decisions; and in making such decisions, careful thought and appraisal should be given to any strategy (‘accept’, ‘avoid’, ‘mitigate’, ‘share’, etc.) to ensure that any adopted strategy is effective for the risk event. Also, the board

and senior executives need to regularly and proactively ensure that control measures are in place for new and emerging key institutional risks and they are also expected to regularly monitor and review the entire risk management process to guarantee its effectiveness. Finally, to guarantee inclusiveness and buy-in from everyone within the institution, there should always be an awareness campaign through every available channel such as – trainings, focus group discussions, team meetings, bills and posters in strategic locations, etc. – and also, regular feedback should be obtained from staff to gauge their feelings towards the entire risk management process.

6.3.2 Practical Implications of Risk Management in HEIs

Effective risk management ensures that institutions are able to achieve their strategic objectives and make them creative in seeking more opportunities. A key attribute of risk management rest on the fact that it is a good business practice and according to Gallagher (1999), an effective risk management practice presents and guarantees institutions the following:

- A well protected and sound reputation
- Successful opportunities
- Disaster management and business continuity in the event of a catastrophe
- General improvement of campus life and operations within the institution

However, effective risk management is not instantaneous. Sometimes, developing passion for the risk management process alone could lead to a positive institution-wide response and early gains from the implementation process. Conversely, uncertainties and ambivalence should be expected as the institutional culture may not be receptive or conducive to change or certain persons in the institution may find it difficult or slow to learning and developing new skills and knowledge. Effective risk management requires patience and persistence. When it comes to managing risk, there is never a perfect system and therefore, the approach should be to encourage inclusiveness and buy-in from every stakeholder while striving for perfection. Successful risk management is dependent on support from top-level management and commitment from all stakeholders. Other success drivers include but not limited to:

- Well-defined risk management mission, goals and objectives
- Collaboration with all top-level planning and budget approval processes
- Provision of adequate resources
- A well-defined risk appetite and tolerance
- Assigned oversight responsibilities
- Create a risk awareness culture and ensure a strong commitment within the institution
- Sustained and continuous program and process

It should be noted that sometimes, minor mistakes may unfortunately lead to pessimism and inappropriately lead to the abandonment of a promising and rewarding risk management process. Highlighted hereunder are some of the common pitfalls that should be avoided in order to achieve an effective risk management process:

- “Lack of or inadequate support from senior executives
- Resistance to accountability
- Institutional inability to make a long-term commitment
- Inability to commit the required resources
- Difficulty in devising metrics
- Challenge of communicating with faculty and staff
- Unclear/unrealistic expectations
- Lack of clear mission and goals
- Poor planning”.

(Gallagher, 1999: p.38).

The above listed are challenges that could derail the entire risk management process. It is essential to acknowledge these pitfalls and design ways to avoid these mistakes. There is no one-size-fit-all approach to an effective risk management approach. Thus, it should not be seen as a guarantee but rather a process because risk and uncertainty are dynamic and cannot be totally eliminated therefore, creating an enabling environment for the successful management of risk remains the best approach.

6.4 ORIGINALITY, CONTRIBUTION AND IMPLICATION TO STAKEHOLDERS

This study identified and addressed gaps as regards risk management in HEIs. There has been increase in studies in risk management from academic researchers and professionals alike across public, private and financial organisations while unfortunately there have been fragments of risk management studies in the academic sector across the world with non in the UK as at the time of commencing this research. Therefore, this research has contributed to the risk management literature in the academic sector by providing a new dimension and perspective into the risk management discourse.

Previous studies on the risk management architecture have had limitations because of the comprehensive nature of risk management several empirical studies only investigate a small aspect of the organisation risk management architecture which invariably have had some methodological limitations. Therefore, this study has contributed immensely to methodological

applications by adopting the mixed-methods approach (to which there has been a limited use in this field and non within the UK HEIs) to have a wider coverage of the implementation process, structures and practices in the investigation of risk management within HEIs. By adopting this theoretical approach, this research fulfilled the clamours for investigating control systems in operations (Otley, 1999) and utilising a more holistic methodology to organisational practices and studying risk from a wider cultural perspective (Lounsbury, 2008).

Empirical findings from this study have proven the need for a unique tailored risk management framework designed specifically for HEIs considering the unique culture and environment of HEIs which is totally different from any other public and private organisation. Therefore, the researcher intends to progress this study further by researching for the design of a unique risk management architecture for HEIs while also calling on researchers in this field to consider this objective. Therefore, the researcher believes this would be a useful contribution to HEIs, regulators as well as other major stakeholders because it would further enhance the effectiveness of their risk management process.

Risk management in the academic world is quite a new phenomenon and thus there has been no academic research to this effect in the UK prior to this study. Therefore, this research has comprehensively and critically evaluated and discussed all aspects of risk and risk management as it affects HEIs thus it would be useful to both HEIs and regulators as it would be a reference document for them to gauge their risk management processes and practices and understand how they might continuously improve on their risk management models. The researcher also believes that this study would motivate academics and future researchers to research further on risk management in the academic cycle.

6.5 WIDER IMPLICATION OF THIS STUDY BEYOND HEIS IN SCOTLAND

At the start of this study, the researcher defined the boundaries of the study as covering only HEIs within Scotland because of the separate legislation among HEIs across UK institutions. However, empirical findings from this research have revealed that majority of these findings are pertinent to every institution's risk management architecture. Therefore, the researcher is confident that HEI's in the UK and beyond would find recommendations in this research useful and effective to their risk management architecture.

Some of these recommendations as discussed in section 6.3 above include but not limited to:

- Broad and comprehensive categorisation of risk
- Consistent monitoring of internal and external environment (horizon scanning)
- Encourage buy-in and inclusiveness from all stakeholders
- Strike a balance between risk taking and risk avoidance
- Develop a disciplined process and encourage everyone within the institution to develop a culture of regularly monitoring risk
- Regular review of the risk management architecture
- Create a wider cross-functional Risk Management Committee/Group
- Develop and promote a risk language (themes) across the institution
- Ensure a continuous and cyclical risk management process
- The need for a unique risk management architecture tailored towards the needs and culture of HEIs.

6.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study ‘Conceptualising the impact of Risk Management in Scottish Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs)’ is a research that was carried out in Scotland. Because of some differences in regulations and funding bodies between Scottish Universities and other Universities across UK, therefore not every aspect of this study may be fit for generalisation across the entire UK Universities’ population except for Scottish Universities, although other UK HEIs and beyond may still find the recommendations from this research useful. Also, this research did not examine styles of leadership or managerial styles of persons responsible for managing risk within the case or surveyed institutions nor did it examine specific institution’s culture as it relates to risk management.

Furthermore, risk management in Universities is quite a new phenomenon thus research and literature in this area is relatively few across the academic world. Thus, it was quite challenging at the start of this research since there were very limited literature that would have ensured a better understanding and evaluation of the subject at the initial phase of the research. Furthermore, this study was restricted only to institutions with identified risk management program and only institutions with specified risk experts were interviewed, however, there were some challenges encountered as a result of time factor and difference in schedule with some of the respondents causing the researcher to change approach (i.e., including document analysis) in order to ensure reliability and validity of the research.

Finally, the current global pandemic (COVID-19) which was unexpected and took the world by storm meant that the researcher could no longer make use of academic resources as envisaged since institutions and libraries were abruptly locked down. Although fortunately, online resources and virtual meetings was a good alternative, however, there were instances where certain academic resources were practically not available online and only available on hard copies. More so, due to the lock down, it was extremely difficult getting feedback from participants as majority were working from home thus there were bound to be hitches and glitches from technicalities beyond control.

6.7 FINDINGS VS LITERATURE

Risk management is a new phenomenon in the HEI sector, thus there is not much literature in this area. However, from the few available literatures, there are quite a few findings from this research that identified some key differences with existing literature.

Findings from this study explicitly revealed that enhancement of decision-making is the overarching objective while HEI's have embraced risk management. This is against the opinion by (Power, 2009; Arena et.al., 2010) that firms often adopt risk management due to pressure from regulators and does not impact on managerial operations, activities and decisions. Although there were evidences of some coercive pressures from regulators, but it was not enough to conclude that HEIs have been coerced into adopting risk management frameworks. Conversely, findings from this study have also revealed that strategic decisions, goals and objectives of institutions is governed by risk management philosophy. Nevertheless, it would be unfair to dismiss the literature that institutions adopt risk management due to regulatory requirements, what findings from this research thus represent could be that institutions may have suddenly realised the importance and benefits of a coordinated risk management approach to their businesses.

Another interesting finding from this research is that there is an increased level of confidence from stakeholders on HEIs brought about by risk management which counters the assertion by Esaides (2013) that many organisations are weary of risk management because it has failed to convince them of its benefits other than presenting a catalogue of risk already known to them. This is also in contrast to findings from this research because this study has revealed that HEIs believe that regular risk identification process has enabled them to detect some key new and emerging risk that would have gone unnoticed and negatively impacted on their strategic goals and objectives.

Finally, there are also arguments from some quarters that analysis of risk would generally result in assumptions particularly when carried out by different groups. They further argued that placing much trust on quantitative measures (i.e., risk-scoring matrix, KPIs, risk-modelling etc.) could yield to wrong judgement of security because according to their opinion, uncertainty is not measurable therefore it would be wrong to convert it to risk that is measurable (Williamson, 2007; Koenig, 2008; Emblemvag, 2010). However, findings from this study revealed that risk-scoring matrices have been beneficial to institutions because it has helped decision-makers to identify key risks and channel resources and time towards such while other risks are being monitored thereby enabling institutions to be efficient and effective with their resources.

6.8 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Section 6.6 of this research identified limitations to this study which could be addressed in future research projects. Another key reflection for further research would be to examine how administrative bureaucracies due to compliance and risk management may impact and affect the teaching-research quality in HEIs. Again, findings from this study revealed that HEIs are in a fix due to Brexit uncertainty, this would present a great opportunity for researchers to examine the impact of Brexit to the strategic objectives and planning process of HEIs within UK and other European countries.

Furthermore, findings and discussions from this empirical research brought to the light the need for a tailored risk management framework for HEIs. Thus, this research has provided the foundation for the identification of main drivers of effective risk management in HEIs. Furthermore, the researcher is confident that empirical findings from this study would guide

the design of a development of a risk management system that would meet the specific needs of HEIs as discussed above. Therefore, the researcher would welcome studies on this objective. Finally, it would be a good idea if this study is also replicated in other UK regions.

6.9 PERSONAL REFLECTION

Risk and Risk Management has been an age-long tradition; however, its prominence came to the fore once again during the last financial crisis which coincided with the researcher's MSc programme in Financial Services, Risk and Operations. Ever since, the researcher has been keenly interested and involved in private sector risk management which led to him becoming a professional member of the Chartered Institute for Loans and Risk Management of Nigeria (CILRM) and also a member of the Global Association of Risk Professionals (GARP).

The researcher's interest regarding Risk Management (RM) in HEIs however, was aroused after reading an article which argued that introducing RM in HEIs would be counter-productive because it would distort and disorganise the system, structure and the culture of Universities (Huber, 2010). Upon further research, the researcher discovered that despite several studies on RM in private sector organisations, very limited empirical studies have been carried out regarding RM in Universities globally and with none so far published in the UK as at the time of commencing this study. This gap in literature further provoked the researcher's interest to investigate the RM practices and composition within UK HEIs.

Initially, the researcher was keen to undertake this investigation within the University of the West of Scotland only. But having held preliminary discussions with his supervisory team and further meetings with Director of Studies (DoS), the researcher began to understand the importance of generalisation and research validity. Thus, from the insightful comments and advice from the DoS, the researcher decided to extend the scope of the study to cover Universities in the UK. However, upon investigation, it was discovered that various regions within Britain have devolved powers over their educational system – thus legislation governing institutions within these countries were different. This meant that only HEIs in Scotland were included in the study.

Several challenges were encountered during the entire research process ranging from limited academic literature on the subject matter, unwillingness of some key respondents to take part

in the interview phase, technical issues – expiration of software licence (which took some time to be reactivated), to personal (health related) issues and above all the COVID 19 pandemic, which hampered the progress of the research against the planned timetable and some of these challenges brought the researcher to his lowest ebb to the point of almost giving up on the research completely. However, gainful support from close relatives and the encouragement from DoS brought back the zeal to see this research to a gainful conclusion.

Although, these challenges primarily delayed the conclusion of this study, it has however, greatly benefited the researcher both personally and professionally as it has tremendously improved his time-management skills. Specifically, the researcher became more disciplined during this process by avoiding all unnecessary activities and setting daily targets while at the same time making provisions for occasional study breaks in order to avoid being pressured and exhausted which could have affected the study negatively.

Having committed so much effort to ensure a successful completion of this dissertation, the researcher is very confident that several stakeholders within the educational sector and beyond would find this study useful in understanding and addressing challenges regarding risk and risk management particularly in this era of post-Brexit uncertainties. Also, the researcher is pleased to have been able to source information from risk experts of various case institutions which is an indication of high reliability and genuineness of data. More so, the sequential mixed-methods approach adopted in this research enhanced the study's validity since it allowed for data convergence (i.e., triangulation) enhancing credibility of findings (Greene, et.al., 1989; Hesse-Biber, 2010; Bryman, 2006) and also complementarity (Greene et.al., 1989) and completeness (Bryman, 2006) which enhances better understanding of the research problem. Additionally, it provided a holistic understanding of the research problem being that results from *“one method or phase helped developed or informed the other method”* (Greene et.al., 1989, p.259). Therefore, this research being the first of its kind within the UK academic sector, the researcher is optimistic that this study would spur researches on RM within the UK academic sector.

Despite the seemingly strengths of this study – some of which have been discussed above, the researcher is saddened by the inability to include all proposed institutions in the study. Although, this was no fault of the researcher, the researcher thinks it would had further enhanced the validity of the study. Nevertheless, despite the challenges encountered of not

being able to include all proposed Universities in this research, the researcher is pleased that all selected case institutions ticked all the boxes (in terms of geographical, structural and period of establishment) relevant to the reliability, validity and success of this research as observed in chapter 5, table 5.1. However, for greater reliability and validity of this study, the researcher decided to include document analysis as an additional source for data. Thus, the review of documents provided a genuine and a very rich source of information to the research objectives and also important for interview data triangulation (Bowen, 2009).

However, reflecting on the entire process, there are some aspects the researcher thought he could have handled differently if it is possible to turn back the hands of time. I admit to being somewhat a bit of a perfectionist which meant that during the majority part of this research I spent several time trying to perfect every detail of my work and write up. This often resulted in putting down so much information which sometimes became counter-productive as some of the information were either irrelevant or had the tendency to divert my attention from the research objectives. This entire research process has thought me that achieving perfection is not always realistic. Sometimes, it is best to decide what is important or necessary. In other words, there should be a limit or trade-off. Therefore, I have learnt to pace my work and also set guidelines in other not to get too involved in chasing perfection on every detail.

Again, because this is an academic research which is time-bound, some research techniques were deemed not suitable because of the time-horizon in conducting such. However, given the chance to conduct this study over again without time constraints, the researcher would like to conduct this piece through 'Observation'. This process would allow the researcher to observe first-hand the risk management process and frameworks and the risk culture of the various institutions, it would also help the researcher understand better the attitudes of the stakeholders towards the risk management process. The researcher believes this would have widened the scope of the research and also present more detailed result and provocation for further research.

Finally, the researcher is disappointed of the inability to have part of this research published or at least make a seminar presentation of the study. Although, the researcher had envisaged to both make a paper presentation and publication at the start of this research, but with several challenges encountered during the research process, these wishes never materialised. With vital knowledge gained during the course of this study – particularly time management skills and

priority setting as it concerns this discourse, the researcher is however certain that, if he were to undertake this study over again, these objectives would be achieved effortlessly.

6.10 FINAL REMARKS

The higher education sector over the years have greatly experienced a wave of change driven by the need to enhance and sustain quality and excellence. Consequences resulting from these changes according to HEFCE (2005, p.4) include: “*variable tuition fees, increased competition for students and changing student expectations; increased exposure and reliance on overseas markets, global competition and alliances; restructuring, investment in infrastructure, institutional expansion and large capital projects, commercialisation opportunities, and new and emerging technologies and involvement in partnership and associates*”. With these factors as well as several other challenges such as increased cost and uncertainty regarding financial aid or grants from government and other funding bodies have made universities to begin to recognise and embrace the importance of risk management in a competitive, global and dynamic environment.

Although, there is an increasing recognition of the importance of risk management among institutions, it is however arguable the level of commitment to effective risk management among some of these institutions because, it was observed during this study that some institutions do not regularly update their risk management framework and policy documents which is essential to effective risk management. For an effective risk management process, risk management activities must be regarded as vital and should be a culture that everyone is part of. According to Abraham (2013, p.5), “*good risk management is good governance*”. Therefore, risk management activities should not be passive but should be enshrined into the institution’s strategic objectives and driven by top-level management and should comprehensively capture all issues fundamental to the goals and strategic objectives of the institution.

The importance of risk management to HEIs cannot be over-emphasised. A sound risk management process allows institutions to take more calculated risk in a dynamic society, guarantees the efficient use of resources, eliminate regulatory fines for non-compliance, ensures early detection of warning signals, enhances effective communication across the institution, reduction in claims or operational losses, avoid surprises, solidifies and enhances integrity and reputation etc. Also, a good risk management process and practice would help to

reduce effects of media and public scrutiny which is always detrimental to university's reputation whenever there is a catastrophic event.

However, the future focus of this study is to investigate on how best to institutionalise risk management practices and processes into the basic fabrics and culture of the institution while also developing a risk management model or framework that is unique to the university environment as against the current generic frameworks that have been designed specifically for firms within the financial and non-financial organisations without considering the uniqueness of academic establishments.

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX 2.1 MAJOR EVENTS IN RISK MANAGEMENT EVOLUTION

1730	First futures contracts on the price of rice in Japan
1864	First futures contracts on agricultural products at the Chicago Board of Trade
1900	Louis Bachelier's thesis "Théorie de la Spéculation"; Brownian motion
1932	First issue of the <i>Journal of Risk and Insurance</i>
1946	First issue of the <i>Journal of Finance</i>
1952	Publication of Markowitz's article "Portfolio Selection"
1961-1966	Treynor, Sharpe, Lintner and Mossin develop the CAPM
1963	Arrow introduces optimal insurance, moral hazard, and adverse selection
1972	Futures contracts on currencies at the Chicago Mercantile Exchange
1973	Option valuation formulas by Black and Scholes and Merton
1974	Merton's default risk model
1977	Interest rate models by Vasicek and Cox, Ingersoll and Ross (1985)
1980-1990	Exotic options, swaptions and stock derivatives
1979-1982	First OTC contracts in the form of swaps: currency and interest rate swaps.
1985	Creation of the Swap Dealers Association, which established the OTC exchange standards
1987	First risk management department in a bank (Merrill Lynch)
1988	Basel I
Late 1980s	Value at risk (VaR) and calculation of optimal capital
1992	Article by Heath, Jarrow and Morton on the forward rate curve
1992	Integrated Risk Management
1992	RiskMetrics
1994-1995	First bankruptcies associated with misuse (or speculation) of derivatives: Procter and Gamble (manufacturer, rates derivatives, 1994), Orange County (management funds, derivatives on financial securities, 1994) and Barings (futures, 1995)
1997	CreditMetrics
1997-1998	Asian and Russian crisis and LTCM collapse
2001	Enron bankruptcy
2002	New governance rules by Sarbanes-Oxley and NYSE
2004	Basel II
2007	Beginning of the financial crisis
2009	Solvency II (not yet implemented in March 2013)
2010	Basel III

Source: Dionne (2013)

APPENDIX 2.2 FROM TRADITIONAL TO MODERN RISK MANAGEMENT – STAGES OF EVOLUTION

Source: Gallagher (2009)

APPENDIX 2.3: SAMPLE OF A 5 X 5 RISK MATRIX

		Impact →				
		Negligible	Minor	Moderate	Significant	Severe
Likelihood ↑	Very Likely	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi	High	High
	Likely	Low	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi	High
	Possible	Low	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi	Med Hi
	Unlikely	Low	Low Med	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi
	Very Unlikely	Low	Low	Low Med	Medium	Medium

Source: Boers (2017)

APPENDIX 2.4 STEPS IN RM WITH REGARDS TO IMPACT AND ACCEPTABLE LEVEL OF RISK.

Source: Fekete (2009).

APPENDIX 2.5: ELEMENTS OF AN INSTITUTION-WIDE RISK MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

Source: (HEFCE, 2005)

APPENDIX 2.6: SOME POTENTIAL CATEGORIES OF RISK THAT COULD AFFECT HEIS

Risk category	Sample risks
Hazard Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic terrorism • Catastrophic natural event • Pandemic
Financial Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conflicts of interest in financial transactions and agreements • Budget impairment • Ineffective service centre/auxiliary management
Information Technology Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unauthorised modification of data • Decentralisation of systems leading to data inconsistencies and fragmentation • Disclosure of confidential information.
Human Resource Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personnel issues or workplace violence • Professional liability claims • Workers compensation claims
Research Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research misconduct • Intellectual property infringement

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate lab process and practices for promotion of environmental health and safety.
Contract and Grant Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory fines or penalties • Non-compliance with sponsoring agency regulations and agreement terms and conditions • Cost sharing procedures are not compliant with federal requirements.
Student Life Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sports/Public event disturbances • Student mental health • Inappropriate athletic recruiting
Facilities and Maintenance Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deferred maintenance • Increased in energy costs • Equipment/facility malfunction

Source: Kageyama (2014)

APPENDIX 2.7: SOME MAJOR DEFINITIONS OF RISK

Reference	Definition
Lawrence (1976).	Risk is the measure of probability and the weight of undesired consequences.
Kaplan and Garrick (1981).	Risk equals the triplet (s_i, p_i, c_i) , where s_i is the set of scenarios, p_i is the likelihood of that scenario, and c_i is the consequence of the scenario, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$
Wilson and Crouch (1982)	Risk equals the product of probability and severity
Kumamoto and Henley (1996).	Risk is a combination of five primitives: outcome, likelihood, significance, causal scenario and population affected.
Rosa (1998).	Risk is a situation or event where something of human value (including humans themselves) has been put at stake and where the outcome is uncertain.
MIL-STD-882D (2000).	Risk is the expression of influence and possibility of an accident in the sense of the severity of the potential accident and the probability of the event.
Risk Management Vocabulary ISO (2002).	Risk is a combination of the probability and scope of the consequences.
IRGC (2005).	Risk is an uncertain consequence of an event or activity related to something of human value.
Campbell (2005).	Risk equals expected damage.
Law on Safety and Health at Work (2005).	Risk is the likelihood of an injury, disease or damage to the health of employees due to hazards.
Aven and Renn (2009)	Risk refers to uncertainty about and severity of the events and consequences (or outcomes) of an activity with respect to something that humans' value.
ISO (2009)	Risk is the effect of uncertainty on objectives.

Basel II (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2002)	Operational risk: The risk of loss resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems or from external events.
Federation of European Risk Management (FERMA, 2002)	An uncertain future outcome that can either Associations improve or worsen position – superseded by ISO 31000:2009
Solvency II (Groupe Consultatif Actuariel Européen, 2007).	<p>Compliance risk: legal or regulatory sanctions resulting in a financial loss, or loss of reputation as a result of an insurer's failure to comply with laws, regulations, rules, related self-regulatory organisation standards, and codes of conduct.</p> <p>Operational risk: change in value caused by the fact that actual losses, incurred for inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems, or from external events.</p>
Risk and Insurance Management Society (RIMS, 2012)	An uncertain future outcome that can either improve or worsen position.
Institute of Internal Auditors [IIA] (2013)	The possibility of an event occurring that will have an impact on the achievement of objectives, measured in terms of impact and likelihood.
Project Management Body of Knowledge [PMBOK] (Project Management Institute [PMI], 2013)	An uncertain event or condition, that, if it occurs, has a positive or negative effect on one or more project objectives.
National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, 2010)	Risk is a measure of the extent to which an entity is threatened by a potential circumstance or event, and a function of: (i) the adverse impacts that would arise if the circumstance or event occurs; and (ii) the likelihood of occurrence.
Open Compliance and Ethics Group [OCEG] (Mitchell, Switzer, & Mefford, 2015)	Risk identification: Identify forces that may cause desirable (opportunity) or undesirable (threat) effects on the achievement of objectives, as well as those that may compel the organization to conduct itself in a particular way (requirement).

Source: Šotić and Rajić (2015); Padro (2015).

APPENDIX 3.1: QUANTITATIVE SURVEY INSTRUMENT

Impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Inst.

Dear Sir/Madam,

You have been invited to participate in a research project titled “ *Conceptualising the impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs)*”. This survey is part of a dissertation study for the partial fulfilment of the Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) at University of the West of Scotland (UWS) for Augustine I. Egbele.

In this survey, risk managers with risk management responsibility in universities across Scotland will be asked questions about the decision-making and administrative processes regarding Risk Management (RM) at their institutions in order to gain insight into current RM practices in the higher education setting. Risk managers are those defined as leading the implementation of RM. Selected institutions will also participate in qualitative interviews.

The survey will take approximately 15 - 20 minutes to complete and answers from your questionnaires would be used solely for academic purpose and your response(s) will be kept anonymous – reason you have not been asked to include your name and address anywhere in the questionnaire and your participation in this study is completely voluntary.

There are no foreseeable risks associated with this project. However, if you feel uncomfortable answering any questions, you can withdraw from the survey at any point. Your survey responses will be strictly confidential and data from this research will be reported only in the aggregate. Your information will be coded and will remain confidential. If you have questions at any time about the survey or the procedures, you may contact me or my Director of Studies (DoS) with details provided below.

Thank you very much for your time and support. Please start with the survey now by clicking on the "Next" button below.

Kind Regards,

Augustine I. Egbele. BSc, MSc, BCPA, MCSI, CILRM.

Researcher: University of the West of Scotland,
School of Business and Enterprise,
Paisley Campus,
Paisley, PA1 2BE

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The School of Business and Enterprise,

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T: 0141 848 3465

Name of your Institution

Department

Designation

Q1. In line with regulatory bodies (such as: Higher Education Funding Council for England - HEFCE and Scottish Funding Council – SFC) guidelines on Internal control and a robust Risk Management framework, would you say your institution has a risk management program or framework in place?

- Yes - Fully Adopted
- Yes - But has not been fully incorporated
- No - But plans are underway (please go to question 4)
- No Have not given it a thought (please go to question 4)

Q2. If yes to question 1 above, what term would you use to describe your risk management framework

- Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)
- Strategic Risk Management (SRM)
- Integrated Risk Management (IRM)
- Other, Please state

Q3. Which of the following risk management framework has been adopted by your institution

- COSO ERM framework
- ISO 31000 framework
- Bespoke
- Other please specify

Q4. What would you consider the major driver for adopting a risk management framework in your institution (please select all applicable)

- Response to regulatory requirement
- Response to internal regulatory, legal or compliance failure
- To improve decision-making
- As a part of strategic planning
- Enterprise-wide assessment of major risks
- Board mandate
- Chancellor/President mandate
- Economic climate
- ERM awareness from conferences, journals, readings, colleagues
- Other please state

Q5. What action steps did your institution take when it adopted a risk management framework (select all that apply)?

- Consulted with colleagues at other institutions
- Literature review
- Attended conference sessions
- Engaged the services of consultants
- Other please state

Q6. Do you have a documented risk management policy?

- Yes

No (please go to question 8)

Q7. If yes to question 6, does your risk management policy include any of the following (please select all that apply)?

- Risk appetite
- Risk tolerance
- Risk criteria
- Risk target
- Risk limit
- None of the above

Q8. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The tolerance and risk appetite of the institution are clearly understood and are part of the institution's decision-making culture.	<input type="radio"/>				
In pursuing business objectives, decision-making in my institution is guided by events as they occur without much regard to the amount of risk the institution is willing to take.	<input type="radio"/>				
Operational and strategic decisions of the institution are guided by the institution's risk tolerance.	<input type="radio"/>				
I regard oversight of (enterprise) risk management as a priority at my institutions.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q9. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Senior administrators and Board members keenly and actively engage in discussions regarding risks affecting the institution.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q10. Discussion and consideration of institutional risks occur primarily in (check all that apply):

- Full Board meeting

- Finance committee meeting
- Audit committee meeting
- None of the above
- Other

Q11. Major risks to success of your institution's mission are identified through comprehensive, strategic risk assessments.

- Yes
- No (please skip to Q13)

Q12. If yes to Q11, when was the most recent comprehensive assessment carried out?

- Less than a year ago
- 1-2 years ago
- 3-4 years ago
- Over 5 years ago

Q13. Board members and senior administrators regularly evaluate major risks identified by the strategic risk assessment (please check all applicable options):

- Every board meeting
- Every year
- Every other year
- As needed
- None of the above
- Other

Q14. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The likelihood of expected and unexpected events are regularly assessed and considered by Senior administrators and Board members.	<input type="radio"/>				
Senior administrators and Board members will consider strategies such as: risk avoidance, risk mitigation, risk sharing and risk acceptance when responding to major risks relating to mission success.	<input type="radio"/>				
Board members and senior administrators identify activities needed to ensure that controls for major risks are put in place.	<input type="radio"/>				
Senior administrators and board members use monitoring tools and carry out activities to determine the effectiveness of the institution's risk management framework.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q15. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statement:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The risk management philosophy of the institution is captured in policy statements, oral and written communications, and decision making.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q16. How often are the following risks usually discussed during board meetings?

	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Routinely
Operational	<input type="radio"/>				
Legal and Regulatory	<input type="radio"/>				
Financial	<input type="radio"/>				
Reputational	<input type="radio"/>				
Strategic	<input type="radio"/>				
Political	<input type="radio"/>				

Q17. Who has been assigned with the primary responsibility for institutional risk management by the governing board?

- Principal

- Financial Officer
- Provost/VP academic affairs
- Chief legal counsel
- Chief compliance/audit officer
- Chief risk officer
- None
- Other

Q18. Kindly give your opinion on the level of agreement to the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The governing board monitors the institution's risk through regular and formal reports by the officer assigned with risk management responsibility.	<input type="radio"/>				
As a governing board member or senior administrator, I am adequately furnished with enough information on developments within the institution that may impact upon the risk profile of the establishment.	<input type="radio"/>				
The risk reports include consideration of emerging and/or changing risks.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q19. Overall, how would you rate your institution's approach to, and management of, major risks to the success of your institution's mission and objectives?

- Exemplar
- Above average
- Average
- Below average
- Poor

APPENDIX 3.2: QUALITATIVE SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. I would like to record the interview, so the study can be as accurate as possible. You may request that the recorder be turned off at any point of the interview.

1. How does your institution define Risk Management (RM)?
2. Is there a risk management framework and strategy in place which follows established risk management principles and supports the agreed risk policy and what term would you use to refer to such framework/process?
3. Can you please describe the decision-making process contained in your RM model?
4. Can you please describe the steps your institution took to implement a RM framework?
5. How is RM organized at your institution? Who are the key people? What are their roles and responsibilities?
6. How have you integrated RM into your overall governance, decision-making and strategic planning efforts?
7. Have management from across the college been involved in identifying and evaluating risk?
8. What is the relationship between your RM framework and your institution's mission, objectives and other processes?
9. Is there a programme of induction and regular training in place to ensure that managers across the institution have an adequate knowledge of risk management and how it is applied within the organisation?
10. How do you know if RM has reduced, mitigated, or controlled risk, created opportunity, enhanced financial viability and/or resulted in other positive factors for your institution?
11. What are your greatest challenges related to RM?
12. Has there been cynicisms, scepticisms or resistance emanating from any angle within the institution regarding RM management decisions?
13. Is there anything else about your ERM model or process that you think it is important for me to know?

APPENDIX 3.3: ETHICS APPROVAL LETTER

04/06/2018

Dear Augustine Egbele,

Your application 4763: Conceptualising the impact of Risk Management on UK Higher Educational Institutions, submission 3587, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr A Kourouklis

GLOSSARY

Term	Meaning/Definition
Inherent risk	Potential for waste, loss unauthorised use, or misappropriation due to the nature of an activity itself.
Level of risk	Magnitude of a risk or combination of risks, expressed in terms of consequences and their likelihood.
Risk	The threat or possibility that an action or event will adversely or beneficially affect an organisation's ability to achieve its objectives
Risk appetite	A broad amount of risk an entity is willing to accept in pursuit of its mission or vision.
Risk assessment	Risks are analysed, considering likelihood and impact, as a basis for determining how they should be managed. Risks are assessed on an inherent and a residual basis.
Risk criteria	Risk criteria is the terms of reference (standards, measures, or expectations) used in making a judgement or a decision on the significance of risk to be assessed. It may include: Associated cost and benefits, Legal and statutory requirements, and the concerns of stakeholders.
Risk culture	Risk culture is the system of values and behaviours present in an organisation that shapes risk decisions of management and employees.
Risk evaluation	Process of comparing the results of risk analysis with risk criteria to determine whether the risk and or its magnitude is acceptable or tolerable.
Risk Identification	Risk identification is the process of determining the risks that could potentially prevent the organisation from achieving its strategic goals and objectives.
Risk management	Coordinated activities to direct and control an organisation with regard to risk.
Risk management framework	Set of components that provide the foundations and organisational arrangements for designing, implementing, monitoring, reviewing, and continually improving risk management throughout the organisation.
Risk management policy	A statement of the overall intentions and directions of an organisation as regards risk management.
Risk management process	Systematic application of management policies procedures, and practices to the activities of communicating, consulting, establishing the context, and identifying, analysing, evaluating, treating, monitoring, and reviewing risks.
Risk matrix	A tool for ranking and displaying risks by defining ranges for consequences and likelihood.
Risk register	Record of information about identified risk.
Risk response	Management assesses the effect on risk likelihood and impact, as well as costs and benefits, selecting a response that brings residual risk within the desired risk tolerances.
Residual/Net risk	Residual or Net risk is considered to be the remaining risk, following management applying relevant control and mitigating action in line with the organisation's defined risk appetite.
Risk source	Element which alone or in combination has the intrinsic potential to give rise to risk.
Risk tolerance	This is the specific maximum risk that an organisation is willing to take as it relates to each individual risk.

Risk treatment	Process to modify risk.
Target risk	Target risk describes how much risk management is willing to accept in order to reach objectives. It helps define management's 'risk appetite'. Monitor progress on a regular basis (e.g., at regular management meetings) Target risk helps to ensure that risks are adequately managed.

Source: (COSO, 2004; ISO 2009; PKF, 2011)